

UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO
GRADUATE PROGRAM IN BIOINFORMATICS

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**BUILDING A BIOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE GRAPH VIA WIKIDATA WITH A
FOCUS ON THE HUMAN CELL ATLAS**

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**CONSTRUINDO UM GRAFO DE CONHECIMENTO BIOLÓGICO NO WIKIDATA
COM FOCO NO HUMAN CELL ATLAS**

Preliminary version

Advisor: Prof. Dr. Helder T. I. Nakaya

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2024

Ao Diógenes, que se foi, e à Rosalina, que chegou.

Acknowledgments - Agradecimientos

TODO

 PhD Thesis - Agradecimientos

Nothing in biology makes sense except in the light of cells

(Adapted from Theodosius Dobzhansky, who favored evolution.)

RESUMO

Lubiana, T. **Construindo um grafo de conhecimento biológico via Wikidata com foco no Human Cell Atlas**. 2024. Tese (Doutorado em Ciências) - Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, 2024.

Com os avanços do Human Cell Atlas e das tecnologias ômicas de células únicas (como o *single-cell RNA-seq*) houve um crescimento da necessidade de infraestruturas computacionais que capturem o conhecimento humano sobre os tipos celulares. O uso de sistemas formais de representação é indispensável, por exemplo, para a organização de bases de dados e a anotação de conjuntos de dados ômicos. O presente trabalho investiga o papel do grafos de conhecimento Wikidata nesse contexto, e é apresentado em cinco capítulos. O primeiro apresenta como a infraestrutura do Wikidata, alinhada à Wikipédia, pode ser útil para bioinformatas, gerando conjuntos de genes para o método de enriquecimento funcional. O seguinte apresenta a reconciliação da base de marcadores celulares PanglaoDB ao Wikidata e as vantagens do padrão ouro de *5-star linked open data*. Já o terceiro capítulo discute as definições de "tipo celular" e apresenta diretrizes sobre o que pode delimitar as classes de células cientificamente relevantes. O quarto capítulo apresenta um padrão sistemático, com as informações mínimas necessárias para catalogar um novo tipo celular, seja no Wikidata, seja na Cell Ontology, o recurso de referência para tipos celulares no Human Cell Atlas. Por fim, o último capítulo apresenta um sistema para catálogo de tipos celulares no Wikidata e seu uso para tornar o Wikidata o maior catálogo multi-espécies de tipos de células, com identificadores únicos para mais de 6000 tipos celulares. A velocidade, flexibilidade e colaboratividade do Wikidata fazem da plataforma um recurso estratégico para os sistemas de informação sobre tipos celulares. Apresentamos também como os dados do Wikidata são conectados ao Cell Ontology , garantindo a contribuição da plataforma para o estado-da-arte do catálogo formal de informações sobre tipos celulares, propiciando a anotação dos conjuntos de dados das ômicas de células únicas no Human Cell Atlas.

Palavras-chave: Wikidata, Human Cell Atlas, Cell Ontology, grafo de conhecimento, tipo celular, transcriptômica, ontologia computacional

ABSTRACT

Lubiana, T. **Building a biological knowledge graph via Wikidata with a focus on the Human Cell Atlas**. 2024. Tese (Doutorado em Ciências) - Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, 2024.

With advances in the Human Cell Atlas and single-cell omics technologies such as single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq), there has been an increasing need for computational infrastructures that capture comprehensive knowledge about cell types. Formal representation systems are indispensable for organizing databases and annotating omics datasets. This work investigates the role of Wikidata knowledge graphs in this context and is structured across five chapters. The first chapter introduces how Wikidata's infrastructure, aligned with Wikipedia, can be a valuable resource for bioinformaticians, discussing the generation of gene sets for functional enrichment methods. The second chapter presents the integration of the PanglaoDB cell marker database with Wikidata, highlighting the benefits of adopting the 5-star linked open data gold standard. The third chapter delves into the definitions of "cell type" and provides guidelines for distinguishing scientifically relevant cell classes, clarifying the criteria for classifying cell types. The fourth chapter proposes a systematic standard outlining the minimum necessary information required to catalog a new cell type, applicable to both Wikidata and the Cell Ontology, the reference resource for cell types in the Human Cell Atlas. The final chapter introduces a system for cataloging cell types within Wikidata, showcasing how Wikidata can become the largest multi-species catalog of cell types, with unique identifiers for over 6000 cell types, emphasizing Wikidata's speed, flexibility, and collaborative potential as a strategic resource for cell type information systems. Additionally, the work explains how data from Wikidata is connected to the Cell Ontology, ensuring the platform's contribution to the state-of-the-art formal catalog of cell type information and facilitating the annotation of single-cell omics datasets within the Human Cell Atlas.

Keywords: Wikidata, Human Cell Atlas, Cell Ontology, knowledge graph, cell type, transcriptomics, computational ontology

ABBREVIATIONS

CL - Cell Ontology

GO - Gene Ontology

GSEA - Gene Set Enrichment Analysis

HCA - Human Cell Atlas

HuBMAP - Human BioMolecular Atlas Project

KG - Knowledge Graph

LLM - Large Language Model

MIRACL - **M**inimal **I**nformation **R**eporting **A**bout a **C**ell

OWL - Web Ontology Language

OBO - Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies

RDF - Resource Description Framework

W3C - World Wide Web Consortium

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1. Preface

The present thesis was written among certain events that explain its unconventional format. First and foremost, it was a venture into a nascent branch of biocuration, for which there is still little development in Brazil. To think about biocuration is to enter deeply interdisciplinary realms, requiring flexibility to learn not only the biology of cells and the tools of the single-cell RNA-seq trade but also read, learn, and apply the literature on software development, ontology engineering, standard identifications, the philosophical underpinnings of cell classification and sociotechnical models for open knowledge sharing and integration.

Coming from a bioinformatics background, a lot of this was new to me. For that reason, this PhD project had many different lines open at every moment, and this is reflected in the multi-subject nature of the thesis. Many of the investigations, especially related to the metascientific use of Wikidata, were left out of the main text so as to provide a more concise, coherent picture of the scientific work we undertook.

A second collection of events of a personal nature also explains the variety of directions. Most of the work was done remotely during the COVID-19 pandemic, which somewhat disconnected the project from the activities of colleagues analyzing single-cell RNA-seq data. It also added a few constraints on planning and focus as the pandemic took up the scientific stage. To add to the oddities, the untimely death of a dear colleague, Diógenes, brought grievance and confusion. Other, more joyful life events also have their impact: I met my wife on a plane, got married a year later, and now we are raising a beautiful daughter.

This series of life events is perhaps not unusual, but these ever-changing personal settings are naturally reflected in a change of focus, priorities, and plans, which consequently affects the way this project underwent. This is to justify the unorthodox development of the work over the past four years, mixing methods from the humanities, the computer sciences, and biology. However erratic, I believe we have

managed to connect the dots in a way that reflects what we tried to do from the beginning: study the classification of cells into types in the context of the Human Cell Atlas and suggest sociotechnical ways to improve the state-of-the-art using computational ontologies and the framework of Wikidata.

Tiago Lubiana

2. Introduction

2.1 The Human Cell Atlas

In his 2022 bestseller titled "The Song of the Cell," Siddhartha Mukherjee asserts that if the 20th century was the century of genes, the 21st century is the century of cells. In medicine, therapies based on modified cells, such as chimeric antigen receptor T cells (CAR-T), stem cell therapies, and CRISPR cell reprogramming, bring formidable advances to human health. (MUKHERJEE, 2023) In basic research, the advent of single-cell omics—especially RNA sequencing—opens new research avenues, providing unprecedented details on cellular diversity. In this zeitgeist, the Human Cell Atlas (HCA) emerges, an international, multicentric, and collaborative consortium aimed at characterizing different types of human cells in detail. (REGEV et al., 2017)

The HCA is a game-changer for the biomedical sciences, crafting tools, setting standards for basic research, and facilitating a comprehensive characterization of diseases, ultimately enhancing diagnostics and therapeutic strategies. For this large-reaching effort to be a complete success, its data products need to embody the FAIR principles: being findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. (WILKINSON et al., 2016, p. 201) With an increased emphasis on data stewardship and data management, the scientific community is rapidly adapting to these core demands, improving the standards used to organize scientific outputs. The HCA grows through community interactions and states in its opening paper that "As with

the Human Genome Project, a robust plan will best emerge from wide-ranging scientific discussions and careful planning." (REGEV et al., 2017) Thus, this project inserts itself among the wide-ranging scientific discussions to improve knowledge interoperability within the Atlas.

With the vast volume of data generated by the HCA, efficient knowledge management strategies are crucial. One approach includes extensive use of ontologies to annotate datasets and consolidate information. Ontologies, in this context, are precise computational representations of reality, attempting to encapsulate concepts and their relationships accurately. (SCHULZE-KREMER; SMITH, 2005) These formal concepts are used by data annotators to improve the interoperability of data and are at the core of minimal information schemas, such as the minSCe (Minimum Information about a Single-Cell Experiment) guidelines. (FÜLLGRABE et al., 2020)

The annotation of metadata at the cell level presents itself as a socio-technical challenge, and as of 2021, an estimated 75% of published single-cell RNA-seq datasets did not contain proper metadata.

The technical challenges of the Human Cell Atlas have included theoretical problems since its inception. One of the main challenges lies in the very definition of "cell type" and the foundation of information systems capable of representing this diversity. (CLEVERS et al., 2017; DIEHL et al., 2016; LUBIANA; NAKAYA, 2021; OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021) The problem of defining concepts has significant philosophical dimensions (GUPTA; MACKERETH, 2023), and a grounded approach can aid in the development of models and theories about cells. This will be discussed in more depth in the introduction of the chapter on the classification of cell types.

As a sample of the philosophical challenges, it is notable that the Human Cell Atlas does not even estimate the order of magnitude of the number of human cell types (Aviv Regev, personal communication, Human Cell Atlas General Meeting 2023). In

the literature, an estimate by Stephen Quake for an upper limit on the number of cell types is argued based on personal intuitions such as "textbooks place the number of cells around 300 [...] It seems impossible to me that they have overlooked more than 95% of what there is to see [...], so the upper limit of cell types to be discovered is around 6000 (i.e., $300/0.05$)."

(QUAKE, 2021) On the other hand, in a lecture at the Institute of Chemistry of the University of São Paulo in 2024, Australian researcher John Mattick stated that, in his opinion, there are 80 trillion human cell types, corresponding to each decision made during development (personal communication), which is roughly the same order of magnitude as the total number of cells in an adult human. (HATTON et al., 2023)

These theoretical challenges reverberate into practical challenges of information systems and data set annotation. The gold standard of such systems is based on unique identifiers for concepts (unambiguous alphanumeric codes assigned by expert committees) arranged hierarchically. (MCMURRY et al., 2017) Regarding cell types, the identifiers for cell types used by Human Cell Atlas members are provided by the Cell Ontology (CL), a constantly updated computational ontology, a method for knowledge organization presented in the next section.

2.2 Ontologies, OBO Foundry and biocuration

Our academic interest in the knowledge infrastructure of the Human Cell Atlas inevitably led us to the philosophical realm of classification theories and the field of computational ontologies. The classification of biological concepts is at the core of biology. At least since the Aristotelian endeavors to group classes of animals, a good part of the scientific work is based on the capture of concepts into knowledge systems. (SCHULZE-KREMER; SMITH, 2005) Linnaeus' binomial system for naming species and Mendeleev's periodic table are likely the two most famous classification systems but are part of a much larger ecosystem of structuring scientific knowledge.

In the 20th century, the development of the analytical philosophy of Russell and Wittgenstein and their search for formalizations gradually laid the foundations for the logic of scientific descriptions. (KLEMENT, 2020) Karl Popper and his “The Logic of Scientific Discovery” (*Logik der Forschung*) were heavily influenced by analytical philosophy. (POPPER, 1934) Less known among life scientists, Tarski’s inquiries on what can be considered to be “true” (TARSKI, 1944) were also foundational for formal ontologies. At the end of the 20th century, the tradition of analytic philosophy contributed to the rise of applied ontology, which provided the theoretical basis for the computational ontologies of the early 21st century. (MUNN; SMITH, 2008)

A computational ontology, or simply ontology, as used here, is a formal computational representation of reality that tries to represent concepts (and their relations) as precisely as possible. (SCHULZE-KREMER; SMITH, 2005)

Constructing an ontology is a process of selecting and defining terms of interest, selecting and defining relationships of interest, and making statements about reality using terms and relationships. The Gene Ontology is probably the most well-known biomedical ontology; it describes (among other things) different classes of biological processes related to each other by “is_a” and “part_of” relations. (ASHBURNER et al., 2000; THE GENE ONTOLOGY CONSORTIUM et al., 2023, p. 202)

Most bioinformaticians have, at some point, dealt with the Gene Ontology. This resource was one of the first computational ontologies to become mainstream, as it fitted the boom of genome sequencing in the early 2000's. (ASHBURNER et al., 2000; THE GENE ONTOLOGY CONSORTIUM et al., 2023, p. 202) The Gene Ontology knowledgebase in 2023 contains more than just a computational ontology artifact. The GO Consortium hosts a rich web interface and a wealth of Gene Ontology annotations mappings of gene products to ontology concepts, enabling computerized insights leveraging the collective knowledge of genes. They are annotated to terms under three hierarchies describing the activities at the molecular level, the intracellular locations, and the biological programs. Through manual curation over the years, the Gene Ontology Consortium presents a glance at the

power of biocuration and how science benefits from organized, machine-readable standards.

Though immensely useful, the Gene Ontology is but one of the hundreds of federated ontologies under the Open Biomedical and Biological Ontologies (OBO) Foundry hat. (THE OBI CONSORTIUM et al., 2007) Established in 2007, the OBO Foundry is a central repository of biomedical ontologies that provides guidelines for designing and constructing high-quality ontologies. The initial OBO Foundry unified several independent ontologies like the Cell Ontology (CL), the Disease Ontology (DO), and the Protein Ontology (PRO) - in addition to the Gene Ontology, of course - under a common framework. They share technical components (for example, reliance on the OWL format and use of the Basic Formal Ontology as an upper ontology) but also social components, agreeing, for example, that each theoretical domain should be cataloged under one single ontology, avoiding redundancy. (ARP; SMITH; SPEAR, 2015; JACKSON et al., 2021)

2.2.1 OWL and ontology languages

One of the OBO Principles for its ontologies is that they should be resolvable as a “syntactically valid OWL file using the RDF/XML syntax.”¹ The OWL Web Ontology Language was introduced as a standard by the W3C consortium in 2004. OWL is not a programming language, as it does not instruct computers to perform actions, but an ontology language, which allows computable descriptions of the world. Furthermore, it is an umbrella ontology language that includes several languages with varying levels of expressivity. Generally, more expressive languages can represent more complex ideas but make computations harder.

Regardless of ontology’s sublanguage, it must be resolvable to an RDF/XML file. RDF stands for Resource Description Framework, another W3C standard built around a graph-based data model.² Statements in RDF are triples consisting of 2

¹ obofoundry.org/principles/fp-002-format.htm

² w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/

nodes (a subject and an object) and an edge (a predicate) connecting the nodes. All nodes and edges are represented in RDFs by International Resource Identifiers (IRIs), and there are many ways to lay out those IRIs on a text file to represent triples. One of those layouts is the RDF-XML syntax, inspired by the XML markup language. Arguably, other syntaxes (interchangeable with RDF-XML) are easier to read for a human. As an example of an RDF triple, here is how one would represent in the Turtle RDF Syntax, the notion that plasmacytoid dendritic cells are a type of dendritic cells:

```
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000784  
http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#subClassOf  
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000451 .
```

Where `http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000784` and `http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000451` are the unique IDs in the Cell Ontology for *plasmacytoid dendritic cell* and *dendritic cell*, respectively, and `http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#subClassOf` is the identifier for the *subclass of* relation as defined by the RDF schema. All ontologies in the OBO Foundry conform to that way of organizing knowledge about the world.

The use of common formats and a common framework makes it possible for OBO ontologies to be interoperable, reusing terms from each other, in adherence to the FAIR principles. In the workflow of maintaining and editing OBO ontologies, a number of different tools are used for managing the RDF files and ensuring their proper syntax, logical consistency and adherence to standards. These includes the Protégé software, a graphical interface to build ontologies, (MUSEN, 2015), and the Ontology Development Kit³ for executing ontology engineering workflows. (MATENTZOGLU et al., 2022a) These tools, alongside the GitHub system for managing source code, form the basis of how OBO Foundry ontologies are developed and maintained.

³ github.com/INCATools/ontology-development-kit

2.2.2 The Cell Ontology

Among the many ontologies relevant to the Human Cell Atlas, the Cell Ontology (the ontology of cell types) probably is the one of most immediate relevance. (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021) The CL was created in 2004 with the goal of capturing and formalizing the field of cell-type knowledge for use in information systems, a goal that persists.⁴ (BARD; RHEE; ASHBURNER, 2005) The advancement of experimental methods has fostered philosophical discussions directly aimed at data representation in the CL. (AEVERMANN et al., 2018; ANDO; KWON; SHIN, 2020) Currently, the CL team (of which the candidate is a part) is discussing the representation of cell states (e.g., "proliferating fibroblast") and which phenotypic aspects are, or are not, valid for determining new cell types.

By 2011, the demand for computable definitions resulted in an increase in the number and quality of immune cell types represented in CL. (MEEHAN et al., 2011, p. 20) Over the years, the development of the Cell Ontology included both technical enhancements and the addition of new cell types. As of the last official CL publication in 2016, it featured approximately 2,200 classes. (DIEHL et al., 2016, p. 1) Today, the Cell Ontology continues to expand as a resource for the Human Cell Atlas, providing identifiers for cell types, and now encompasses over 2,500 cell classes. (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021)

Besides the Human Cell Atlas Data Coordination platform, the Cell Ontology is used by a number of core resources for life scientists, including the EBI Single Cell Expression Atlas (PAPATHEODOROU et al., 2020) and the cellxgene resource (CZI SINGLE-CELL BIOLOGY PROGRAM et al., 2023). It is also used in entrepreneurial

⁴ The first article about the cell ontology also expressed an educational desire for the ontology, enabling researchers to "learn a considerable amount about that cell type and its relationships to other biological objects". (BARD; RHEE; ASHBURNER, 2005)

settings in data pipelines of commercial companies, such as the ontology-based data management system of Novo Nordisk.⁵ (TAN et al., 2024)

While ontologies are powerful tools, they demand a high level of technical expertise to get started. Recently, the dawn of collaborative knowledge graphs has given rise to a new methodology for formal knowledge representation: collective, low-barrier buildup in Wiki format run by the Wikimedia Foundation and with close ties to Wikipedia: Wikidata. (WAAGMEESTER et al., 2019) This knowledge graph, built collectively under support from the Wikimedia Foundation, encourages users to contribute classes and statements, aligning with Wikipedia's ethos of communal wisdom and its epistemic virtues of power, speed, and availability. (FALLIS, 2008a)

2.3 Wikidata in the biomedical research ecosystem

Wikidata is the general purpose, collaboratively edited, public domain knowledge graph of the Wikimedia Foundation created in 2013. (VRANDEČIĆ; PINTSCHER; KRÖTZSCH, 2023) With a community of over 46,000 active monthly editors and attracting 420 million views per month, it covers an expansive range of concepts far beyond the reach of any individual user. Wikidata is also speedy because it requires no software installation or permissions to update: any user can simply make changes via a web interface. This speed makes it more accessible for newcomers to join and contribute, a stark contrast to the OBO Foundry ontologies that necessitate extensive semantic training and knowledge of Git/GitHub for contributions.

Wikidata's information is readily available through a user interface, a SPARQL query service, and as comprehensive database dumps, ensuring full-scale reusability. Its CC0 public domain license waiver guarantees this reusability in all settings. The success of the Wikidata model led Google to migrate its own knowledge base,

⁵ As a note, a former colleague from the Nakaya Lab, Cesar Prada, is currently working at Novo Nordisk, and has worked with the Cell Ontology in their pipeline alongside Shawn Tan, the first author of the linked reference.

Freebase, entirely into Wikidata. (PELLISSIER TANON et al., 2016) Wikidata has now been integrated into workflows by major organizations like Amazon, OpenAI, Twitter, Apple, The Met and Smithsonian museums, and more. (VRANDEČIĆ; PINTSCHER; KRÖTZSCH, 2023)

Even before this PhD project started, several advancements had been made toward biological data integration and analysis in Wikidata. The work of the GeneWiki and related teams had demonstrated its potential for bioinformatics-related analyses, such as drug repurposing and ID conversion (Mitraka et al., 2015; Waagmeester et al., 2020). With over 50,000 human gene items indexed and hundreds of biomedical-related properties, Wikidata had already been proposed as a unified base for collecting and disseminating biomedical knowledge (Turki et al., 2019).

During the past four years, Wikidata continued to show its value for the biomedical research landscape, both through collaborations that stemmed from this PhD project and by independent teams.⁶ Developments included several works related to Wikidata and the Covid-19 pandemic and its role in organizing the knowledge acquired quickly in the first months of the crisis. (SAORÍN; PASTOR-SÁNCHEZ; BAÑOS-MORENO, 2020, 2020; TURKI et al., 2022a, 2022b; WAAGMEESTER et al., 2021a) Other instances that illustrate the interplay include the use of Wikidata as a database for natural products (RUTZ et al., 2022), the connection information from Wikipathways and Complex Portal to the platform (MARTENS et al., 2020; MELDAL et al., 2021) and featuring on the *Plos Computational Biology* "Ten Quick Tips" series (SHAFEE et al., 2023). It even became integrated directly into the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics semantic data pipelines (SIB SWISS INSTITUTE OF BIOINFORMATICS RDF GROUP MEMBERS et al., 2023).

⁶ For clarity, the author of this thesis has participated in the work and articles related to WikiProject COVID-19, to the connection of Complex Portal with Wikidata and the writing of the Plos Ten Quick Tips article.

2.3.1 How knowledge is organized inside Wikidata

Wikidata uses the same framework (RDF) that powers ontologies, though it is hidden behind a graphical user interface. Like RDF documents, Wikidata's data model represents statements about the world in triples containing a subject, a property and an object.⁷ Its data model is serialized both in JSON and RDF. The data model contains 17 different data types, including, for example, *Item*, an entry on Wikidata that refers to “a real-world object, concept, or event that is given an identifier in Wikidata” and *String*, a “sequence of freely chosen characters interpreted as text”.⁸ Knowledge is stored on Wikidata upon basic triples containing a subject (of type “Item”), a property and a value (which can be of any of the 17 types). As of November 2021, Wikidata contains more than 110 million data items and more than 10 000 properties that link them to values. As values often are other items, the database acquires a network format with labeled edges.

As seen in the example in Figure {{douglas_adams}}, each of the items in the database contains an item identifier (Q followed by numbers). They also contain a label, a description, and a list of aliases, which can be recorded in more than 200 hundred languages, making it a multilingual project.⁹ Each item is decorated with statements comprising property-value pairs. These pairs can be further specified via qualifiers and references, which treat the full triple as the subject, adding metadata to it (a process called *reification*). Qualifiers provide ways to extend the information on the triple, while references provide provenance, enabling users to judge the validity of the claims in the database.

⁷ mediawiki.org/wiki/Wikibase/DataModel

⁸ wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Data_type

⁹ wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Multilingual

Figure {{douglas_adams}}: Wikidata’s model for describing an item. Image released in Public Domain by Charlie Kritschmar.

All the information is available on a user interface and programmatically. Advanced users can download dumps in JSON and RDF dumps and access the data via the MediaWiki API and a SPARQL endpoint.¹⁰ Several wrappers of such services are available in languages such as R and Python. The data scheme can be seen in Figure {{wikidata_data_model}}|, where each item is connected to a statement node via a property in the “p:” namespace, from which references and qualifiers are accessible. To facilitate primary usage, the namespace “wdt:” connects items to values directly, simplifying, for example, the writing of SPARQL queries.

¹⁰ wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Data_access

Figure {{wikidata_data_model}}: Wikidata's inner data model. Scheme released under the CC-BY 4.0 license by Michael F. Schönitzer. It outlines the primary representation of statements, qualifiers and values in the Wikidata database.

Information on Wikidata is released under a CC0 license, which enables full reuse of the data.¹¹ One of the major points of access and reuse of the information is the Wikidata Query Service,¹² a core resource of the community that enables live querying in the SPARQL language. A number of services make use of embedded queries from the Wikidata Query Service to create interactive, live dashboards such as the Scholia platform for navigating the bibliometric landscape on the platform, which provides profiles of pre-templated SPARQL queries for particular authors and articles (e.g. Scholia profile on Prof. Helder Nakaya available at

¹¹ wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Licensing

¹² query.wikidata.org/

[/scholia.toolforge.org/author/Q42614737](https://scholia.toolforge.org/author/Q42614737)). (NIELSEN; MIETCHEN; WILLIGHAGEN, 2017; RASBERRY et al., 2019)

Wikidata does not have a predefined upper ontology by design, and the structure of data grows collaboratively. No mandatory schemas exist for any objects, and structure is maintained based on convention. With time, Wikidata was updated to include EntitySchemas, a system that uses ShapeExpressions (ShEx) to enable data validation and test conformity to a standard. The system, as of 2024, is still not mandatory, but has been gaining maturity and has already been tested in academic contexts. (HOSSEINI BEGHAEIRAVERI et al., 2023; LABRA-GAYO, [s.d.]; WAAGMEESTER et al., 2021b)

Wikidata is accessible and writable in many ways. It provides a user-friendly, point-and-click interface for modifying the database, providing low entry barriers for newcomers. It is also possible to semi-automatically reconcile spreadsheets to Wikidata items and use batch tools such as Open Refine¹³ and Quickstatements¹⁴, which enable batches on the magnitude of thousands of edits. For larger amounts of edits, it is possible to ask for bot permissions and deploy systems that integrate big data sources.¹⁵ Bot edits are made via the Wikimedia API and are predominantly written via Python wrappers, such as Pywikibot¹⁶ and the Wikidata Integrator.¹⁷

2.3.2 Wikidata as a knowledge graph for the life sciences

Due to its privileged position inside the linked data ecosystem and its ease of writing and querying, Wikidata has been growing as a hub for interoperable data for the life sciences community. (WAAGMEESTER et al., 2020) Even though Wikidata was created in 2013, the demand for a community-cured life sciences knowledge graph is apparent at least since 2008 with the WikiProteins project. (MONS et al., 2008; WALDROP, 2008) This Wikimedia-independent Wikidata-like project was proposed

¹³ wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/OpenRefine

¹⁴ wikidata.org/wiki/Help:QuickStatements

¹⁵ wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Bots

¹⁶ github.com/wikimedia/pywikibot

¹⁷ github.com/SuLab/WikidataIntegrator

by was eventually discontinued, an example of the challenge of maintaining independent biomedical databases.¹⁸ (HELMY; CRITS-CHRISTOPH; BADER, 2016) As Wikidata has a very large community, has stable funding and is at the core of modern technologies, like the Google Knowledge Graph, Apple's Siri and Amazon's Alexa, it is virtually guaranteed that data in Wikidata will remain accessible for a long time, regardless of local funding schemes.(VRANDEČIĆ; PINTSCHER; KRÖTZSCH, 2023)

The Gene Wiki project was likely the first large-scale biomedical project to rely directly on Wikipedia's infrastructure for community curation. (Huss et al., 2008) It provided a direct connection between the generalist community of Wikipedia and domain experts. The interplay of both communities is a topic of discussion and the opportunities and challenges were already discussed in NAR in 2012. (FINN; GARDNER; BATEMAN, 2012)

Wikidata appeared chronologically after the Gene Wiki project, and was embraced by it due to its potential for data interoperability. (BURGSTALLER-MUEHLBACHER et al., 2016; PUTMAN et al., 2019, 2017) The information on Wikidata is still integrated to Wikipedias across multiple languages, often a source of information in Wikipedia's infoboxes.

Other projects outside the Gene Wiki initiative also started using Wikidata as a platform for knowledge integration. A list of several projects that use Wikidata as part of their service to their community is given in Table {{projects_on_wikidata}}. There is also a movement exploring how Wikidata can be employed to advance Computational Biology and how it can be integrated to the current publication status quo.(BUCUR et al., 2023; "Submit a Topic Page to PLOS Computational Biology and Wikipedia | PLOS Computational Biology", [s.d.]

Table {{projects_on_wikidata}}

¹⁸ The project was signed by several prominent characters, including the founder of Wikipedia Jimmy Wales, the founder of SwissProt Amos Bairoch, the founder of the European Bioinformatics Institute Michael Ashburner and the head of the Scielo publishing platform Abel Packer.

name	project website
LOTUS	https://lotus.naturalproducts.net/
GeneDB	https://www.genedb.org/
Cellosaurus	https://web.expasy.org/cellosaurus/
Complex Portal	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/complexportal/
WikiPathways	https://www.wikipathways.org/
Reactome	https://reactome.org/
CIViC	http://www.civicdb.org
PubChem	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov
Human Disease Ontology	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/doid

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Wikidata has spawned as a hotspot for modeling information about the virus and the pandemic in real-time. The general scope of the database allowed representation in a shared system of molecular, epidemiologic and socio-economic aspects of the pandemic. Information curated in Wikidata was immediately available, feeding live dashboards and other applications based on SPARQL queries. Additionally, as the information presented on Wikidata is multilingual and collaboratively edited, it presented itself as a resource for constructing structured vocabularies in non-English languages. (ARAKAKI; CASTRO; ARAKAKI, 2020; SAORÍN; PASTOR-SÁNCHEZ; BAÑOS-MORENO, 2020; TURKI et al., 2022a, 2022b; WAAGMEESTER et al., 2021a)

In addition to its value as a structured database, Wikidata is tightly connected to Wikipedia. The gene identifiers in the context of Gene Wiki are now fed to Wikipedias across languages, benefitting users directly. Additionally, gene expression information from the Bgee database (BASTIAN et al., 2021) was added to Wikidata and connected to Wikipedia, which led to a sizable increase of access to the Bgee database. Currently, Wikipedia is one of the top 3 sources from which

people access Bgee (Tarcisio Farias, personal communication), thus leading to direct recognition for integrated bases. More generally, the connections of Wikidata and Wikipedia make it unique in the power of flowing knowledge back to human-accessed interfaces. In the words of Matthias Samwald and colleagues, “Wikidata could emerge as a community-backed and highly visible structured knowledge base of medical and biological information, bringing concepts and methodologies such as controlled taxonomies, Semantic Web / semantic technologies and ontologies into mainstream use.” (PFUNDNER et al., 2015)

Wikidata’s unique position, robustness and guarantee of long term stability prompts the need for works exploring new ways of integrating it into current knowledge management systems. In light of the speed and breadth of the Human Cell Atlas and the challenges of knowledge representation on cells, this PhD works on addressing how Wikidata can play a role in organizing the discoveries about all human cell types.

2.4 Wikidata, OBO Foundry and large language models

When this PhD project started, ChatGPT had not been publicized and the powerful generative artificial intelligence models, in particular the large language models (LLMs), were still far from the performance metrics they achieved in 2024. Current LLMs are able to process an immense amount of texts and parse complex information, reaching expert-level performance in several tasks, including scientific reasoning. (NAVEED et al., 2024) The wide range applications - and implications - of LLMs gave rise to a number of publications on the topic, be it in the relation to bioinformatics (LUBIANA et al., 2023), to ontology management (TORO et al., 2023) or to Wikidata. (LAYEGH et al., 2024)

It is still early to gauge the impact of ChatGPT and related LLM technologies in the knowledge engineering landscape. It is a possibility that some of the arguments presented for the value of ontologies and the Wikidata knowledge graph won't continue to be as strong in the future as they are now. The current discussions,

however, point to a synergy between knowledge graphs (KGs) and large language models, where LLMs facilitate the process of ontology-building (TORO et al., 2023) and, more generally, streamline the creation of knowledge graphs. (PAN et al., 2024)

Besides helping to create KGs, including Wikidata, ontologies and other KGs, are being used to improve the performance of these models, as in the case of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) pipelines, that combine a KG search result into LLM prompts to increase performance. (PAN et al., 2024) This interplay extends even to life sciences companies, as explicitly detailed in the white paper about the ontology-based data management system of Novo Nordisk, leveraging OBO Foundry ontologies in integration with generative AI models.¹⁹ (TAN et al., 2024) Thus, it seems reasonable to believe that the discussions and tools built in this project and discussed in the thesis will still be relevant in the future.

2.5 Objectives

This project's goal is to bridge the progress of collaborative knowledge modeling on Wikidata with the scientific endeavor of the Human Cell Atlas. We are reviewing the single-cell literature, refining and formalizing concepts for cell type delineation, and exploring their application in the Wikidata database. Simultaneously, we are investigating how the Wikidata knowledge system can be integrated with the OBO Foundry to improve the coverage and quality of multiple ontologies. The objectives of the project have evolved over time and currently can be better summarized as:

- Analyze and supplement the community-built data model to describe human cell classes on Wikidata.
- Develop a curation workflow for cell types on Wikidata and provide a comprehensive catalog of cell types.

¹⁹ As a note, a former colleague from the Nakaya Lab, Cesar Prada, is currently working at Novo Nordisk, and has worked with the Cell Ontology in their pipeline alongside Shawn Tan, the first author of the linked reference.

-
- Study the intersections of Wikidata and bioinformatics in general, and the Human Cell Atlas in specific, and how the platform can intersect with the needs of scientific stakeholders.
 - Develop tools and standard operating procedures to connect Wikidata and the OBO Foundry, as a stepping stone to improve the Human Cell Atlas curation efforts.

2.6 Thesis outline

The organization into separate chapters is meant to clarify the rationale of each part. Each chapter corresponds to a small research project on itself, each corresponding roughly to one publication.

The first chapter of the results presents WikiGOA, showcasing how the Wikidata infrastructure can be leveraged *directly* for bioinformatics. That was the first idea in this PhD project: explore the potential of Wikidata directly for use in the Human Cell Atlas. For WikiGOA, Wikidata already contained the information needed for the application. However, for organizing knowledge about cells, first we needed a better understanding of the cell type paradigm. This work was originally published as a preprint in BioRxiv in a custom bullet point paper format, exploring an alternative to traditional publishing. (LUBIANA et al., 2022b)

Continuing on the line of direct applications of Wikidata, we present the reconciliation of cell type markers on PanglaoDB – a popular resource for single-cell RNA-seq researchers – to Wikidata. By mapping terms and connecting data, we demonstrated the value of Wikidata for moving biomedical content to the status of 5-star Linked Open Data, a technical gold standard.

The third chapter takes a philosophical turn into the discussion on the concept of cell type, which we figured out as central for the adequate modeling of knowledge produced by the Human Cell Atlas. This dive into the conceptual basis of cell types was chronologically intertwined with the different works in this PhD, but nevertheless is at the base of the work done. A first version of this work was published in the

Authorea preprint platform in January 2021 (LUBIANA; NAKAYA, 2021), but the text was revisited many times over the years that followed, with significant changes.

The fourth chapter also describes a theoretical work, but this time in an applied context, done in collaboration with the Cell Ontology team, with the goal of creating a standard for publication of new cell classes in the scientific literature. This came from the realization that the scientific community is yet to develop a method for formal description of cell types. To advance that standard, we worked on MIRACL, a minimal information scheme for cell types with an initial focus on the Cell Ontology, but with repercussions for knowledge management in general.

Finally, in the last chapter, we present the largest of the five sub projects done over the past few years. Besides connecting databases to Wikidata, a great part of this PhD project concerned itself with the actual value of Wikidata for the Human Cell Atlas community. We developed, then, a workflow for curating cell classes and from the scientific literature and cataloged thousands of them on the platform as structured linked open data. Realizing that through the past 4 years the Human Cell Atlas core databases (like CELLXGENE) adopted the Cell Ontology as the standard for cataloging cell types, as well as other ontologies in the OBO Foundry for annotating metadata, we prototype ways to connect Wikidata to these larger projects, already embedded into the science knowledge management ecosystem.

Finally, after each of the five chapters we present the general considerations about the work and the possible lines of research. The first conclusion of the work is that the sociotechnical framework of Wikidata is powerful for the advancement of biocuration, and increasing its connection with OBO Foundry ontologies has immediate benefits for state-of-the-art knowledge management. The second, more abstract, is that we still have a lot of theoretical work to do and standards to develop to organize our knowledge about cells consistently. New sociotechnical and theoretical frameworks, such as the ones raised here, play a role in the Human Cell Atlas knowledge ecosystem, as we explore and advance human knowledge about cells.

3. WikiGOA: Gene set enrichment analysis based on Wikipedia and the Gene Ontology

Our life is frittered away by detail [...] Simplify, simplify!

Henry David Thoreau (THOREAU, 1854)

3.1 Thesis considerations

The WikiGOA project was developed with the dual goal of probing Wikidata's readiness for life sciences research use and creating a collection of non-redundant, simple gene sets for use in Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA). GSEA is a standard component of omics pipelines in bioinformatics, relying on curated gene sets to infer biological features of collection of genes, incorporating structured knowledge into the results. Gene sets used for GSEA are varied, including those curated by the teams at Reactome, WikiPathways and the Gene Ontology Consortium. (MARTENS et al., 2021; MILACIC et al., 2024; THE GENE ONTOLOGY CONSORTIUM et al., 2023)The choice of a particular collection of gene sets is done usually in light of the research question and personal decisions.

Wikidata has a rich collection of gene annotations, imported mostly from UniProt by the Gene Wiki team. The entries on Wikidata are also linked directly to Wikipedia entries, providing a proxy for the relevance/popularity of concepts. In this first part of the thesis, we describe how we leveraged the infrastructure of Wikidata and the speed brought by using SPARQL query over unambiguous concepts to generate Wikidata-based gene sets in a flexible fashion.

As a qualitative experiment on the speed of using Wikidata, we went from the idea to the preprint on bioRxiv in a couple of weeks, and it was not sent to peer review so as to not side track us from the cell type dimensions of the project. Also as an experiment, the report was originally written in a non-standard format where

assertions are all expressed in bullet points. This was done to clarify statements and assumptions, simplify reading and pave the way for conversion to structured formats (e.g., nanopublications). (GROTH; GIBSON; VELTEROP, 2010)

Finally, the work done here acted as a way to gauge interest of the academic community in directly using Wikidata-based projects on their workflows. In that direction, even though the WikiGOA gene sets presented benefits in certain circumstances – as exemplified in the paper – we did not really get much attention or use. While this lack of impact can be attributed to a number of factors (such as the absence of a peer-reviewed publication), it helped guide some later decisions, particularly on the need to connect Wikidata with ontologies as a path to reach academic impact in the short term.

3.2 Introduction

The analysis of omics data relies on integrating datasets with curated databases of gene function annotation. Gene sets curated to Gene Ontology terms are widely used by the transcriptomics community for Over Representation Analysis and Gene Set Enrichment Analysis. (SUBRAMANIAN et al., 2005; WIJESOORIYA et al., 2022; YON RHEE et al., 2008)

A large number of gene sets is a double-edged sword: there is a tradeoff between coverage of niche fields and the quick interpretability of results. Furthermore, the statistical power of the analysis is reduced when too many comparisons are present. One challenge is identifying which Gene Ontology terms are the most relevant for the task.

Of note, Wikipedia is a common lay metric of relevance, as the creation of pages is bound by notability criteria (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Notability). Wikidata is a Linked Open Data platform (and collaborative knowledge graph) that provides links to Gene Ontology identifiers and to Wikipedia. (VRANDEČIĆ; PINTSCHER; KRÖTZSCH, 2023; WAAGMEESTER et al., 2020)

In this work, we describe the use of Wikidata to generate a dataset comprising only gene sets for Gene Ontology Biological Processes with a corresponding Wikipedia page. We refer to the datasets as “WikiGOA”, standing for “Wikipedia Gene Ontology Annotations”. We use the dataset to analyze gene expression data and show that it provides readily understandable results, useful for exploring complex biological datasets. A visual representation of our workflow is shown in **Figure {{wikigoa_1}}**.

Figure {{wikigoa_1}}: The WikiGOA dataset. Using SPARQL, we extracted gene sets from Wikidata, reconciled previously mostly from UniProt-GOA. Only GO terms with associated English Wikipedia pages were selected. We rendered datasets in standard formats, and compared the performance with default Gene Ontology annotations from MSigDB.

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Dataset preparation

The dataset for Biological Process Gene Sets, released under the CC-BY-4.0 License,²⁰ was downloaded from MSigDB (gsea-msigdb.org/gsea/downloads.jsp). (ASHBURNER et al., 2000; THE GENE ONTOLOGY CONSORTIUM et al., 2023) Gene Ontology terms with English Wikipedia pages were obtained from Wikidata using the SPARQL query language via the Wikidata Query Service (**Code Snippet 1**) The dataset was prepared via Wikidata and includes HGNC gene symbols, Ensembl IDs and Entrez IDs

The final dataset had 269 gene sets, comprising all Gene Ontology Biological Process terms with Wikidata cross references to Wikidata as of June 2022. The datasets for enrichment analysis are available at doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6624354 both as a .tsv table and in the standard .gmt format. Gene Ontology Annotations were obtained from Wikidata, where most of the protein annotations come from the UniProt-GoA database (HUNTLEY et al., 2015) via mappings done by the ProteinBoxBot. (Waagmeester et al. 2020) The list of all Gene

Ontology terms with Wikipedia pages, in all categories (Biological Process, Cell Component and Molecular Function) is also available via the Wikidata Query Service: w.wiki/5Dsh

²⁰ https://www.gsea-msigdb.org/gsea/msigdb_license_terms.jsp

```

SELECT DISTINCT ?site ?item ?itemLabel ?go

    ?gene_symbol ?entrez ?ensembl_gene_id .
WHERE
{
    ?item wdt:P686 ?go .
    ?protein wdt:P682 ?item ;

        wdt:P703 wd:Q15978631 ;
        wdt:P702 ?gene .
    ?gene wdt:P353 ?gene_symbol ;
        wdt:P351 ?entrez ;
        wdt:P594 ?ensembl_gene_id .
    ?sitelink schema:about ?item ;

        schema:isPartOf <https://en.wikipedia.org/> .
    ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel . FILTER (LANG (?itemLabel) = "en")
}

```

Code Snippet 1: SPARQL query to generate the Wikipedia-based gene sets.
w.wiki/5DsS

3.3.2 Data analysis

The gene sets were analyzed in R using the fGSEA package. (KOROTKEVICH et al., 2021). We realized a dataset containing data from SARS-CoV-2 infected cells. (BLANCO-MELO et al., 2020) Code is available at github.com/luxeredias/WikiGOA.

3.4 Results

We qualitatively compare the performance of WikiGOA and the MSigDB Gene Ontology Biological Processes dataset (MSigDB GOBP) for two publicly available gene expression datasets; one about SARS-CoV-2 infected cells and the other about post-mortem samples of schizophrenia patients. (BLANCO-MELO et al., 2020; GANDAL et al., 2018) (**Figure {{wikigoa_2}}**)

Figure {{wikigoa_2}}: Comparison of the performance of WikiGOA and MSigDB datasets. Top 6 up positively and negatively enriched biological process for both WikiGOA and MSigDB GOBP for A) ACE+ A549 cells infected with SARS-CoV-2 in comparison to non-infected cells and B) brains from schizophrenia patients in comparison to non-schizophrenia brains.

3.4.1 SARS-CoV-2 dataset

The SARS-CoV-2 dataset compared the transcriptomes of ACE+ A549 cells (derived from a lung carcinoma) that were infected with SARS-CoV-2 to identical cells that were not infected.

For that dataset, WikiGOA highlights an upregulation of immune response genes and a general downregulation of the basal energy metabolism of the cells, consistent with what is known in the literature about the biology of SARS-CoV-2. (“Immune Response in SARS-CoV-2 Infection: The Role of Interferons Type I and Type III” 2020; Andrade Silva et al. 2021)

3.4.2 Schizophrenia dataset

The schizophrenia dataset compared the post-mortem brains of people diagnosed with schizophrenia with the post-mortem brains of non-schizophrenia matched controls. For that dataset, WikiGOA highlights a series of different upregulated processes, including the complement pathway and hippo signaling pathway, both of which have been associated with schizophrenia before. (PANIZZUTTI et al., 2021; WOO et al., 2020)

The upregulation of fibrinolysis is in the opposite direction of previous studies that found a global hypofibrinolysis and hypercoagulability in schizophrenia patients. (CHOW et al., 2015) We reason that the difference is welcome, as it shows WikiGOA as capable of raising unexpected situations that may lead, in practice, to novel interpretations and explanations of biological phenomena.

3.5 Discussion

In summary, for both datasets, the WikiGOA enrichment highlighted simple terms that are easier to understand. It also seems that the terms picked by WikiGOA are less redundant than the ones retrieved in the GOBP analysis. These 2

characteristics (readability and independence of the terms retrieved) are arguably more useful for a first-pass overview of the data than the fine-grained results brought when using MSigDB. The lower complexity of the retrieved terms and the guaranteed presence of the concepts on Wikipedia also arguably present a more friendly environment for bioinformatics students learning to handle gene sets.

One limitation is that, by design, WikiGOA will have a gross granularity, as only major biological processes have Wikipedia pages. Thus, for bioinformatics research we recommend using WikiGOA alongside fine-grained datasets, such as MSigDB, for a more complete overview of the data at hand.

In conclusion, the Wikipedia Gene Ontology Annotations dataset is a simple but powerful addition to the arsenal of the transcriptomics community. We envision its usage for quick exploration of gene expression data both in the context of bioinformatics research and higher education.

4. Bringing PanglaoDB to 5-star Linked Open Data using Wikidata

"There is one web ... Anyone that tries to chop it into two will find that their piece looks very boring."

Tim Berners-Lee

4.1 Thesis Considerations

PanglaoDB is a database of cell-type markers widely used for single-cell RNA sequencing data analysis. (FRANZÉN; GAN; BJÖRKEGREN, 2019) However, cell types and genes in the database are encoded by free text, lacking proper identifiers. Wikidata, is a freely editable knowledge graph database useful for integrating biomedical knowledge. We thus reasoned that porting PanglaoDB's markers to the platform could improve their reusability and overall technical quality (FAIRness).

We mapped 188 cell types from PanglaoDB to species-neutral terms on Wikidata and created 376 species-specific terms for cell types in *Homo sapiens* and *Mus musculus*. These terms were enriched with marker information via the *has marker* (P8872) property, totaling over 15.000 cell type to. marker associations ([w.wiki/9iw6](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/9iw6)). We explored this new subset of the graph via SPARQL queries, illustrating the discovery potential of structured, integrated knowledge. For example, we found a previously unexplored link between roship neurons, clozapine, and schizophrenia via the *HRH1* marker. Besides the graph-based insights, we took time to describe the details of the reconciliation process, hoping to stimulate more resources for a move to a 5-star linked open data format.

4.2 Introduction

PanglaoDB is a publicly available database that hosts metadata and results of hundreds of single-cell RNA sequencing experiments. It also provides a rich dataset of cell type markers, containing thousands of cell type to marker associations. It also displays a rich web user interface for easy data acquisition, including database dumps for bulk downloads.

As of 30 December 2020, when the first draft of this article was completed, the PanglaoDB had already been cited 88 times. As of 27 March 2024, when we were finalizing the preprint for bioRxiv, PanglaoDB had been cited even more impressively, amassing over 880 citations. Despite that, PanglaoDB's data is still at a 3-star level of quality for Linked Open Data (Berners-Lee, 2008) as it does not use the open semantic standards from W3C (RDF and links to the web, **Figure {{5-star open data}}**). Moving data format toward W3C's gold standards is a valuable step in making biological knowledge FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). (WILKINSON et al., 2016, p. 201) Among other qualities, 5-star linked open data uses unique resolvable identifiers, removing ambiguity, and is parseable by computers, making it easier to integrate it into smart algorithms.

Figure {{5-star open data}}: The 5-star linked open data schematics, designed by Sir Tim Berners-Lee. Image in public domain, available at 5stardata.info/en. Cell marker data in PanglaoDB is at 3 stars, with openly available CSV dumps.

Wikidata provides two extra layers of quality: RDF support and links to the wider web of data.

Wikidata is an open, freely editable, knowledge graph database within the semantic web that stores knowledge across a multitude of domains and uses an item-property-value model (**Figure 2**). It is easy to use and edit by both humans and machines, with a rich web user interface and wrapper packages available in R and Python. All pieces of information within Wikidata are automatically available on the web and released in the public domain for unrestricted reuse.

The screenshot displays the Wikidata interface for the item 'hepatocyte' (Q827450). At the top, the item name 'hepatocyte' is highlighted in a red box, and its identifier '(Q827450) Item Identifier' is highlighted in a yellow box. Below this, the item is described as 'liver cell type' with an 'edit' link. A section titled 'In more languages' contains a table of alternative labels. The table has four columns: Language, Label, Description, and Also known as. The rows show labels for English, Portuguese, German, and Italian. The 'Also known as' column lists alternative names for each language. Below the table is a 'Statements' section, which is highlighted with a green box. It shows the item is an instance of 'cell type', with an 'edit' link and options to add references or values.

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	hepatocyte	liver cell type	Hepatocyte hepatocytes
Portuguese	Hepatócito	tipo celular	
German	Hepatozyt	Hauptzelltyp der Leber	Hepatocyt Leberepithelzelle Hepatozyten Leberzelle
Italian	Epatocito	No description defined	Epatociti Epatocita

Figure 2: Wikidata item example, showing item hepatocyte (Q827450), the labels change according to the user's language, but each item has a universal identifier, called the QID²¹ and formatted as a Q followed by numbers. Items are assigned numbers in chronological order, as they are created.

Several advances for biological data in Wikidata have been made before, showcasing its potential for bioinformatics. The platform has been proposed as a unified base to gather and distribute biomedical knowledge and includes concepts for a myriad of genes, organs, diseases, biological processes, and other biological and biomedical concepts (Mitraka et al., 2015; Turki et al., 2019, 2022; Waagmeester et al., 2020).

Wikidata already covers a wide range of concepts in the life sciences, but as it is collaborative, quality depends on the attention given to a particular domain. In particular, Wikidata had very little information about cell types when we started, with less than 300 items classified as cell types, while other projects described over 2,000. (Diehl et al., 2016; Stachelscheid et al., 2013).

We, thus, had 2 main motivations for the work described here. The first was integrating PanglaoDB into the semantic web, in light of the needs of the Human Cell Atlas community. (REGEV et al., 2017) And second, increasing the scientific usefulness of Wikidata while describing the steps taken as references for similar projects.

²¹ The Q comes from Qamarniso, the partner of Denny Vrandečić, co-developer of Wikidata. There are more details on that decision at diff.wikimedia.org/2023/11/23/wikidata-and-stories-of-love/.

4.3 Methods

In **Figure 3** we show an outline of the relatively simple steps taken on this work. In summary, we got permission to do the migration from Oscar Franzén from PanglaoDB, then selected the bits of information needed (cell types and genes). We then figured out a semantic schema for markers on Wikidata. Some curation followed, with manual mappings of the controlled vocabulary of PanglaoDB to Wikidata identifiers. We then used the mappings as the basis for some Python scripts that used WikidataIntegrator to batch-add the markers to Wikidata.

4.3.1 Getting the data

Figure 3. An overview of the basic pipeline for reconciling a resource to Wikidata.

Gene data from Wikidata was acquired using the Wikidata Query Service for *Homo sapiens* genes and *Mus musculus* genes. The markers dataset was downloaded manually from PanglaoDB's website (panglaodb.se/markers/PanglaoDB_markers_27_Mar_2020.tsv.gz). It contained 15 columns and 8256 rows. Only the columns *species*, *official gene symbol*, and *cell type* were used for the reconciliation. All data was handled using the *pandas* Python library.

4.3.2 Creating classes on Wikidata

Classes corresponding to species-neutral concepts were retrieved from Wikidata manually using Wikidata's graphical user interface and biocurated to matching terms in PanglaoDB. Cell types not represented on Wikidata were added via its web interface and logged into the mapping table. Although PanglaoDB is not a semantic resource, we used the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM) based format for sharing openly the mappings on Zenodo (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10936294). (MATENTZOGLU et al., 2022)

Mappings were not purely based on lexical matches, but carefully curated to reflect meaning. For example, the description of "Basal cells" on PanglaoDB states that "*Basal cells are keratinocytes found in the basal layer of the skin*", so the concept was matched to *basal cell of the skin* (Q101062513) instead of the more general *basal cell* (Q809772). The concept of *basal cell* may be used to describe cells in many organs, but that is seemingly not what was intended by PanglaoDB curators. The lack of unique identifiers on PanglaoDB (and its subsequent 3-star rating) makes the platform ambiguous, and the matching process opinionated, time-consuming, and somewhat delicate.

After the mapping, species-specific cell types for human and mouse cell types were created for every entry in the reference table and connected to the species-neutral concept via a *subclass of* (P279) property (e.g., *human neutrophil* is a subclass of *neutrophil*). Our approach to species-specificity was analogous to the one taken by

the CELDA ontology, which used *rdfs:subClassOf* to denote it. (SELTMANN et al., 2013)

Each item was labeled “human” + the label for the neutral cell type, described as “cell type found in Homo sapiens” and tagged with the statement found in taxon *Homo sapiens*. An analogous framework was used for mouse cell types, assuming that “mouse” in PanglaoDB meant *Mus musculus*. Batch creations were added to Wikidata via the Quickstatements tool.²²

All genes in PanglaoDB either had a 1:1 mapping to Wikidata, in which case they were mapped via the HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) ID (P354) property, or resolved to multiple entities, in which case they were excluded from the reconciliation. Mouse markers on PanglaoDB are curiously also identified with HGNC symbols. They were assumed to be valid only when the upper case transformation of their Mouse Genome Informatics (MGI) Gene Symbol (P2394) was a 1:1 match to HGNC.

4.3.3 Crafting the "has marker" property on Wikidata

We needed a way to represent marker information on Wikidata. New properties need to be supported by the community in a public forum before creation. Thus, we proposed a property called *has marker* for peer review, so we would have the technical infrastructure for the project. We posted a message on 17 November 2020 presenting the property, domain, range constraints, and additional comments. The following motivation statement accompanied the proposal:

"Even though the concept of a marker gene/protein is not clear cut, it is very important, and widely used in databases and scientific articles. This property will help us to represent that a gene/protein has been **reported** as a marker by a

²² quickstatements.toolforge.org/ .

credible source, and should always contain a reference. Some markers are reported as proteins and some as genes. Some genes don't encode proteins, and some protein markers are actually protein complexes. The property would be inclusive to these slightly different markers. Some cell types are marked by the absence of expression of genes/proteins/protein expression. As these seem to be less common than positive markers (no organized databases, for example) they are left outside the value range for this property"

The proposal had specifications of the property such as:

- **Description:** "a gene or a protein published as a marker of a species-specific cell type"
 - **Data type:** Item (Wikidata Uniform Resource Identifiers)
 - **Domain:** instances of (P31) cell type (Q189118)
 - **Allowed values:** instances of protein (Q8054), gene (Q7187) or macromolecular complex (Q22325163)
-
- **Planned use:** *"reconcile knowledge from the PanglaoDB marker database to Wikidata. In the future, expand to other trusted sources of cell type marker information."*The property was approved on 27 November 2020. For those curious about it, more details can be found on the Wikidata property proposal page, available online ([wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/has_positive_marker](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Property_proposal/has_positive_marker)).

4.3.4 Integration to Wikidata

The reconciled dataset was uploaded to Wikidata via the WikidataIntegrator python package²³, a wrapper for the Wikidata Application Programming Interface. The integration details can be seen in the Jupyter notebooks on the GitHub page [jyfe/wikidata_panglaodb](https://github.com/jyfe/wikidata_panglaodb). Authorization to do the migration and release the data in the CC0 license on Wikidata was provided by e-mail by Oscar Franzén, lead developer of PanglaoDB.

4.3.5 Access to reconciled data

The PanglaoDB markers are now part of the main Wikidata content and are available via two formats: database dumps and a SPARQL endpoint. The bulk formats include RDF dumps at wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Database_download and it is possible to also download partial dumps of the database with reduced size (ex: wdumps.toolforge.org/dump/987 for all cell types with the *has marker* property).

Besides the Wikidata Dumps, Wikidata provides an SPARQL endpoint with a Graphical User Interface (query.wikidata.org/). Updated data was instantly accessible via the endpoint, enabling integrative queries.

Of note, as Wikidata is an open system, marker information from different resources was added in the years that followed. Thus, to get only information from PanglaoDB, one needs to filter the markers by the provenance, with SPARQL queries as the one shown in **Code snippet 1**.

4.3.6 Code and data availability

²³ github.com/SuLab/WikidataIntegrator

All source code used for the study and data created during the study are available in a GitHub repository, github.com/jvfe/wikidata_panglaodb, as well as archived (as of April 2024) at doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4438614.

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?cell ?marker
WHERE
{
  ?cell p:P8872 ?statement .
  ?statement ps:P8872 ?marker .
  ?statement prov:wasDerivedFrom [ pr:P248 wd:Q99936939 ]
}
```

Code snippet 1. SPARQL query to get only PanglaoDB (Q99936939) cell type markers (P8872) on Wikidata. 15772 edges as of 8 April 2024. Available at w.wiki/9hgV.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Cell types on Wikidata

As of August 2020, Wikidata had 264 items being categorized as instances of *cell type*, considerably less than in specialized cell catalogs at the type, which counted over two thousand cell types. Strikingly, there were also 23 items categorized as instances of *cell* (Q7868). This classification was imprecise, as an instance of *cell* would be an individual named cell from a single named individual, which should not generally be on Wikidata.

Wikidata editors often mix first-order with second-order classes. First-order classes point to real-world individuals, like the zygote that gave rise to Dolly, the sheep (a real-world *cell*), and the brain of Albert Einstein (a real-world *organ*). Second-order classes point to classes, like *zygote* (a conceptual *cell type*) and *brain* (a conceptual *organ type*). (BRASILEIRO et al., 2016) For that reason, alongside the PanglaoDB

Figure 4. Two of the current markers of “human cholinergic neuron” (Q101405051) in the Wikidata interface for web navigation.

integration, we improved the modeling of cell types on Wikidata. As of February 2021, the Wikidata database contained 1828 instances of *cell type* ([w.wiki/b2t](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q101405051)) and no instances of “cell” ([w.wiki/b2q](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q101405051)), reducing conceptual disarray.

As a note, by April 2024, the number of instances of “cell type” on Wikidata is much higher (5624), due to subsequent curation efforts, and we were able to clean it to keep it with no instances of “cell.” Of note, the data shown here was generated back in 2020/2021 and represents the state of the platform then.

4.4.2 Cell markers on Wikidata

Adding marker information on Wikidata was not possible before this study and became possible after community approval of the property *has marker* (P8872) (see Methods). In **Figure 4** we illustrate two of the current markers of “human cholinergic neuron”, *CHAT* and *ACHE*, as they are seen on Wikidata. The PanglaoDB is referenced via a URL to the website (panglaodb.se/markers.html) and a pointer to the PanglaoDB item on Wikidata (Q99936939).

Since Wikidata is an open system, user contributions now complement the PanglaoDB information about markers. Until February 2021, however, no other project had systematically integrated cell-type markers into Wikidata, and thus, most of the information shown here comes from PanglaoDB. **Tables 1 and 2** show the marker count for the five cell types of humans and mice with the most markers on Wikidata, for both species around two hundred marker genes.

Table 1: Top 5 Homo sapiens cell types with the most markers on Wikidata (15/02/2021, full query on w.wiki/zoQ).

cell type	markers
human interneuron	216
human neuron	203
human endothelial cell	187
human fibroblast	170
human hepatocyte	149

Table 2: Top 5 Mus musculus cell types with the most markers on Wikidata (15/02/2021, full query on [/w.wiki/zoN](https://w.wiki/zoN)).

cell type	markers
mouse neocortical interneuron	219
mouse interneuron	219

mouse neuron	210
mouse endothelial cell	188
mouse fibroblast	176

4.4.3 Wikidata SPARQL queries enabled by the integration

One of the benefits of our pipeline is the ability to query the data using SPARQL and potentially running federated queries (Martens et al., 2021; Sima et al., 2019). After finishing adding the markers we explored some of these questions, outlined in **Figure 5**.

4.4.4 Which cell types are related to neurogenesis via cell markers?

Figure 5: Wikidata SPARQL queries bring to light hidden biomedical knowledge. Blue nodes represent Items on Wikidata and green nodes represent variables in the SPARQL queries. A-C) Graphical representation of feasible SPARQL queries and a sample of their results as of 07/02/2021 ([w.wiki/yQ6](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/yQ6), [/w.wiki/yQD](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/yQD) and [w.wiki/3Hj](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/3Hj)).

To test this first question, we leverage the mapping of Wikidata genes to Gene Ontology terms done by others in the past to get cell types related to the biological process "neurogenesis" (Ashburner et al., 2000; The Gene Ontology Consortium et al., 2023). The query results showed over 55 cell types linked by genes (Fig. 5A)

which is illustrated in **Figure 6**. The results, exemplified in **Table 3**, show a series of neuron types, such as *human Purkinje neuron* and *human Cajal-Retzius cell*. It also retrieved non-neural cell types such as the *human loop of Henle cell*, a type of kidney cell, and *human osteoclast*, a type of bone cell.

Figure 6. Overview of the graph linking cell types (red) and their markers (white) to neurogenesis (blue) as of 08/04/2024. See the current version on w.wiki/9hj2.

These seemingly unrelated cell types markedly express genes involved in neurogenesis, but that of course does not mean that they are involved in this process. As genes play different roles in the body, just because a set of genes plays a role in two biological systems does not mean we can make a direct, mechanistic

connection. These results reinforce the need for carefulness when interpreting data based on curated pathways.

Table 3: Sample of 10 cell types related to neurogenesis via markers (07/02/2021, current version on [w.wiki/yQ6](https://www.wikiwand.com/en/wiki/yQ6))

gene	cell type
<i>OMP</i>	human Purkinje neuron
<i>OMP</i>	human olfactory epithelial cell
<i>OMP</i>	human neuron
<i>EPHB1</i>	human oligodendrocyte
<i>EPHB1</i>	human osteoclast
<i>PCSK9</i>	human delta cell
<i>PCSK9</i>	human loop of Henle cell
<i>CXCR4</i>	human B cell
<i>CXCR4</i>	human T cell
<i>CXCR4</i>	human NK cell

4.4.5 Which cell types express markers associated with Parkinson's disease?

Besides Gene Ontology, Wikidata has been integrated with sources about diseases, such as the Disease Ontology (Schriml et al., 2021; Waagmeester et al., 2020). This makes Wikidata a spot to quickly investigate links of cell types to particular diseases. The genes linked to diseases (via the *genetic association* property, P2293) are often compiled from Genome-Wide Association Studies, which look for sequence variation at the overall genomic level. These studies are blind to cell types, and bridging the gap from GWAS to cell types is a topic of research in itself. In **Table 4**, we can see some cell types marked by genes genetically associated with Parkinson's disease (PD).

Once more, we have a mix of confirming and surprising results. The relation with human neurons is obviously expected, but we see hits of cells from the immune system and the pancreas. Reassuringly, the immune axis connections to Parkinson's disease via BST1 are indeed studied in the literature.(YOKOYAMA, 2023)

The *SH3GL2* gene. related to Parkinson's, has not been yet connected to via their role on pancreatic cells to the disease. The gene apparently plays a more direct role, acting on brain synapses. (DECET; SOUKUP, 2023) *SH3GL2* is reportedly expressed in pancreatic endocrine cells, but we could not find much information about its role in the organ, as most papers seem to focus on its role in the central nervous system.²⁴ This can signal that this particular link has little biological significance or there is a biological connection to be investigated.

²⁴ proteatlas.org/ENSG00000107295-SH3GL2/tissue/pancreas

Table 4: Sample of 5 cell types related to Parkinson's disease via markers (07/02/2021, current version of query on w.wiki/yQD).

gene	disease	cell type
<i>BST1</i>	Parkinson's disease	human B cell
<i>BST1</i>	Parkinson's disease	human neutrophil
<i>RIT2</i>	Parkinson's disease	human neuron
<i>SH3GL2</i>	Parkinson's disease	human alpha cell
<i>SH3GL2</i>	Parkinson's disease	human beta cell

4.4.6 Which diseases are associated with the markers of pancreatic beta cells?

With the flexibility of SPARQL queries, we can investigate the cell-type-to-disease relation in both ways. One may be interested in particular cell types and which diseases are related to their cell type of interest.

For that, we looked for the diseases linked to human pancreatic beta cells, which play an important role in controlling blood sugar levels (**Table 5**). Reassuringly, the top hits associated with markers included obesity and type-2 diabetes. Other diseases, such as Parkinson's, asthma and aniridia - a disturbance of the iris of the eye - do not bear a clear link with classic pancreatic functions. Once more, the links may either be spurious or hint at unknown connections, providing seeds for future research.

Table 5: Top 5 diseases (by number of links) related to human pancreatic beta cells via markers (07/02/2020, full query on <https://w.wiki/yQD>).

disease	genes	cell type
obesity	<i>PCSK2, ADCYAP1, SLC30A8</i>	human beta cell
type 2 diabetes	<i>SLC30A8, TGFBR3</i>	human beta cell
Parkinson's	<i>SH3GL2</i>	human beta cell
asthma	<i>SLC30A8</i>	human beta cell
aniridia	<i>PAX6</i>	human beta cell

4.4.7 Disease-drug-gene-cell networks associate rosehip neurons with schizophrenia

For this section, we took inspiration from the work by Lüscher Dias and colleagues on networks containing drugs, diseases, and genes using the now-discontinued Watson Drug Discovery (Dias et al., 2020). We decided to query for similar multi-hop connections on Wikidata now enriched with PanglaoDB, linking cell types and diseases in more elaborate ways.

Complex conditions, like schizophrenia, are not caused by a single gene mutation, and disease progression may be influenced by several cell types. Reasoning that drugs might perturb the cell types expressing their targets, we explored cell types that express markers (1) genetically associated with schizophrenia and, at the same time, markers (2) targeted by drugs used for the disease.

Figure 7A showcases some of the cell types related to schizophrenia via markers and drugs. Purkinje neurons, for example, connect via the marker *GRIA3* to the disease, and via the marker *GABRA1* to clonazepam, an anti-epileptic drug sometimes used for schizophrenia. Some relations are probably spurious, such as the link between hepatic stellate cells—*RELN*—and schizophrenia. *RELN* is expressed independently in the brain and the liver, and it is reasonable to assume that its association with schizophrenia occurs at the brain level (Alexander et al., 2023).

A particular cell type caught our eye: the human-specific, recently discovered rosehip neuron, highlighted in **Figure 7B** (Boldog et al., 2018). Boldog et al. when describing the cell type highlighted that "*several highly selective markers for RCs have been implicated as risk factors for neuropsychiatric disease, including netrin G1 (NTNG1) for Rett syndrome and neurotrypsin (PRSS12) for mental retardation*" and even mentioned *HRH1* as a marker, but did not make the link to schizophrenia.

Figure 7. A disease-drug-gene-cell network on Wikidata reveals hidden connections of schizophrenia genes (08/04/2024). A. The network relates schizophrenia (orange) to drugs (green) and cell types (blue) via genes (white). A live version is available at this [long link](#). B. A Subset of the graph includes the connection of rosehip neurons to schizophrenia.

A later study comparing transcriptomic markers to genetic markers in schizophrenia pointed to a link between the cell type and the disease (Yu et al., 2021) and a third study used single-cell RNA-seq to look at various populations in the brain, including rosehip neurons, but did not investigate the matter in detail (Ruzicka et al., 2020). Neither, however, seemed to have dedicated much time to investigating the association of rosehip neurons with schizophrenia in detail. Given that rosehip neurons are marked by *HRH1* and the histamine H1 receptor is a target of many antipsychotic drugs, like clozapine (Fell et al., 2012), there is a hint of a role for these cells in the natural history of the disease, or at least in the response to treatment.

The PanglaoDB-enriched Wikidata graph allows us to traverse many types of edges through the biomedical knowledge landscape. The disease-drug-gene-cell graphs showcase the strength of 5-star Linked Open Data for cross-domain integration. We added similar plots in the Supplementary Disease-Drug-Gene-Cell Network Collection, each generated for a different disease by changing a single line of the SPARQL query in **Figure 7**. As with the other pieces of knowledge here, all edges are backed by references on Wikidata, and thus reliable to some extent. As usual, interpretation should be done carefully.

4.5 Discussion

We hope that the results section has provided the reader with a flavor of what 5-star Linked Open Data and SPARQL queries - particularly on Wikidata - can bring research insights. The contribution detailed here is small, and the actual processing of data and connections took only a couple of months of part-time work. If one is familiar with the Wikidata data model and some basic Python programming, reconciling small datasets is quite straightforward.

As we care about cell types, the Human Cell Atlas, and the rise of the single-cell transcriptomics field, we focused on the PanglaoDB information. While we don't necessarily expect bioinformaticians to use Wikidata directly - though it is definitely possible - the community curation model provides a way of crowdsourcing cell-type

markers for later reuse. The PanglaoDB data is, then, but a seed to grow the structured representation of cell type-gene associations on Wikidata.

We considered writing some R or Python packages to connect the PanglaoDB markers on Wikidata to single-cell RNA-seq workflows but eventually gave up on the idea. There are already too many single-cell RNA-seq tools, some even using PanglaoDB (Osorio et al., 2022). If Wikidata indeed becomes a hub for marker genes, then it will find its way into the single-cell RNA-seq workflows. All gene-to-cell-type annotations can be retrieved and reused, and while the technical details were not discussed in this paper, we demonstrated analogous procedures in the past (Lubiana et al., 2022).

It is important to note that not all data on PanglaoDB was added to Wikidata. Some fine-grained details did not fit a general-purpose knowledge base like Wikidata (e.g., the scores for sensitivity and specificity attached to each marker-cell type pair). If one really wanted to get the additional bits in 5-star Linked Open Data, these parts could be also transformed to RDF format and connected to independent SPARQL endpoints. For reference, similar processes have been done for other datasets by the Bio2RDF effort (Callahan et al., 2013).

One other option for turning PanglaoDB into 5-star linked open data would be using the infrastructure of the OBO Foundry community of ontologies, including the major source for cell type IDs, the Cell Ontology. (Diehl et al., 2016; Jackson et al., 2021) However, the way markers are defined on PanglaoDB is semantically ambiguous, and not very amenable to rigorous ontologization. Also, as the project was a branch of a Ph.D. work, done with J.V.F.C., an undergraduate student at the time, we chose the simpler Wikidata to have a straightforward, technically lighter framework. Wikidata makes it extremely easy to mint new identifiers for a scientific concept, by just clicking a few buttons on a web interface, without authorization systems or gatekeeping (Shafee et al., 2023).

As described in the methods session, we added species-specific terms to Wikidata for cell types of *Homo sapiens* and *Mus musculus* described in the PanglaoDB database. The use of species-specific cell types is necessary because genes in Wikidata are also species-specific. In the biomedical literature, however, genes and cell types are sometimes referred to broadly, in a multi-species or species-neutral way. These fuzzy ways of human language are not always compatible with formalized data models. Thus, this mapping task is not merely one of picking the right match on Wikidata, but largely of consistent and coherent interpretations of data.

Also, though usage of Wikidata on bioinformatics is limited, its impact on the web is decently sized. Data on Wikidata is commonly reused on Wikipedia, a major source of information for scientists and laypeople alike (Good et al., 2012; Thompson & Hanley, 2017). Moreover, Google, Apple, and several other organizations leverage Wikidata's graph directly. They value Wikidata's public domain licensing, reusing data in many automated ways. Thus, though it may be hard to track, adding knowledge to Wikidata certainly influences the information landscape on the web (Pellissier Tanon et al., 2016; Vrandečić et al., 2023).

Of course, Wikidata has its limitations. Concerns with the reliability of Wikipedia are as old as the encyclopedia itself²⁵ and Wikidata shares many of such concerns. The ontological modeling of Wikidata is often far from perfect, and inconsistencies and logical mistakes abound (Brasileiro et al., 2016). While a comprehensive analysis of the pros and cons of scientific Wikidata is not available, we extend Don Fallis' view on Wikipedia and argue that Wikidata also has a number of "epistemic virtues (e.g., power, speed, and fecundity) that arguably outweigh any deficiency in terms of reliability" (Fallis, 2008).

²⁵ For some context and background, see en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reliability_of_Wikipedia

In summary, this work provides the biomedical community with a semantically accessible, 5-star Linked Open Data dataset of cell markers, adding knowledge from PanglaoDB to Wikidata. The work also provides a blueprint for other databases of cell-type markers, such as CellMarker, labome, CellFinder, and SHOGoiN/CELLPEDIA (Hatano et al., 2011; Stachelscheid et al., 2013; Yakimchuk, 2013; Zhang et al., 2018) in case they want to increase FAIRness even more and integrate their datasets as a 5-star Linked Open Data on Wikidata.

4.6 Supplementary Disease-Drug-Gene-Cell Networks

Parkinson's disease (08/04/2024, [link](#))

Alzheimer's disease (08/04/2024, [link](#))

Major depressive disorder (08/04/2024, [link](#))

5. A conceptual definition of scientific cell classes for use in ontologies and data annotation

Nature is very unwilling to accommodate herself to our schemes. The object of her aim is quite opposed to that of our intellect. She accords and accommodates all contrarities by gentle transitions: the intellect disjoins, and seeks everywhere for strongly-marked contrasts.

Theodor Schwann, translated by Henry Smith

5.1 Thesis Considerations

The concept of cell type is vital for modeling biology in knowledge bases. Recent technological advances prompt us to rethink what we understand by cell type and how we classify them. The diverse terminology, including types, states, identities and phenotypes, complicates the matter further. As we lack standard ways of classifying cells, coming up with the parts list of the human body is a poorly defined task. With no parts list and no standards, we naturally struggle with annotating data, even more so when multiple species are involved.

We propose here that knowledge- and databases should focus on the *cell classes*, and that we should have ways to identify any grouping of cells that is theoretically useful. That is, any grouping of cells that helps data annotation, or that are an inseparable part of scientific statements (hypothesis, conclusions, and alike).

We also identify four metaclasses useful for conceptual clarity and effective knowledge management: *sensu stricto* cell classes, archeclasses, infraclasses, and technoclasses. They refer to the ideas of a *cell class* when restricted to a single species, multiple species, populations below the species level, and particular experiments. This theoretical system is extended to include a pragmatic *atomic cell class*, deriving the framework for practical knowledge management applications in CELLxGENE and similar platforms. For that, we explore the CELLxGENE metadata

schema and illustrate how the atomic-cell-class-based method can be leveraged to improve the usefulness of the Cell Ontology.

The concepts and frameworks we propose provide a solid option for basing theoretical systems and computerized applications. In particular, these named abstractions improve both the tools for curating cell types in registries and the workflows for single-cell RNA-seq annotation, ultimately providing technical and philosophical groundings for better knowledge management in cell atlases.

5.2 Introduction

One of the primary subjects in any undergraduate major in life sciences is histology. Students must identify cell types across various tissues and look for color and shape patterns in hematoxylin-eosin stains. Textbooks, like Junqueira's Basic Histology (Mescher, 2018), work as manuals that perpetuate the paradigms (in the Kuhnian sense) (Kuhn, 1962) of what we know about a few hundred cell types. Consequently, our current perception of "cell type" is still based on centuries-old histochemical techniques, such as the Golgi stains of neurons immortalized by Ramon y Cajal (Ramón y Cajal, 1894). The histological influence is noticeable even in the names given to cell types, such as erythrocyte, eosinophils, basophils, and oxyphilic thyroid cell. The concepts we use are drawn from studies of microanatomy. This connection with anatomy makes us consider cell types as anatomical entities dissectible and fixed in an organism. The resolution limits perpetuated by the histological-anatomical view may be why attempts to quantify cell types use the scale of hundreds of human cell types. (HUBMAP CONSORTIUM et al., 2019; REGEV et al., 2017)

New techniques have challenged this anatomy-based conceptualization. From flow cytometry to patch clamping to single-cell RNA-seq, we saw a burst of new categories, and novel cell subtypes popped up in the literature. The bursting intensified in the past few years, with the rise of projects to characterize *all* human cell types, like the Human Cell Atlas and HUBMAP. (HUBMAP CONSORTIUM et al.,

2019; REGEV et al., 2017) The recently published brain cell census from the Allen Brain Institute highlighted over 3000 cell types only in the brain, confirming the need for going beyond histology to understand cell diversity. (Siletti et al., 2023)

A 2017 article on the Human Cell Atlas describes how the current technological changes brought up conceptual challenges: "Descriptors such as 'cell type' and 'cell state' can be difficult to define at the moment. An integrative, systematic effort by many teams of scientists working together and bringing different expertise to the problem could dramatically sharpen our terminology, and revolutionize the way we see our cells, tissues and organs. We invite you to join the effort." (Rozenblatt-Rosen et al., 2017)

The advances in biology require us to find better answers for how to define a cell type. Such a concept might not have a true meaning in a philosophical-realistic sense. Nevertheless, we can strive to find nominal, pragmatic definitions for the real challenges of large-scale biology. Otherwise, how can we precisely label single-cell data? How can we formalize the discovery of new cell types? How can we integrate the knowledge from millions of published scientific articles?

The community is perceiving the need for a conceptual advance, and new perspectives are rising (Korem et al., 2015; Márquez-Zacarías et al., 2021; Morris, 2019; Panina et al., 2020; Rozenblatt-Rosen et al., 2017; Sachkova & Burkhardt, 2019; Tabansky et al., 2015; "What Is Your Conceptual Definition of 'Cell Type' in the Context of a Mature Organism?," 2017; Xia & Yanai, 2019; Yuste et al., 2020). In an opinion article published in Cell Systems in 2017, a series of researchers presented their views on the conceptual definition of 'cell type' in the context of a mature organism ("What Is Your Conceptual Definition of 'Cell Type' in the Context of a Mature Organism?," 2017). Many scientists believe that the function of cells has a core role in defining cell types, which is a slippery road, as the meaning of the word "function" in biology is elusive (Keeling et al., 2019). The opinions were varied, and no consensus was achieved.

One core line of thought to define “cell type” is based on the cell type as an evolutionary unit represented by a Core Regulatory Complex (CoRC) of transcription factors. That definition enables the drawing of parallels, from the evolution of other biological entities (such as genes, proteins, and species) to cell types’ evolution. Models of how multicellular life works greatly benefit from concepts such as sister types (cell types that diverged from a single ancestor), cell type homology (cell types in different species that share a common evolutionary origin), and cell type convergence (cell types that execute similar functions but which are not directly evolutionarily related) (Arendt, 2008; Luecken & Theis, 2019)

Another direction is based on attractors: regions of dynamical stability in a feature space. (Casey et al., 2019; Enver et al., 2009) Following this theory, basins of attraction pull cell phenotypes in a gene expression space towards which different cells move their expression programs. This dynamic view sees each cell type corresponding to “a self-stabilizing regulatory program, which maintains and restores the cell type-specific program of gene expression (Mukamel & Ngai, 2019).” It aligns itself with dynamic systems theory, and some authors go as far as to say that “Lacking the idea of attractors, we have no clear idea of what a cell type is (Bornholdt & Kauffman, 2019).”

As much as different concepts of species coexist (De Queiroz, 2007), our quest to define cell types may take various forms. The challenge of representing cell types in the context of evolution is conceptually different from representing cell types in biomedical experimentation. In that second direction, the groundwork of the Cell Ontology (Bard et al., 2005; Diehl et al., 2016; Meehan et al., 2011) and the contributions of the International Workshop on Cells in Experimental Life Sciences series (Santivijai et al., 2017, 2019) are notable. Their contributions base much of the views here and will be discussed throughout the article.

More explicitly, we target the question: which definition allows crafting coherent biological statements? Which definition best serves the current databases? The goal here is not to say what cell types *are*, but what they can be for a consistent worldview. We also assume that biological statements that derive from experimentation should be logically valid, and thus aim to distill ways to resolve ambiguities in natural language statements that make knowledge unresolvable (i.e., neither true nor false).

Thus, here we focus on the concept of “cell class,” that is, the conceptual sets encompassing cells with similar features, avoiding the cell type/cell state dilemma. Others have drifted away from this distinction, adopting the term “cell identity” (Luecken & Theis, 2019). As the term “identity” brings up ideas of persistence, we preferred using “cell class” throughout this discussion.

The body of this chapter is divided into four parts. In Part 1, we propose a set of rules that are necessary and sufficient for defining cell classes. Part 2 offers a small set of names for differentiating the main metaclasses of cell types. In Part 3, we address some logical consequences of the proposed definitions, and in Part 4, we discuss some practical implications of the theoretical developments.

5.3 A set of 3 principles for determining a cell class

After a thorough review of the literature and multiple discussions, we arrived at a pragmatic definition of scientific *cell class*, restricted to eukaryotic multicellular organisms, consists of 3 criteria for which any theoretical cell group must have to be a scientific cell class:

1. An explicit name
2. Usefulness for theory
3. Identifiability within a group of organisms

For the first criterion, for a cell class to be valid, it needs to be named. Names can be simple or combinatorial and follow a standard or not. Ideally, the names should be attached to unique identifiers and clear descriptions that allow rational judgments of whether a singular cell belongs to the class. For perfectly accurate knowledge management, these descriptions should also be *complete definitions* (Gruber, 1995) and provide necessary and sufficient criteria for classification.

However, many cell classes are named in datasets, articles, and other knowledge products in practice but need to be described or identified formally. This theoretical grouping has been acknowledged by having a published name; thus, we should formally represent it.

This set of rules separates logic from technology and acknowledges that the idea of cell classes for knowledge management should not be restricted to any particular technology.

The recognition of multiple valid characteristics to define types is not a novelty. The first Cell Ontology article in 2005 explicitly acknowledged criteria based on function, histology, lineage, and ploidy (Bard et al., 2005). These features were combined in defining species-neutral cell types, arguably helpful in integrating databases or teaching biology. Gradually, we acknowledge that we might need more specific classes to characterize experimental biology, leading to the determination of species-specific types defined by granular characteristics (Meehan et al., 2011).

Of note, we do not call for an explicit definition as a criterion for recognition, but plainly an explicit name. Names imply identifiable groupings. While having precise definitions for each cell class would be logically great, citing David Osumi-Sutherland, there is a “*mismatch between quantified logic, which records assertions about all members of a class, and the messy, noisy reality of biology and the data we collect about it.*” (Osumi-Sutherland, 2017) Thus, we consider concepts for cell class scientifically valid even if they are somewhat undefined but still recognizable.

The second criterion, usefulness, is precisely and intentionally vague. Rigorously, there is an infinite number of names, justified by explicit definitions, that any scientist might come up with. One simple proof of this infinitude is that size-based cell definition ("cells over 20 nm", "cells over 19 nm") may alone consider any of the infinite real numbers. A cell class created just for its own sake is invalid: one must be able to say something meaningful about the real world by employing the concept.

Meaningful statements do not need to be accurate, and falsified hypotheses are of great value to science. As usefulness is subjective, the number of possible cell types is constrained by one's goals. Thus, this rule is not intersubjectively applicable: no one can deny a claim of usefulness. However, it is a principle worth considering when cataloging cell types.

The third criterion, a specialization of the second, argues that for a scientific class to be *useful* in the sense intended here, it needs generalizability across group organisms. In other words, it must be valid for different individuals from a particular population, which can be sampled over time. The ability to generalize and deduce is at the heart of science, and this rule might strike as redundant or obvious. It is, nevertheless, a baseline restriction on what groups *can be validly named*. In practice, it challenges the usefulness of classes observed in single individuals (e.g., in single-cell RNA-seq experiments). As an aside, genetically modified cells, in particular mouse strains, could be validly classified (see "infratype" and "technotype" below) and should be taken into account in databases.

While groups can assume many forms, the usefulness argument is strengthened if a given cell class is seen in a well-recognized biological taxon. We call it the *taxonomic scope* of the cell type. In its strongest sense, it states that the cell type needs to be discoverable in any individual of the taxa of interest, given the appropriate conditions (e.g., stage of life and biological sex). A taxonomic scope would be necessary for making transparent, falsifiable statements about cell classes, as it sets the boundary for where to look for the cells in the real world. Pragmatically, though, cell classes are often presented to readers via species-neutral concepts, and

the taxonomic scope is omitted. If the scope can be inferred from the context, there is less harm; however, it is very important to keep track of the intentions regarding scope to avoid overstatements, especially in data annotation, where context is often hidden.

The consequences of this set of criteria will be discussed in the further sections of the chapter. Though simple, these principles are necessary and sufficient to outline the cell classes relevant to modern research.

5.4 Cell classes, cell types and cell states

Named cell classes may refer to theoretical groups united by robust, persistent characteristics, in which case they correspond to *types* (e.g., neuron or pericyte), groups united by transient traits, in which case they correspond to *states* (e.g., activated cell or cycling cell). The named cell classes may also combine states and types in concepts like activated neurons or cycling pericyte. Additionally, various concepts fall into gray zones, complex in theoretical nature, such as female cell or fetal cell.

We argue that the concepts of cell state and cell type in the context of knowledge organization are both conceptual specializations of the idea of *cell class*. The 3 criteria for a scientifically valid class are, in our view, *necessary but insufficient* for scientifically valid cell type. For the practical purpose adopted here, we avoid the cell type x cell state dilemma, and for a discussion on the matter see the “Definition of cell identity” section in (Hon et al., 2017). While we acknowledge the topic needs more theoretical research, it is not strictly required to classify cells or annotate data so we won't tackle it here.

While the subdivision in cell type/cell state is potentially contentious, we focus on a potentially less contentious panorama: the pragmatic subdivision of cell classes based on the taxa where they occur. In the next session, we will explore that perspective in depth.

5.5 Dividing the metaclasses of cells by taxonomic scope

Much of the literature mixes cell classes in one species (e.g., when dealing with a cell type as an evolutionary unit) or multiple species (e.g., in the Cell Ontology). It is helpful to distill these different concepts into names. Given the importance of the species concept in biological classification, we derive a species-centric view on naming classes of cell classes, named hereafter metaclasses. The four metaclasses (Figure 1) we propose are as follows:

- archeclass, for when the taxonomic scope of the cell class is beyond the level of species; for example, *cytotoxic T cell* or the explicit and more restrictive *mammal cytotoxic T cell*.
- *sensu stricto* cell class, for when the taxonomic scope of the class corresponds to a single species; for example, *Mus musculus* cytotoxic T cell.
- infraclass, for when the taxonomic scope is below the species level; for example, BALB/c mice cytotoxic T cell.
- technoclass, for specific, experimentally defined cell classes that harbor in their definition the precise conditions of the cells sampled: male BALB/c CD3+ CD8+ cell.

Figure 1: Names, scopes, illustrations, and examples for metaclasses of cells, covering different levels of organism populations. Below, is the major research context where these types are present and dealt with, often implicitly.

5.5.1 Archeclasses

Cell archeclasses, short for archetypical classes, are the scientific cell classes that manifest themselves in multiple species. The prefix *arche* is intended to capture that the relation of the cells in these groups has foundations that exceed the species boundaries. In light of evolution, archeclasses (like neutrophil) are often expected to entail a shared origin for the class and the presence of cells in this class in the common ancestor.

For descriptions of cell classes, however, we are not always interested in monophyletic relations. As mentioned before, most researchers validate the grouping of cells by function, and in different species, cell classes might often share similar transcriptomes not by conservation, but by convergence (Konstantinides et al., 2018). Valid cell archeclasses, thus, may be para- or polyphyletic, as long as they are helpful in research.

Of note, determining the evolutionary relations of cell classes is not necessary for appreciating the value of archeclasses for education. High-school-level textbooks, for example, use archeclasses to introduce students to the basic functionalities of neurons, but neurons might have a polyphyletic origin. (Burkhardt & Sprecher, 2017; Moroz, 2009)

Archeclasses are also of value for databases, and arguably the most important resource of single-cell RNA-seq data for humans in 2023, CELLxGENE, relied heavily on the Cell Ontology species-neutral concepts (archeclasses) to annotate cell types (CZI Single-Cell Biology Program et al., 2023). Nevertheless, much of our reasoning as scientists occurs at the species level. Thus, it is essential to formalize our concept of cell classes for single species, especially if we are to build a Human Cell Atlas.

5.5.2 *Sensu stricto* cell classes

The concept of species is central to modern biology and the representation of biological concepts. The nomenclature and organization of species are at the heart of the taxonomy field, and information at the species level is the usual base for knowledge systems, encyclopedias, conservation strategies, and biodiversity lists.

Besides the direct use of species, other biological entities inherit the species-level specificity. Model Organism Databases (like Pombase, ZFIN, and FlyBase) organize data of individual species, and genes receive nomenclatures at the species level (*TP53* for *Homo sapiens*, *Tp53* for *Mus musculus*, for example). The reference genomes are also built at the species level, collecting references for single species. The same applies to the reference sequence of protein entities, defined at the species level.

The same applies to cells. The Human Cell Atlas is a species-specific endeavor, and while it may benefit from data obtained from other species, they complement the goal of deriving a parts list of the human body. Thus, it seems necessary to catalog cell classes at the species level. A human neutrophil will always have different properties from a mouse neutrophil besides appearing in mice. This is well exemplified in practice from studies with chimeric mice: laboratory mice engrafted with human glial progenitor cells will develop a "*humanized white matter*" and have human-derived myelin (Mariani et al., 2019). The cells do not become mice glial progenitors just because they are present in mice.

In knowledge management systems, we often want to connect cell types with gene markers and core transcription factors. We currently do not have standardized, widely used nomenclatures for a set of homologous genes across species, and it is reasonable to expect that similar cell types in two species may have some different markers.

As the species concept is already at the base of knowledge systems, explicitly acknowledging and cataloging cells at the species levels is a natural step in knowledge management. Notably, while the Cell Ontology started as a species-neutral catalog of cell types (archeclasses), it grew to gradually include species-specific cell types for *Mus musculus* and *Homo sapiens* (*sensu stricto* cell classes).

5.5.3 Infraclasses

While literature reviews and scientific theorization about cells usually occur at the species level, individual scientific experiments rarely include a representative sample of the variety of cells within a species. Quite the opposite happens in laboratory conditions, where isogenic mouse lines are bred to "*allow experimenters to vary only the parameters of interest and to measure their effects (ruling out genetic variance), which is important for discovering causal factors and allowing experimental reproducibility*". Even though inbred strains are not perfectly isogenic in practice, and subject to several evolutionary processes, they are perfect to show the theoretical need for cataloging cell classes below the species level. (Chebib et al., 2021)

The nomenclature of *infraclass* applies to theoretical groupings of cells in a particular subpopulation, strain, species, or any other subspecific group of individuals. Cell types in different strains are known to showcase biological differences. For example, the discovery of the Th1 and Th2 cell types in immunology was made possible by the failure of strains of BALB/c mice to control experimental infection by *Leishmania major*. On the other hand, other strains of the same species, such as the C57BL/6 strain, are resistant to infection (Sacks & Noben-Trauth, 2002). Of note, recent research on immunology indicates an intrinsic difference in unstimulated macrophages in BALB/c and C57BL/6, indicating the need for infraclasses for accurate knowledge representation for single-cell RNA-seq data (Breda et al., 2022).

5.5.4 Technoclasses

While infraclasses are necessary to represent strain-level cell knowledge, the theoretical objects targeted by single experiments are of an even more granular nature. Besides being usually from a single strain/subpopulation, they are probed in non-random research setups filled with pragmatic choices. For example, researchers might use the name "CD4 T cells" when referring to flow-cytometry sorted CD3⁺, CD4⁺, CD8⁻ cells from the axillary lymph node of 2-month-old chow-fed female BALB/c mice from the mouse-house of the Institute of Chemistry of the University of São Paulo collected on several mornings around 10 pm.

Although quite specific, all the mentioned facets (markers, anatomical location, age, diet, biological sex, strain, housing conditions, and circadian clock) are known to alter what we know about cell types (see Tabansky et al. for a more extended discussion ([Tabansky et al., 2015](#))). The cross-product of these different facets creates a particular class targeted by an experiment. Defining a class logically by the cross-product of characteristics is a well-known strategy, even used for describing some Gene Ontology entities ([Mungall et al., 2011](#)). Here, we call this class, consisting of the combination of all experimentally-restricted features, a technoclass.

A technoclass is still a class, not an individual entity or group, even if it is specific. A researcher should be able to re-sample the class, a basic criterion for reproducibility. Formally, the technoclass is a universal, not a continuant. In the words of Grenon, Smith, and Goldberg, "*Universals are the real invariants or patterns in the world apprehended by the specific sciences. Universals are multiply instantiated: they wholly exist at different places and different times in the different particulars which instantiate them* ([Smith et al., 2004](#))."

The technoclass is the universal class whose instances have a certain distribution, from which we take samples and for which statistical tests are expected to hold. In our view, it is the most granular cell class for research synthesis. The technoclass mirrors the idea from Gene Ontology that annotations should be made for the most specific terms available, to avoid overstating and imprecision ([Balakrishnan et al., 2013](#)). As such, Gene Ontology

extension annotations that provide experimental context (Huntley et al., 2014) should, theoretically, refer to technoclasses if the goal is to maximize precision.

Implicitly, scientific claims are made and tested for technoclass, and we speculate that overstating reports conflating technoclasses and *sensu stricto* cell classes are the source of much confusion in current biomedical research. The claims about techno classes can base statements reaching a higher degree of universality. Still, if we are to be rigorous, this theoretical move should not be implicit (see Yarkoni for a similar problem in the psychological sciences (Yarkoni, 2019)). In the Popperian framework of how science should work logically, knowledge may only travel “quasi-inductionally” by fostering hypotheses with higher degrees of generality, which can then be tested for the universal class (Popper, 2013). While scientists might navigate more freely the rules of logic, computational systems cannot afford such looseness, and thus computable classifications need to be very explicit as to the real-world objects they refer to.

5.6 Contextualizing the theory

5.6.1 Cell type claims in published research

The set of criteria and definitions here may also contribute to formalizing new cell claims and streamlining the discovery and registering process for cell classes.

Suppose one explicitly claims to have discovered a new *sensu stricto* cell class. In that case, one should provide enough evidence that cells from this class are identifiable across individuals of a species (given the constraints as age and biological sex). A claim of an archeclass would require evidence of existence in more than one species. Consequently, experiments would *not* be able to call a newly discovered single-cell RNA-seq cluster a new *sensu stricto* cell class (or cell type), unless there is evidence from multiple populations.

An example of the discovery of a new archeclass that provided multispecies evidence is the pair of articles published in *Nature* in 2018 about the newly found “ionocyte,” a class of cells in the trachea enriched for the expression of genes homologous to the human *CFTR* gene (Montoro et al., 2018; Plasschaert et al., 2018). Both studies displayed evidence for such a class in both mouse and human samples, corroborating the archeclass’s existence. This discovery of an archeclass has been denominated by both articles as a discovery of a new cell type.

In another example of cell type discovery, Villani et al. describe subclasses of monocytes and dendritic cells in humans, including the AXL+ SIGLEC6+ AS dendritic cell (Villani et al., 2017). The cells were detected from patients from “*the Boston-based PhenoGenetic project (...) and the Newcastle community.*” It is noticeable that the sampling implies a skewed sample of humanity, though this is not clear in the results. It is possible that the described class is not present in South American indigenous populations, for example, or people of sub saharan or Middle-Eastern descent. The jump from the infraclass to, then, *sensu stricto* cell class (all humans) is done at once the paper. While the work is of the utmost technical quality, it might be overstating in affirming the identification of a new *human* cell type. It could be a *British-descent* infraclass for all we know.

5.6.2 The vast number of cell classes

Given the biodiversity of Earth, the complexity of multicellular life, and the intricacies of research, it is evident that the number of archeclasses, *sensu stricto* classes, infraclasses, and technoclasses is absurdly huge. With millions of cataloged animal species, it is reasonable to estimate that the order of magnitude exceeds hundreds of millions of *sensu stricto* cell classes. For well-researched species, like *Homo sapiens* and *Mus musculus*, there are millions of research articles published every year, which may discuss particular populations and settings, putting the numbers of technoclasses also in high magnitudes. The number of human *sensu stricto* cell classes might not be that large. However, pinning a particular number will depend on

our knowledge of infrastructures, the requirements of the parts list for what counts as applicable and our ability to disambiguate and merge synonyms.

Estimating the number of currently useful classes would be harder than estimating the number of cell types, depending on the philosophical foundations one stands on. Some pin the number of cell types in under 6000 (Quake, 2021) and others use just around 400 types (but 1264 cell *groups*, spread in 60 tissues) for calculating the total number of human cells (Hatton et al., 2023). Others calculate that just *Drosophila* brains have around 3800 types, and as they are quite small animals with around 150.000 neurons, we would expect the human brain and its almost 100.000.000.000 neurons to host a larger diversity (Bates et al., 2019; Herculano-Houzel, 2009). In any case, while there may be biological discontinuities and genomically encoded programs, such as CoRCs, which may put a real-world limit on the number of cell *types*, the intricacies of human thought and life sciences research make cataloging the technically valid and useful cell classes a likely more extensive task.

In any case, the scale of the task implies a need to use our information infrastructures the best we can. Sabina Leonelli states that the challenges raised by big data in biology require advancing our philosophical theories, and we argue that the converse is also true: advancing the theoretical foundations of modern biology requires us to harness the power of computational tools (Leonelli, 2019). In other words, to organize and formalize what we know about cells, we must use databases and schemas, save information in digital memory, and leverage computer processing.

For example, we don't need to agree on a single naming system or a language for that naming system to catalog cell classes. In parallel, each class can be assigned a Unique Resource Identifier, a URI, or its Internationalized version, and IRI, enabling unambiguous identification of each concept. IRIs, which are resolvable on the web and thus self-explainable, are the current best practice for cataloging biomedical resources (McMurry et al., 2017). This technique is already used by the Cell

Ontology (CL) and in the knowledge graph of Wikidata to represent cell types (Diehl et al., 2016; Waagmeester et al., 2020).

Of note, the classification of cells into classes and the naming of cell types are related, but parallel tasks. While there has been progress on rules for naming cell types (particularly in neuroscience), discussing the nomenclature criteria is outside this work's scope (Hamilton et al., 2016; Miller et al., 2020; Shepherd et al., 2019). As mentioned before, URIs are the best practice for information systems, with the potential benefit of being opaque. Opaque alpha-numeric identifiers, without inherent meaning, can help us avoid discussions on purported essences of cell classes, a benefit discussed at least since 1977 (Rowe & Stone, 1977).

The usage of URIs and unique identifiers has pragmatic importance. Over the past few years, several single-cell transcriptomics tools have been developed to try and assign labels to cell observations. There is a clear rush towards tools to “call” cell types, but we have yet to agree on a common identification standard for cell types (Clarke et al., 2021). Several tools in the Human Cell Atlas ecosystem have chosen the Cell Ontology as the trusted provider of cell types (or cell classes) names. (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021) The last part of this chapter discusses the CELLxGENE use of cell classes (or types) and the implications of our theoretical system for better knowledge management in that context.

5.7 Atomic cell classes in CELLxGENE

The last part of this chapter is dedicated to one more pragmatic definition: the *atomic cell class*, an indivisible cell class, given a context in which the concept can be factored out in meaningful parts. Take, as an example, the concept of a retinal glutamatergic neuron. In theory, we may consider strictly neurons as the *atomic cell class*, factoring out the retinal presence and glutamate transmission as simply modifiers. A database may implement the theory, allocating space to record separately the location of the cell, the retina, and the neurotransmitter used, glutamate. If the database only has a field for location, the atomic cell becomes

glutamatergic neuron. Consequently, the database must identify retinal glutamatergic neuron as its atomic cell class if no fields are available.

Besides pragmatic applications, theoreticians can introduce constraints to determine atomic cell types at a purely theoretical level. The term *cell state* is widely used to describe cell types with complementary properties considered secondary or ephemeral. Usually, the so-called *cell states* are composed of cell types and some qualifiers such as *proliferating* or *migratory*. The task of how databases represent cell states and other non-canonical cell classes remains open. Solutions include incorporating states into atomic classes, such as a resting double-positive thymocyte or not adding them anywhere, and using new facets to organize thoughts, such as adding a cell activity dimension to the database (Figure X)

November 15th, 2023 ▾

D

David Osumi-Sutherland 2:06 PM

Hi @channel - Quick poll;

There is significant demand for compound terms for cell type x Cell state - mostly commonly recording cell cycle but also other states we could record by combining a CL term with a GO term following a standard pattern. It is hard to persuade the developers of annotation pipelines to post-compose terms so we would like a home for single compound terms - added using DOSDPs. We would like to poll for possible solutions:

1. Add these to CL. Vote with 1
2. Add these to PCL. Vote with 2
3. New ontology with compound IDs (more infrastructure needed) 3
4. Don't add them anywhere! 🤖

2319🤖 1👍 2😊

1 reply 2 months ago

Figure X: Slack thread in the Cell Ontology workspace bringing into discussion the open-endedness of the compound term (cell type + cell state) situation. CL: Cell

Ontology, GO: Gene Ontology, PCL: Provisional Cell Ontology, DOSDPs: Dead Simple Ontology Design Patterns

The framework of the *atomic cell classes* is an extension of the four-class system described before, where the organismal taxonomy is treated as a unique dimension for its value in biology. An information system might have two columns, one describing species and the other describing the *archeclass*. Or, instead, it may have a single column, encoding the species + *archeclass* combination, denoting a *sensu stricto cell class*. The choice will depend on the technical implementation of the infrastructure and is scientifically equivalent.

Applying this framework in practice requires identifying a context and its constraints first and then classifying cell types for the task of interest. In the Human Cell Atlas endeavor, arguably the most well-structured context is provided by the CELLxGENE platform, which harmonizes and reannotates datasets across the biomedical landscape. Thus, our approach in this work is to use the CELLxGENE platform as a case study for atomic cell types. We'll describe an overview of annotations in the CELLxGENE platform for the Human Lung Cell Atlas (**Figure Y**) and how *atomic cell class* can improve knowledge modeling and data integration.

5.7.1 The CELLxGENE platform

The CELLxGENE (pronounced *cell by gene*) platform is currently the best system for annotating and visualizing cell types in single-cell RNA-seq datasets. The platform includes free-form annotations (what the authors want to say) and normalized fields with ontology terms (what the authors can tell given the constraints). Data is shown in a UMAP projection that can be colored by several Standard Categories and Author Categories, which include different facets of the data. (CZI Single-Cell Biology Program et al., 2023)

Figure Y - The CELLxGENE platform for the integrated Human Lung Cell Atlas dataset²⁶

The Standard Categories in CELLxGENE provide essential context for delimiting atomic cell classes. Data annotated with these categories are more accessible for algorithmic parsing and integration with other datasets, minimizing manual mapping errors and time consumption. As of January 2024, the reannotation of author labels

²⁶

<https://CELLxGENE.cziscience.com/e/9f222629-9e39-47d0-b83f-e08d610c7479.cxg/>

adheres to a well-structured schema, currently at version 4.1.0²⁷, detailed in Table 1. Some categories are useful only to find datasets (author, gene count, cell count, publication date) while others describe the technical context of the observation (assay, suspension type, is primary data).

Table 1: Metadata Categories, Ontologies, and Entry Types on CELLxGENE M

Category	Description	Examples	Ontology Used
Assay	Type of assay used	drop-seq, 10x 3' v1	EFO
Author	Dataset contributor	Teichmann, Sarah A., Regev, Aviv	none, free text
Cell Count	Number of cells in the dataset	146, 413434	none, integer
Donor ID	Unique identifier for individual donors	-	none, local ids
Is Primary Data	Indicates primary data source	true, false	local controlled vocabulary
Suspension Type	Type of cell suspension	cell, nucleus or na	Local controlled vocabulary
Publication Date	Date of dataset publication	-	none, date
Gene Count	Number of genes in the dataset	3234, 52000	none, integer
Cell Type	Type of cells	B cell, club cell	CL
Development Stage	Stage of development	1-month-old human stage	HsapDv

²⁷

<https://github.com/chanzuckerberg/single-cell-curation/blob/main/schema/4.1.0/schema.md>

Disease	Associated disease	COVID-19, cystic fibrosis	MONDO
Organism	Species	<i>Homo sapiens</i> , , <i>Mus musculus</i>	NCBITaxon
Self-Reported Ethnicity	Self-reported ethnicity	African, Asian	HANCESTRO
Sex	Biological sex	male, unknown female,	PATO
Tissue	Tissue source	lung, heart	UBERON

All other categories described are relevant for describing cell diversity and could all be lumped together to form highly detailed cell classes (*technoclasses*) , such as a COVID-19 40-year-old female caucasian *Homo sapiens* lung club cell. This class is very specific, but in a system lacking descriptive fields it would be a valid *atomic cell class*. The absence of these monsters in CELLxGENE is evidence that the database implements the atomic cell class concept tacitly, where a “cell type” field covers one phenotypical dimension and other fields cover the others.

5.7.2 Fixing duplicated terms with atomic cell types

As the atomic cell class concept is currently only used implicitly, some knowledge modeling inconsistencies exist in the database.

For example, in a dataset for the pediatric human gut (Figure ZA), there are cells annotated with *archeoclasses* (conventional dendritic cell). In contrast, other cells are annotated at the *sensu stricto cell class* level (dendritic cell, human).

The ambiguity introduces confusion and hinders data integration, with duplication of information and the possibility of confusion, given that other human datasets are annotated with just dendritic cell (Figure ZB). Thus, the CELLxGENE annotation team could improve their annotation procedure to avoid duplication by specifying the requirements for species-neutral *archeclasses* in their metadata schema.

A similar situation happens with tissue-specific terms. Some annotations in the Human Lung Cell Atlas use lung-specific Cell Ontology classes such as lung pericyte, lung macrophage, and lung neuroendocrine cell. As the "lung" information is already captured in the "tissue" field, there is redundancy to redundancy. General, tissue-neutral, terms would be preferred, keeping information in the correct buckets.

A	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> M cell of gut 249 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> T follicular helper cell 232 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> activated CD4-po... a-beta T cell, human 301 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> conventional dendritic cell 398 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> dendritic cell, human 43 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> endothelial cell of artery 355	B	dendritic cell, human 7 dendritic cell, non-specific 72
----------	--	----------	--

Figure Z: Annotations in CELLxGENE showing a mix-up of species-neutral archeclasses and human-specific cell classes. A) terms in a Pediatric Human Gut Atlas²⁸. B) Search results for “dendritic cell” in datasets containing only *Homo sapiens* cells, showing duplication of labels.

²⁸

<https://CELLxGENE.cziscience.com/e/8e47ed12-c658-4252-b126-381df8d52a3d.cxg/>

5.7.3 Partitioning cell states in the context of atomic cell types

Besides helping to organize current labels, atomic cell classes can help developers improve navigation on the platform by creating new ways to handle cell states or non-cataloged cell types.

Currently, author labels undergo lossy transformations when annotating cell types to standard terms. For example, the “finest_level” annotation of the Human Lung Cell Atlas²⁹ contains different cell states that are dropped when cell type annotations are normalized (Figure W). For example, the author-provided labels outline 3 classes of lymphatic endothelial cells: *Lymphatic EC differentiating*, *Lymphatic EC mature* and *Lymphatic EC proliferating*. Fine-grained information is lost when labels are converted into *endothelial cell of the lymphatic vessel*.

Figure W. Example of lossy annotation in the CELLxGENE platform. The “proliferating” state is lumped with a general state, and mature and differentiating cells are lumped together.

²⁹

<https://CELLxGENE.cziscience.com/e/9f222629-9e39-47d0-b83f-e08d610c7479.cxg/>

There are two main technical options for preserving the information in the structured database: (1) adding the new terms to the registry of cell types used or (2) adding a new ontology with missing complements.

The first option entails minting a new identifier for the cell class in the registry of reference, where the crafting of new terms would require approval by the curators of the registry.

The Cell Ontology, the current registry for CELLxGENE cell types, has some terms that are compounded with non-anatomical features, like maturity (e.g., mature astrocyte, mature neutrophil, and immature B cell) and proliferativeness (e.g., resting double-positive thymocyte). There is, thus, some precedent for new terms for the missing classes in Figure W in the scope of the Cell Ontology.

THEORETICAL APPLICATION OF THE ATOMIC CELL TYPE FRAMEWORK

Figure Q: Implementation of the atomic cell class in the CELLxGENE system. (A) The qualifying slots present in the CELLxGENE platform and some possible, missing dimensions of cells in the system. (B) A simple decision tree for how to preserve meaning for a new term submitted to CELLxGENE, outlining some possible paths. Currently, the extra information is lost by the schema.

However, it needs to be clarified from the Cell Ontology guidelines if cell *states* or compound terms are within its scope or not, and as it can be seen in Figure X, there are multiple internal opinions on it. Cell-type registries should be able to cover all atomic cell classes needed by major resources that rely on it. In this case, if

CELLxGENE and Cell Ontology are to partner up in cell classification, Cell Ontology should also cover cell states and compounded terms to the extent required by data. As long as a class is logically valid and needed to annotate actual data, the curation of the term should be non-controversial.

Table 2 - Author labels of the Human Lung Cell Atlas, their mapping to Cell Ontology, and possible complements.

Author Annotation	Cell Ontology label	Missing information
EC aerocyte capillary	capillary endothelial cell	specialized cell type: aerocyte
Alveolar Mph CCL3+	alveolar macrophage	CCL3+
Lymphatic EC mature	endothelial cell of lymphatic vessel	mature
Basal resting	respiratory basal cell	resting
Suprabasal	respiratory basal cell	suprabasal
SM activated stress response	smooth muscle cell	activated stress response
EC venous systemic	vein endothelial cell	systemic
Interstitial Mph perivascular	lung macrophage	Interstitial and perivascular
EC general capillary	capillary endothelial cell	specialized cell type: general lung capillary (distinct from aerocyte)
Peribronchial fibroblasts	bronchus fibroblast of lung	peribronchial
pre-TB secretory	epithelial cell of lower respiratory tract	pre-TB
AT0	epithelial cell of alveolus of lung	specialized cell type: AT0
Lymphatic EC differentiating	endothelial cell of lymphatic vessel	differentiating
Alveolar Mph MT-positive	alveolar macrophage	MT-positive
Smooth muscle FAM83D+	stromal cell	FAM83D+
Migratory DCs	dendritic cell	migratory
Alveolar Mph proliferating	alveolar macrophage	proliferating
AT2 proliferating	type II pneumocyte	proliferating
Subpleural fibroblasts	fibroblast	subpleural

SMG duct	acinar cell	SMG (submucosal gland)
Goblet (subsegmental)	tracheobronchial goblet cell	subsegmental
Deuterosomal	multi-ciliated epithelial cell	specialized cell type: deuterosomal cell
Lymphatic EC proliferating	endothelial cell of lymphatic vessel	proliferating

The second approach would be leaving the cell ontology terms as they are and filling the missing pieces with post-composition. For example, some of these terms for cell states could be derived from the Gene Ontology (as shown in the comments in Figure X). The pieces of information not currently covered by the CELLxGENE schema are varied, and scientists are often creative with their categories and add unpredictable, a priori dimensions. In Table 2, we explore the cell classes in the Human Lung Cell Atlas, displaying the complements for author fields currently missing for the interface. Extending this analysis for CELLxGENE is needed for a complete panorama and roadmap on improving information coverage.

5.8 Discussion

In this work, we shared some thoughts on how we can organize our knowledge about cells. Based on technical and logical foundations, knowledge systems should focus, at the first moment, not on cell *types* or *states*, but on the more general concept of cell classes. We further subdivide the *cell class* concept, leveraging organism taxonomy as a grounding point for *archeclasses* (multi-species), *sensu stricto cell classes* (single species), *infraclasses* (particular subpopulations), and *technoclasses* (specific experiments).

After a theoretical presentation of the concepts, we discussed a practical context: the management of cell knowledge in the CELLxGENE platform. One dataset in the platform, The Human Lung Cell Atlas, was explored to demonstrate that by using *atomic cell classes*, we can better organize knowledge, detect redundancies, improve database schemas, and identify terms to catalog in cell type registries. The

concept of *atomic cell class* is generalizable to other pragmatic and theoretical contexts and could facilitate thinking when organizing knowledge in the context of the Human Cell Atlas. Of note, when discussing the practical details of the cell by gene, we found that the concepts in the first half of the work were useful to convey ideas more clearly, in anecdotal evidence for the usefulness of this system.

The logical systems presented here are foundational for the other parts of the thesis. We used them explicitly and sometimes implicitly to guide the curation of cell types via Wikidata and the role of the interplay of Cell Ontology and Wikidata in this ecosystem. Besides the immediate usefulness of this Ph.D. thesis, the logical system presented here provides clear, solid bases for representing cells in knowledge systems. It will help us better define and catalog classes of cells in general, ultimately improving the state-of-the-art data annotation and our comprehension of the parts that make up our human bodies.

6. Guidelines for reporting cell types: the MIRACL standard

Nomenclature, the other foundation of botany, should provide the names as soon as the classification is made...If the names are unknown knowledge of the things also perishes.

Carl Linnaeus, translated by Frans A. Stafleu

6.1 Thesis considerations

This chapter is a formatted version of a scientific article published as a Preprint in Arxiv (LUBIANA et al., 2022a). This work, constructed in dialogue with editors of the Cell Ontology, discussed the formation of a standard for reporting cell types in the scientific literature. The need for such a standard became clear during the curation of cell types described in the previous chapter.

The work was mostly used by the HubMAP community in a few of their inner pipelines to catalyze the process of bringing data into the Cell Ontology. We plan on revisiting the work and submitting it to publication in a peer-reviewed journal taking in consideration the fast advances related to data about cell types and the way they are mentioned in the literature. Meanwhile, it has influenced heavily the framework described later in the thesis to curate cells into Wikidata, thus having an immediate impact in the development of this work.

Cell types are at the root of modern biology, and describing them is a core task of the Human Cell Atlas project. Surprisingly, there are no standards for reporting new cell types, leading to a gap between classes mentioned in biomedical literature and the Cell Ontology, the primary registry of cell types. Here we introduce the **Minimal Information Reporting About a Cell** (MIRACL) standard, a guideline for describing cell types alongside scientific articles. In a MIRACL sheet, authors organize a label,

a diagnostic description, a taxon, an anatomical structure, and a parent cell class for each cell type of interest. The MIRACL standard bridges the gap between wet-lab researchers and ontologists, facilitating the integration of biomedical knowledge into ontologies and artificial intelligence systems.

Cell-type-oriented research has gained traction thanks to the recent blooming of projects like the Human Cell Atlas (HCA) (ROZENBLATT-ROSEN et al., 2017), the Human Protein Atlas (HPA)(KARLSSON et al., 2021), the Human BioMolecular Atlas Program (HuBMAP) (HUBMAP CONSORTIUM et al., 2019) and more (ANDO; KWON; SHIN, 2020). These efforts encompass diverse domains, from morphology to biophysics to molecular biology, and data integration requires advanced knowledge management. Programs like the Cell Annotation Platform (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021), the CCF ASCT+B Reporter (BÖRNER et al., 2021) and the Chan-Zuckerberg Initiative cellxgene Discover (CZI SINGLE-CELL BIOLOGY PROGRAM et al., 2023) are contributing to and reusing data annotation from the Cell Ontology (DIEHL et al., 2016) to standardize references to cell types.

Despite the importance of curation, the community has yet to agree on common standards to report cell types in the scientific literature. Minimum information standards are widely used for assays and data reporting, and submission of standardized data to public databases is a prerequisite for publication when articles describe e.g. DNA and protein sequences and protein structures. Although there are standards for single-cell RNA-seq data (FÜLLGRABE et al., 2020) there is a broader urge to standardize metadata of cell type discoveries, consequently improving the organization of knowledge about cell types and states. (AEVERMANN et al., 2018; BAKKEN et al., 2017; MEEHAN et al., 2011; MILLER et al., 2020; PANINA et al., 2020)

In this perspective, we discuss the creation of guidelines for reporting cell classes, namely a Minimal Information Reporting About a Cell (MIRACL) standard focusing on the curation provided by the Cell Ontology. We outline a set of core fields for

cataloging new types, and provide a schema and template for orienting reports of new cell classes.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Who can report a MIRACL sheet?

Cell types are currently described in various research contexts, few of which are solely descriptive, microanatomy works. Any research involving a cell class not cataloged in the Cell Ontology would benefit from providing a MIRACL sheet. We outline three different situations in which a MIRACL sheet would be most valuable: (1) articles claiming new cell types/subtypes (STECCO et al., 2018; VILLANI et al., 2017) Sometimes a close superclass is cataloged, but there is value in reporting specific subclasses, as researchers might want to represent different degrees of granularity; (2) articles bringing up information that might change the classification of a cell type, for example the identification of a cell type in a different region (ELMENTAITE et al., 2020) and (3) articles mentioning previously identified cell types in other works that are not cataloged in the Cell Ontology. (BIGAEVA et al., 2020) Scenarios may include proposing a synonym for a previously reported cell type. (POPESCU; FAUSSONE-PELLEGRINI, 2010)

Figure 1: The flow from cell type discovery to knowledge reuse, with an author-guided structuring of information catalyzing the biocuration process. Currently, the curation process requires Cell Ontology editors to sift through full texts to identify the core information needed to catalog cells. A MIRACL sheet would

structure information at the publication level, thereby leveraging the expertise of the original authors. That, in turn, facilitates the process of curation and, subsequently, the reuse of new terms, for example, to label clusters in single-cell omics data.

While anyone is welcome to request a new term in the Cell Ontology GitHub Tracker using standardized term templates (<https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology/issues>), ideally, we would like to engage the authors in the process, to minimize misinterpretation of data, and reduce overhead and time required for inclusion in the Cell Ontology. If authors share information in a standardized fashion, the knowledge is quickly incorporated into the system (depicted in Figure 1), magnifying the impact of articles.

6.2.2 What might a MIRACL sheet contain?

Cells are notoriously difficult to classify, as there is not a single biological feature that guides taxonomists. From simple colorimetric stains, to multiplexed immunohistochemistry, to patch clamps, to flow cytometry, to the multiple omics now performed at the single-cell level, scientists employ fundamentally different techniques to guide their perspectives on the cellular world. Any universal standard for cell type reporting faces the challenge of finding commonalities across different domains of research, while preserving the power to represent the details of each project.

A MIRACL sheet is aimed at capturing the very basic information for descriptions of new cell types. As a middle stage between full ontological axiomatization and free text, the selected fields must facilitate the work of ontology editors without requiring too much technical training of contributors. We reason that 7 different fields of information should be available for any new description of a cell type:

- A label. An unambiguous name for the cell type being described. While listing synonyms is useful, a pragmatic decision on a label is necessary when building an ontology.

-
- A diagnostic description. A concise, free-text description of the core characteristics of the class, similar to the diagnosis section in species taxonomy (WINSTON, 1999). It should suffice to distinguish the cell type from similarly existing types (e.g. the specific marker genes).
 - A superclass. A Cell Ontology class, with name and identifier, corresponding to a broader category of the new cell type. For example, a report for a new type of neuron might include “neuron (CL:0000540)” as a superclass.
 - A taxon. The scientific name for the taxon for which cells of the type are expected to be found. In most cases, it will be the name of the species in which the cells were found, but this depends on the generality claim being made.
 - An anatomical structure. The UBERON (MUNGALL et al., 2009) ontology identifier for the anatomical structure(s) in which the cells of the type were found, usually a particular organ or tissue. If cells of the type are known to span multiple structures (e.g. a long neuron), or are believed to be present in other anatomical locations, details should be noted in the additional information field. Note that some cell types, especially immune ones, may not be tied to a single anatomical structure.
 - A reference. A free-text field pointing to the reference(s) that support the new cell type.
 - Additional information. Any additional core information about the cell or the classification that complements the previous assertions, as well as details and technicalities that might aid curation.

In Table 1, we present an example of what a MIRACL sheet would look like in the case of two different publications (VILLANI et al., 2017) based on the original texts and on searching the EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service for CL and UBERON terms (JUPP et al., 2015). In a report, we propose that the information is provided in an independent tab-separated value (TSV) spreadsheet as supplementary information. Defining cell types, and attributing cell superclass(es), may sometimes

be a non-trivial task. Hence, we encourage authors to provide as many suggestions as they find relevant, rather than considering the template format as a bottleneck. A ready-to-use MIRACL template in tabular format is provided in this [Google Sheet](#).

Table 1

An example of a MIRACL sheet

Label	Diagnostic description	Superclass	Taxon	Anatomical structure	Reference	Additional information
AXL ⁺	A dendritic cell that expresses AXL and SIGLEC6.	dendritic cell (CL:000105 6)	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	blood (UBERON: 0000178)	<i>This article*</i>	-
Lamina propria fibroblast	A fibroblast in the lamina propria mucosa.	fibroblast (CL:000005 7)	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	lamina propria (UBERON: 0000030)	<i>PMID: 31474370, DOI:10.1101/2020.01.10.901579</i>	Articles used different names to refer to the class.

* If this sheet was provided alongside the original publications (BIGAEVA et al., 2020; VILLANI et al., 2017)

6.2.3 MIRACL Extensions

While MIRACL's fields are designed to be simple, there are guidelines that complement MIRACL (like the Petilla convention ("Petilla terminology: nomenclature of features of GABAergic interneurons of the cerebral cortex", 2008), Allen Institute's cell type nomenclature (MILLER et al., 2020), and Human Immunology Project Consortium's tentative standard (OVERTON et al., 2019) that might provide additional support for particular situations. Additionally, the Cell Ontology and other

OBO Foundry ontologies have tools for formal representation of other aspects of cells. To formalize, extend and make the proposal computer processable, we have started a collaborative LinkML schema (<https://lubianat.github.io/miracl/>).

The current may be extended by checklists applicable for particular communities, adding fields specific to subtypes of stem cell, neuron, immune cell, and others. The standard can also be tailored to particular experimental modalities, e.g. by adding a field for single-cell RNAseq markers, often used to define cell classes. (AEVERMANN et al., 2018)

Extensions could also adapt MIRACL to species more distant from mammals. Single-cell technology provides an opportunity to better understand plants, fungi, and bacteria (COLE et al., 2021). MIRACL could be used with adaptations for these taxa. For example, for submission of plant cell types to the Plant Ontology (PO), the anatomical structure field would require a plant structure represented in PO, rather than an Uberon term.

6.2.4 Pilot test of MIRACL sheets

To gauge community response to MIRACL standards, a pilot test was performed. The volunteers were researchers who wished to request new ontology terms for anatomical structures or cell types. Those terms were determined to be missing from either the UBERON ontology or Cell Ontology as part of their work for HuBMAP in building tables of anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers (ASCT+B). (BÖRNER et al., 2021)

To minimize barriers to submitting information conforming to MIRACL standards, MIRACL sheets were provided as Google Sheets templates to authors of ASCT+B tables for thymus, spleen and lymph node (v1.1, see Acknowledgements for details). Most wet bench researchers were uncomfortable engaging with the GitHub environment, where requests for anatomy and cell type terms are usually made, and

the MIRACL sheets provided a simple way to obtain and communicate information directly between the experts and ontology curators. The MIRACL tables curated by ASCT+B authors are provided in the [Supplementary Data](#) as examples.

Beyond the basic MIRACL information, HuBMAP ASCT+B authors have added 2 additional fields: “Gene Biomarkers” and “Protein Biomarkers”. Such extensions are welcome, as long as the core MIRACL fields are present. Additionally, the table was adapted for curating new anatomical structures for UBERON, highlighting the usefulness of the scaffold for different ontologies.

We noticed that the superclass concept was the most difficult for researchers, while all other fields of data in the MIRACL sheet were easily provided. Ontology editors further curated the superclasses provided by the authors, and the final ontology placement may be different. Thus, if navigating the ontology proves time-consuming, authors might provide broad MIRACL superclasses (e.g. “neuron” or “lymphocyte”), as these already serve as pointers to ontology editors.

6.3 Discussion

This work presents a standard to report new cell types, making cell discoveries explicit and accelerating curation by the Cell Ontology. MIRACL can accelerate biomedical discovery by supporting a more comprehensive support of CL, as it is used by a number of cell-type annotation systems and biomedical databases (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021; WANG et al., 2021). In the authors’ experience, scientists unfamiliar with GitHub repositories, and/or under tighter time constraints, are often reluctant to engage with the GitHub issue tracking system, but are happy to provide information in a MIRACL template to create or modify existing terms. This standard therefore can maximize output and minimize time needed for inclusion in the Cell Ontology - a gain for the entire community.

The MIRACL standard has been approved on FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/4117>), the major repository for biomedical standards (THE FAIRSHARING COMMUNITY et al., 2019) but it only will be truly valuable if the community adopts it. MIRACL's success also depends on being adopted by journals as a requirement for reporting new cell types, and that in turn depends on a community agreement on standard operating procedures. Additionally, if researchers submit MIRACL sheets to the Cell Ontology before article submission, the cell types would be given unique identifiers that the authors (and the community) could use promptly - similarly to how e.g. accession numbers for DNA sequences can be used even before publication.

7. Using Wikidata to curate cell types in the context of the Human Cell Atlas

En sus remotas páginas está escrito que los animales se dividen en a) pertenecientes al Emperador, b) embalsamados, c) amaestrados, d) lechones, e) sirenas, f) fabulosos, g) perros sueltos, h) incluidos en esta clasificación, i) que se agitan como locos, j) innumerables, k) dibujados con un pincel finísimo de pelo de camello, l) etcétera, m) que acaban de romper el jarrón, n) que de lejos parecen moscas.

Jorge Luis Borges

7.1 Thesis considerations

This last chapter of the thesis presents the biocuration of cell types that was done on Wikidata during the course of the PhD. Leveraging the concepts, frameworks and discussions presented before in the thesis, we built a standard procedure to triage the scientific literature for uncataloged cell types and record them in a structured, computer-processable format. The activity led to the catalog of over 4000 cell classes, all with references to sources in the literature (or, in some cases, to the Cell Ontology).

The task of curating cell types presented here was an attempt at an extensive classification using the criteria described in Chapter 3. The system of archeclasses, species-specific classes and infraclasses was not explicitly used on Wikidata, as this perspective still needs to be presented to peers (and hopefully accepted) before being put in the Wikidata system. However, the criteria for validity of a cell class, namely (1) an explicit name, (2) usefulness for theory and (3) identifiability within a group of organisms were fundamental for the decisions made in the curation process.

Inside this chapter, there are a few different sub projects amalgamated. The first is the building of a system to curate cell classes (or types) on Wikidata, which included an evaluation of the semantic infrastructure of the platform, a conventionated MIRACL-like spreadsheet-based system for recording information, and a Python module that parses this spreadsheet and adds the data to Wikidata.

The second part was the actual curation work itself, which included screening over 1000 articles, from which over 350 served as reference for the thousands of new cell classes hosted at Wikidata. It also included connecting all Wikipedia pages about cell types to the Wikidata hierarchy and quality-checking all other cell-type terms on Wikidata.

Finally, we worked on ways to make the information more readily available to researchers in the Human Cell Atlas and beyond, a task that included the creation of web pages displaying user-friendly results of SPARQL queries. It also included a detailed mapping of the terms in the Cell Ontology to Wikidata, and the development of a Wikidata userscript to connect information from the platform with the ontology curation framework.

7.2 Introduction

The diversity of cells in animals has been a cause of awe and wonder for centuries. It is not surprising that, as in other disciplines that deal with the richness of nature, the classification of cells has been part of research activities since the first observations of these elements. As reviewed by Vickaryous and Hall, 2006, in 1839, in the same work where Theodor Schwann introduced the cell theory, there is a classification of tissues (and their cells) in five main types: those comprised of isolated cells, the ones cells are combined, but independent, the ones cells are connected by intercellular substance, the ones made of fibers derived from cells, and finally the ones where cell walls have been merged. With the development of microscopy and physiology, other subdivisions came later. In 1969, Junqueira and Carneiro divided tissues (and, implicitly, their cells) into four kinds: epithelial,

muscular, nervous and connective.³⁰ In 1997, Stevens and Lowe provided a similar schema, grouping cell types in eight: epithelial, support, contractile, nerve, germ, blood, immune, and hormone-secreting cells.

These and other general schemas did not, however, catalog the cells into fine-grained types, and were mostly concerned with the larger groupings. Explicit, dedicated catalogs of cell types can be found in the literature, with 178 cell types categorized by Lentz in 1971, 210 listed by Alberts et al. in 1989 and 411 human cell types listed by Vickaryous and Hall in 2006. Lists, however, are limited in their usefulness in modern biology, as they do not provide unique identifiers and are not computable, thus less useful for e.g. annotating datasets.

The catalog and organization of cell types using unique identifiers and a computable structure arguably started with the Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA) ontology, dedicated to represent human anatomical structures, including cell types, in 2003.³¹ It was shortly followed by the development of the Cell Ontology³² in 2005 (BARD; RHEE; ASHBURNER, 2005) which cataloged 680 cell types, sorted according to the criteria used, like `cell_by_function`, `cell_by_histology` and `cell_by_ploidy`. The Cell Ontology continued to grow as the resource for cataloged cell types and became a core part of modern bioinformatics infrastructure, particularly in the context of the Human Cell Types, assembling, until 2021, "2,401 terms covering all major cell types." (OSUMI-SUTHERLAND et al., 2021)

The sociotechnical process of curation by the Cell Ontology has some particularities. Firstly, the resource is much richer than just a list: cell types cataloged have textual and computable definitions, tying cell types to cell components, anatomical structures, biological components and more. It is under the larger scope of computational ontologies and the OBO Foundry community, with a set of strict

³⁰ <https://ww3.icb.usp.br/conheca-o-livro-brasileiro-que-e-referencia-mundial-no-ensino-de-histologia/>

³¹ The number of cell types cataloged in FMA was not reported directly by the authors. Currently, there are over 800 subclasses of "cell" cataloged in FMA (<https://w.wiki/AKBx>).

³² The term Cell Ontology, mentioned in upper case, refers both to the community of curators and the catalog itself, being used indistinguishably in the scientific literature. A similar polysemy is seen in mentions of other ontologies, e.g. the Gene Ontology.

guidelines and several technical checks to ensure perfect logic consistency and interoperability with catalogs of other entities (such as those run by the Gene Ontology and the UBERON anatomy ontology). (THE OBI CONSORTIUM et al., 2007) These perks come with the side effect that a large amount of technical, niche informatics skills is needed to get involved. Additionally, while the ontology adopts an open, community-contribution system, few people are technically able to contribute to its open-source code system on GitHub. The Cell Ontology is also monolingual, cataloging only names used in English, and restricted in scope to cell types, thus requiring editors to be able to navigate multiple ontologies and communities to contribute.

In that way, while the Cell Ontology is growing to be the *de facto* scientific reference for cell types, its technical intricacies make it possible to think of complementary systems to catalog cell diversity that could be more inclusive technically, multilingual, and with more flexibility, leading to a faster catalog of cell diversity. This speed is of particular importance given the modern advances in single-cell analytics, particularly with the vertiginous rise in the number of single-cell RNA-seq datasets, with an ever-increasing number of probed cells, reported clusters, and annotated cell types. (SVENSSON; BELTRAME; PACHTER, 2020)

Wikipedia is one extremely successful project that is in some ways complementary to the curation in computational ontologies of the OBO Foundry. It is technically easy to contribute to, uniting a large number of voluntary contributors that quickly update information, which is, in turn, immediately available on the web, with large reach (the epistemic virtues of power, speed, and fecundity). (FALLIS, 2008b) As such, Wikipedia has also been a platform for cataloging encyclopedic information about cell types, with an explicit list of human cell types (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_distinct_cell_types_in_the_adult_human_body) and a Category:Human cells collecting a number of entries on cell types (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Human_cells).

In 2013, the Wikimedia Foundation started a sister project to Wikipedia, Wikidata, a structured, multilingual knowledge graph of encyclopedic information and a central hub connecting Wikipedia pages across different languages. (VRANDEČIĆ; PINTSCHER; KRÖTZSCH, 2023) Wikidata gradually acquired a large community of contributors and became a hub in the web of knowledge, including as a host of identifiers and collecting biomedical contents from several sources, forming a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) knowledge graph for the life sciences. (SHAFEE et al., 2023; WAAGMEESTER et al., 2020)

In this work, we describe how we leveraged the infrastructure of Wikidata to catalog and curate cell types, using a lightweight framework that requires only a basic laptop to run. With over 4000 newly cataloged cell types from over 350 sources together with quality-checks and enrichment from the terms present in the platform, Wikidata became the largest multi-species catalog of cell types to date, amassing over 6000 manually-curated, literature-referenced cell classes in a fully-connected multi hierarchy. Of note, these classes include links to more than 100 language versions of Wikipedia, bridging encyclopedias across the world. Below, we will present the tools developed for the task, the results of the curation and the processes we devise to use this information both directly in research practices and on OBO Foundry ontologies, contributing to the technical infrastructure of cell atlases.

7.3 Methods

7.3.1 A system to curate cell types to Wikidata

Articles read during the course of Ph.D. were screened for mentions of cell types absent from Wikidata. We considered a “cell type” as any class of cells described by a domain expert with evidence of the reality of its instances, following the ideas discussed in Chapter 3.

After identifying potentially new cell classes, the authors double-checked Wikidata manually for its absence and for figuring out a parent class in the hierarchy. If the

class was indeed absent from Wikidata, the new term was added to a MIRACL-like Google Spreadsheet (LUBIANA et al., 2022a), as shown in Figure *workflow_for_curation*.

The following fields were present on the database and curated for every cell type.

- *label*: The main label for the cell type, preferably as used by the authors. As per convention on Wikidata, terms start with a lowercase. Recorded as *rdfs:label* value in English.
- *subclass of*: One or more (tab-separated) unique terms for the direct parent classes on the Wikidata hierarchy. A dictionary was used to match the term to Wikidata QIDs. Recorded as the value of the Item property P279 (subclass of)
- *stated in*: The QID for the reference supporting the existence of this particular cell type. Recorded in the provenance structure for the "instance of cell type" statement (P31 Q189118) as the value of the Item property P248 (stated in)

In the spreadsheet to the unique identifiers for the concepts on Wikidata. The dictionaries are obtained by a mix of manual curation and via custom SPARQL queries.

Abstract

The heterogeneity of endothelial cells (ECs) across tissues remains incompletely inventoried. We constructed an atlas of >32,000 single-EC transcriptomes from 11 mouse tissues and identified 78 EC subclusters, including Aqp7⁺ intestinal capillaries and angiogenic ECs in healthy tissues. ECs from

The image shows a workflow for curating Wikidata entries. It starts with a table in a spreadsheet application titled "Biocuration of Cell Classes for Wikidata". The table has columns labeled B, C, and D. The first row contains the labels "subclass of", "stated in", and "aliases". The second row contains the values "endothelial cell", "Q89720882", and "angiogenic EC". A red box highlights the text "angiogenic ECs" in the abstract above, with a red arrow pointing to the "angiogenic EC" cell in the table. A green arrow points from the "angiogenic endothelial cell" cell in the table to a Wikidata page for "angiogenic endothelial cell (Q109908611)". The Wikidata page shows the cell type "angiogenic EC" and lists statements: "instance of" (cell type) and "subclass of" (endothelial cell).

	B	C	D
label	subclass of	stated in	aliases
angiogenic endothelial cell	endothelial cell	Q89720882	angiogenic EC

angiogenic endothelial cell (Q109908611)...

cell type
angiogenic EC

- Most relevant properties which are absent: ID
- Recoin: Most relevant properties which are absent
- In more languages

Statements

- instance of
by TiagoLubiana
cell type ...
stated in
Single-Cell Transcriptome Atlas of Murine Endothelial Cells
1 reference
- subclass of
by TiagoLubiana
endothelial cell ...
0 references

Figure {{workflow_for_curation}}

Additionally, other fields such as anatomical *location* and *aliases* were used when deemed relevant. In parallel to the curation of cell classes, we also curated reported markers for the cell types occasionally when they were available, using a similar system, but relying on the fields *label* (a species-specific cell type, matched post-hoc for a QID), *marker* (a list of genes, matched post-hoc to QIDs, P8872), *stated in* (as above) and *quotation* (an excerpt of text justifying the claim, P1683).

The information from the spreadsheet was pulled by a command-line, open-source Python module and processed locally, using a series of dictionaries to match the natural language

In the example shown in Figure *workflow_for_curation*, the string “endothelial cell” under the *subclass of* field spreadsheet was matched semi-automatically to the Wikidata entry “[Q11394395](#)”, which represents that concept on Wikidata. After reconciling the data, the script uses the Wikidata Integrator python package ([github.com/SuLab/WikidataIntegrator](#)) to insert new entries or update previously existing ones on the Wikidata database, making sure to not overwrite changes done by other users in the graphical interface. The code for integrating a Google Spreadsheet to Wikidata is available at [github.com/lubianat/wikidata_cell_curation](#).

7.3.2 The connection of Wikidata to the Cell Ontology

To map the Cell Ontology on Wikidata, we proposed and got the approval of a specific Wikidata identifier for the Cell Ontology, the “Cell Ontology ID” ([wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P7963](#)). After approval, identifiers could be added to Wikidata entities to connect them to external databases, enabling integrative SPARQL queries. Besides using the common Wikidata interface, one can crowd-curate identifiers via a 3rd-party service, Mix’N’Match, which provides a user-friendly framework for connecting identifier catalogs to Wikidata. As a first step in curation, we created a Mix’N’Match catalog for harmonizing Cell Ontology (exemplified in Figure *Figure mix_n_match*) to Wikidata ([mix-n-match.toolforge.org/#/catalog/4719](#)), harnessing the community support for the task.

List of cells of the Cell Ontology

Next entry

Entry	116729110
Catalog ID	CL_0000094
Catalog description	

Enter Q number of matching item

Set Q New item N/A

Search

[Search Wikidata](#) | [Search en.wikipedia](#) | [Google-search Wikipedias](#) | [Google-search Wikisource](#) | [Google-search Wikidata](#)

Wikidata search results

Q223143 [↑] **granulocyte**
mature white blood cells with granules in the cytoplasm

Figure *mix_n_match*

Besides the decentralized community curation, about a year after curation, we decided to use a semi-automatic workflow to fill the missing gaps. The pipeline used ROBOT to extract terms and their cross-references (Tauber et al. 2019) and a custom Python script for the curation of the terms, derived, *wdcuration*, available at github.com/lubianat/wdcuration. The code used for integrating CL with Wikidata is accessible at github.com/lubianat/cl_match_to_wikidata. During the curation process, we noticed that approximately half of the terms in the Cell Ontology (~1300) were already present on Wikidata (either historically or via the curation described in the previous step), and the remaining 1300 were created semi-automatically, with individual human supervision and statement-level references to the Cell Ontology.

A byproduct of this task, the WDCuration package is available under an MIT license on GitHub (github.com/lubianat/wdcuration) and PyPI (pypi.org/project/wdcuration/). It introduces a series of functions that provide:

-
- The ability to input a term of interest and a JSON dictionary mapping strings to Wikidata IDs and then search the dictionary for an exact match.
 - If the term is not in the dictionary, initiate a lookup on Wikidata via ElasticSearch and return the best match for the term.
 - Await for the user selection to confirm if the match is accurate or input a new, manually-acquired match.
 - Update the JSON dictionary with a label-to-Wikidata mapping.

The tool also allows customization of the default Wikidata ElasticSearch algorithm by leveraging knowledge graph structure, for example including only “instances of → cell type” or excluding all “instance of → scientific article” triples.

Additionally, we created a userscript that opens tickets for new cell types on the Cell Ontology and the UBERON ontology leveraging the linked data from Wikidata. The script adds a button to the Wikidata interface to make the bridge between both systems and is available at wikidata.org/wiki/User:TiagoLubiana/cell-ontology.js .

7.4 Results

7.4.1 The volume of cell classes on Wikidata

When this project started, in August 2020, Wikidata had 264 items being categorized as a “cell type,” considerably less than in specialized cell catalogs, which counted over two thousand cell types at the time (DIEHL et al., 2016; STACHELSCHIED et al., 2014). After the intense curation activity performed in this PhD project, Wikidata now contains 6102 subclasses of “cell (Q7868)” as of 20 of April of 2023. From those, 550 cell classes are specific for humans, and 318 are specific for mice.

As a reference number, the second-largest multi-species cell collection, the Cell Ontology, currently hosts less than 3000 classes.

From the 6102 cell classes on Wikidata, 5981 (98.0%) have been edited somehow by User:TiagoLubiana, and 4686 (76.8%) have been created by User:TiagoLubiana

(Figure *edits_by_author*). Edits included adding multi language labels, connecting a dangling Wikipedia page to the cell subclass hierarchy, adding identifiers, images, markers, and other pieces of information. Approximately 430 hundred terms were added via manual curation based on PanglaoDB entries, and 1300 terms semi-automatically added from the Cell Ontology, while the remaining entries were created either via the curation workflow described in this chapter or by the Wikidata community.

Figure *edits_by_author*: Statistics on cell type information on Wikidata as of 31/05/2024. A) Number of cell type items divided by taxon (P703, found in taxon, relation). The top 5 is shown. B) Number of cell type items created by each Wikidata user. The top 10 are shown. C-D) Total number of modifications of cell type items by each user, either total number (C) or the number of different edited items (D). The top 10 are shown.

One benefit of the linked open data infrastructure of Wikidata is the possibility to record computer-readable references for each claim made. The "instance of cell type" claims were backed by over 350 different references. The distribution of cell types obtained per reference can be seen in *cell_type_refs*. The majority of the articles provided support for only one or few new classes on Wikidata, but some provided tens of new cell classes.

Figure cell_type_refs: Articles and databases most frequently used for curating cell types on Wikidata

These statistics are a demonstration of how the curation system used during this PhD project efficiently contributes to the status of cell type information on Wikidata. *Figure subclass_hierarchy* depicts the network for just one relation, “subclass of” (P279), providing a visual idea of the size of the cell class taxonomy on the platform. This connectedness underscores the value of the curation of Wikidata beyond a flat

list of terms. Of note, this is only one of the technical ways to represent knowledge in the Wikidata graph, a system that is detailed in the next section of the Chapter.

Figure {{subclass_hierarchy}}: Overview of the subclass structure for cells in the Wikidata knowledge graph. The labels for the ten nodes with the highest degree are shown.

7.4.2 The semantic infrastructure of Wikidata

While a comprehensive cell class hierarchy has value on its own, the expressivity permitted by the Wikidata infrastructure allows many more pieces of knowledge to be curated, organized, and queried. Figure *{{relation_schema}}* shows a schema for the most used properties in the platform and exemplifies the kinds of knowledge that can be formalized in the system. Each of those relations can be queried in Wikidata's SPARQL endpoint, enabling complex, multi-hop queries navigating the biological

landscape of Wikidata. A set of SPARQL queries showcasing different questions now askable in the Wikidata graph can be seen at lubianat.github.io/cell_type_query_book. Furthermore, these cell classes are linked to identifiers in a variety of external platforms, providing a cross-mapping and acquiring the role of a knowledge hub (see Table [{{top_identifiers}}](#)). As of June 8 2024, there are 84 different semantic relations used to describe cells on Wikidata ([/w.wiki/AKpL](https://w.wiki/AKpL)) and 150 different resources for external identifiers linked to them ([/w.wiki/AKpR](https://w.wiki/AKpR)).

* relations designed by User:TiagoLubiana

Figure [{{relation_schema}}](#): Top 10 relations used in Wikidata to represent cell classes as of May 12, 2023. The number of triples using each of the relations is shown under parenthesis.

Table *top_identifiers*: Top 10 links to identifiers community curated on cell classes on Wikidata. The identifier with larger coverage is the Cell Ontology ID, designed and curated in the course of this PhD project.

property	propertyLabel	counts
wd:P7963	Cell Ontology ID	2635
wd:P1402	Foundational Model of Anatomy ID	889
wd:P672	MeSH tree code	542
wd:P6366	Microsoft Academic ID	505
wd:P646	Freebase ID	387
wd:P10283	OpenAlex ID	277
wd:P486	MeSH descriptor ID	269
wd:P1417	Encyclopædia Britannica Online ID	201
wd:P3827	JSTOR topic ID	150
wd:P1694	Terminologia Histologica	149

Besides the main relations described in the Figure *relation_schema*, the Wikidata model allows curation of pieces of knowledge missing from the Cell Ontology. For example, cell types may include names, aliases and descriptions in over 200 languages, as can be seen in Figure *multilinguality_of_neuron* and Table *langs_for_cells*. These labels were in the vast majority curated by other contributors of Wikidata, highlighting the power of collaboration in the platform. Besides labels, the Wikidata community has curated other types of metadata on the cell types, including the *discoverers or inventors* (P61) and *time of discovery or invention* (P575) and *named after* (P138), making the graph structure also valuable as a digital humanities infrastructure for scholars studying the history of biology.

neuron (Q43054)

electrically excitable cell that communicates via synapses

 edit

nerve cell | nerve cells | neurons | neuronal cell | individual neuron

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	neuron	electrically excitable cell that communicates via synapses	nerve cell nerve cells neurons neuronal cell individual neuron
German	Nervenzelle	eukaryotische Zelle zur Erregungsleitung und Erregungsübertragung	Neurone Hirnzelle Neuron Gehirnzelle Neuronen
Spanish	neurona	célula del sistema nervioso	célula nerviosa terminación nerviosa célula cerebral neuron neuronal celula nerviosa terminacion nerviosa celula cerebral
French	neurone	cellule spécialisée sur l'influx nerveux et la transmission synaptique	Cellules neurales La cellule nerveuse Cellule nerveuse Neurones Cellules nerveuses Neuronal
Italian	neurone	cellula che compone il sistema nervoso	Cellula nervosa Soma Neurocito Neuroni
Brazilian Portuguese	neurônio	célula que processa e transmite informação	célula nervosa

Figure {{multilinguality_of_neuron}}

Table {{langs_for_cells}} The 5 most used languages for cell classes on Wikidata³³

languageLabel	count
English	6044
French	321
Arabic	318

³³ w.wiki/AKpB, 07/06/2024

Spanish	291
Portuguese	270

The flexibility of Wikidata allowed us to also curate several cell type markers. Extending the automated curation of markers from PanglaoDB described in Chapter 2, we manually curated markers alongside the particular excerpts mentioning them in the literature. As navigating the literature for marker information is one of the routine tasks of bioinformaticians, annotating single-cell RNA-seq data, having a platform with both the hard information (the marker genes) and the soft nuances (the selection and wording of human authors). A simple portal with the marker information is available on https://lubianat.github.io/wikidata_cell_curation/.

and/or

human biocurator

curate markers from the literature

	A	B	C	D
1	cell class	marker	stated in	stated as
44	human IgM B cell	IGHM	Q92826478	"IgM+ (IGHM) B cells"
45	human IgG3+ B cell	IGHG3	Q92826478	"IgG3+ (IGHG3) B cells"
46	mouse spinal cord astrocyte	LAMP1	Q106535191	"The most abundant marker expressed by spinal cord astrocytes was lysosomal-associated membrane protein 1 (LAMP1;"
47	mouse LAMP1+ TRAIL+ astrocytes	TRAIL	Q106535191	"mouse LAMP1+ TRAIL+ astrocytes"
48	human right atrium cardiomyocyte	HAMP	Q95602396	"HAMP, a master regulator of ironhomeostasis, was significantly enriched in over 50% of RA CM compared to 3% LA CM"

run Python script

```

reconcile_markers.py 3.M X
86: @ reconcile_markers.py 2...
114 | new claim = datatypes.Item(
115 |     prop_nr="P8872", value=gene_gid, references=references
116 | )
117 | entity.claims.add(
118 |     new_claim, action_if_exists=ActionIfExists.MERGE_REFS_OR_APPEND
119 | )
120 | entity.write(summary="Add curated marker ((marker)).")
121

```

add in batch to Wikidata

- 17:00, 14 May 2024 (diff | hist) .. (+1,186) .. human dNK3 (Q107446691) (Updated Item: Add curated marker (ITGAE)) (current)
- 16:59, 14 May 2024 (diff | hist) .. (+1,213) .. human dNK1 (Q107446689) (Updated Item: Add curated marker (B4GALNT1))
- 16:59, 14 May 2024 (diff | hist) .. (+1,213) .. human dNK1 (Q107446689) (Updated Item: Add curated marker (CYP26A1))
- 16:59, 14 May 2024 (diff | hist) .. (+1,231) .. human dNK1 (Q107446689) (Updated Item: Add curated marker (ENTPD1))
- 16:59, 14 May 2024 (diff | hist) .. (+1,244) .. mouse large peritoneal macrophage (Q107446685) (Updated Item: Add curated marker (Itgax))

navigate/monitor in the Wikidata interface

human cone photoreceptor

(Q107446918)

cell type in Homo sapiens

has marker (P8872)

by TiagoLubiana

ARR3 (Q17832015)

1 reference

quotation (P1683)

"Based on known markers [...], we were able to assign cell identities to [...] cone photoreceptors (ARR3, GNGT2, GUCA1C)" (English)

stated in (P248)

A single-cell transcriptome atlas of the adult human retina (Q92766837)

query and visualize

Curated Cell Markers with Quotations

Spotted anything weird? Just click on the cell type name and fix it!

Show 1 to 3 entries

Species	Cell	Gene
Homo sapiens	human retinal ganglion cell	NEFL
Homo sapiens	human retinal ganglion cell	GAP43
Homo sapiens	human retinal ganglion cell	SNCG

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries (filtered from 110 total entries)

Figure {{marker_curation}}

The curation of cell types was done manually for the most part of this work. While approaching the end of the PhD, Large Language Models started to become popular, including for applications in bioinformatics (see LUBIANA et al., 2023 for a longer discussion). In that direction, we made a ChatGPT plugin to aid curation of cell markers, available at chatgpt.com/g/g-7M0hY82Bs-cell-marker-biocurator and shown in Fig {{chatgpt_cellmarker_biocurator}}. The simple plugin takes as input the full text of an article and outputs a curation table with a label, a marker list and a quotation. With very few manual changes, the tables can be inserted into the Wikidata curation workflow, contributing knowledge to the platform.

We observed a great performance of the current ChatGPT 4o model in the detection of cell types, their markers and the relevant snippets. The capturing of quotations by the model is specially useful, as that allows the human biocurator to double check the results before adding to Wikidata. A similar system could be imagined for the curation of new cell types too, but the need for checks of parent classes and the risk of duplications makes it less feasible at the moment.

We argue that there is a great promise for combining curation assisted by Large Language Models and the Wikidata platform for hosting, disambiguating and connecting that information with the larger web. Importantly, by having a humanly editable interface, we can have an additional layer of checks, thereby mitigating the risk of model hallucinations lingering, a fear of researchers. Also, there is currently no policy on Wikidata for the direct adding of LLM-generated curation, so a human layer of review before the information is recorded is required to comply with

Cell Marker Biocurator

Por community builder

Detailed biocurator for comprehensive cell class detection and associated markers with species-specific and neutral terms from full text articles.

community standards.

cell type	marker genes	quotation
human atrial cardiomyocyte (CMs-A)	MYH6, MYL7, ULK4	"We found that CMs-A specifically expressed MYH6, MYL7, and ULK4..."
human ventricular cardiomyocyte (CMs-V)	MYH7, S100A4, LBH	"...while MYH7, S100A4, and LBH were specifically expressed in CMs-V."
human epicardial cells (EPs)	UPK3B, WT1	"Cluster C6 (n = 46) was composed of epicardial cells (EPs) because they highly expressed UPK3B and WT1."
human proepicardial cells (proEPs)	UPK3B, ALDH1A2, WT1, TBX18, HEY1, HEY2	"Cells in subcluster C2 (n = 85) specifically expressed UPK3B, ALDH1A2, WT1, and TBX18... proEPs specifically expressed the genes HEY1 and HEY2..."
human valvar interstitial cells (VICs)	SOX9	"These valvar cells highly expressed SOX9, an important transcription factor for valve formation and development."
human endothelial cells (ECs)	PECAM1, CDH5, KDR	"Another main cell type in the heart was the ECs (cluster C4, n = 445), with specific expression of PECAM1 (also called CD31), CDH5 (also called VE-cadherin), and KDR (also known as VEGFR2 or FLK1)."
human cardiac fibroblasts	COL1A1, COL1A2, COL3A1, POSTN, DCN, PDGFRA, SOX9	"Cells in cluster C3 (n = 786) highly expressed extracellular matrix (ECM) genes, such as COL1A1, COL1A2, COL3A1, POSTN, and DCN... also highly expressed PDGFRA and SOX9."

Fig {{chatgpt_cellmarker_biocurator}}

7.4.3 Wikidata and the Cell Ontology interplay

Besides cataloging cell types and information about them on Wikidata, we considered ways the information could be more effectively inserted into the technical infrastructure of the Human Cell Atlas. We focused on ways to integrate Wikidata

with the Cell Ontology, the *de facto* provider of cell type identifiers for biomedical resources. We proposed and created the property "Cell Ontology ID" (P7963) in March 2020. By December 2022, over 700 Cell Ontology IDs had been manually cross-referenced with Wikidata (by User:TiagoLubiana and others), via both the graphic user interface and the Mix'n'Match platform. The scope of the curation effort was subsequently expanded to include manual curation of the extra Wikidata-Cell Ontology links, including creating new classes for the absent Cell Ontology terms. As of May 12th, 2023, Wikidata boasted 2636 cross-references to the Cell Ontology, virtually covering all terms in the ontology.

One immediate result of the curation effort was a list of cell types featured on Wikipedia, indicating their general notability, but missing from the Cell Ontology. The SPARQL query below presents an example of such results, exploring the graph structure to extract neurons that lack a CL identifier, but are included in English Wikipedia. The result of the query (see Code Snippet `{{neuron_types}}`) as of May 12, 2023, is presented in *Table `{{neuron_types}}`*, an a live version of the query can be executed in the Wikidata Query Service. (<https://w.wiki/6hJT>)

```
SELECT ?item ?label ?sitelink
WHERE
{
  # Cell classes that do not have a link to the Cell Ontology
  ?item wdt:P279* wd:Q43054 . s
  # Excluding sensory receptors, as some classify as cells
  # and others classify as anatomical structures.
  FILTER NOT EXISTS {?item wdt:P279* wd:Q729463 .}
  MINUS {?item wdt:P7963 [] . }

  ?sitelink schema:isPartOf <https://en.wikipedia.org/>;
    schema:about ?item .

  ?item rdfs:label ?label
  FILTER (lang(?label) = 'en')
}
LIMIT 10
```

Code Snippet {{neuron_types}}: 10 neuron types present on Wikipedia and Wikidata but not on the Cell Ontology

Table {{neuron_types}}: 10 neuron types present on Wikipedia and Wikidata but not on the Cell Ontology

Item	Label	English Wikipedia Page
Q309082	Mirror Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mirror_neuron
Q863495	Grid Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grid_cell
Q934475	Photosensitive Ganglion Cell	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intrinsically_photosensitive_retinal_ganglion_cell
Q1476783	Wide Dynamic Range Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wide_dynamic_range_neuron
Q1756451	Renshaw Cell	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Renshaw_cell
Q2384084	Spindle Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Von_Economo_neuron
Q4944635	Boundary Vector Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boundary_cell
Q4944637	Drosophila Border Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Border_cells_(Drosophila)
Q5064084	Cerebellar Granule Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cerebellar_granule_cell
Q5152118	Command Neuron	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Command_neuron

Besides a source for new terms, Wikidata’s community presents a platform to validate and gather decentralized feedback on the platform with respect to new axioms and new classes, as well as on the consistency of existing classes. For example, in Figure *{{wikidata_cl_mismatch}}* we display one case in which the existence of multiple Wikidata-to-CL mappings allowed us to discover an inconsistency in CL in relation to the common classification of cell types on Wikipedia, which separate “multinucleate cell” into two different entities, “coenocytic cell” and “syncytial cell”. The discovery led to a ticket on the Cell Ontology issue tracker, to be worked on in the future.

A multinucleate cell (Q5796041)...

cell type
multinucleated cell | polynuclear cell

Identifiers

Cell Ontology ID (P7963) by TiagoLubiana CL_0000228 ⓘ

Microsoft Academic I by Nikola Tulechki

Online PWN Encyclo

Potential issues

distinct-values constraint [Help](#) [Discuss](#)

This property's value should not be present on any other item, but is also present on [syncytium](#).

This result is cached and might be out of date by up to 15 minutes.

B

OLS / Cell Ontology CL / CL:0000228 Copy

multinucleate cell

http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000228 Copy

A cell with more than one nucleus. [<http://flybase.org/reports/ma.html>]

Term information

database cross reference

- WBbt:0008074
- AEO:0000203

definition

- A cell with more than one nucleus.

has exact synonym

- syncytium
- syncylium
- syncyial cell

C

Multinucleate

Página [Discussão](#)

De Wikipedia

Wikidata: [multinucleate cell \(Q5796041\)](#), cell type

Aliases: [multinucleated cell](#), [polynuclear cell](#)

Multinucleate cells, depending on the mechanism by which they are formed, can be divided into^{[3][4]} "syncytia" (formed by cell fusion) or "coenocytes" (formed by nuclear division not being followed by cytokinesis).

D

obophenotype / cell-ontology Public

Code Issues 164 Pull requests 9 Actions Projects 9 Releases 49

"syncytium" and "multinucleate cell" are treated as synonyms but correspond to different concepts #1967

Open 0 comments

lubianat commented 4 minutes ago • edited

In Wikidata, two concepts are mapped to CL_0000228, "syncytium" and "multinucleate cell".

Figure {{wikidata_cl_mismatch}}: Wikidata's community curation helps Cell Ontology to improve. A) The entry for "multinucleate cell" showing a constraint violation, as the CL identifiers is also used in "syncytium". B) The CL entry for "multinucleate cell", showing "syncytium" as a synonym. C) The Wikipedia page, describing two types of multinucleate cells: syncytium and coenocytes. D) An open ticket in the Cell Ontology GitHub Issue Tracker to start the discussion towards normalizing the structure.

7.5 Discussion

In this chapter we presented the process of developing Wikidata as a robust database for cell type information. We detailed the process of setting up a semantic infrastructure on the platform alongside computational methods for the curation.

These protocols were leveraged to establish Wikidata as an important repository of cell type information, the largest multi-species structure available for cells up to the time.

It is important to note that content on Wikidata is constantly evolving and changed by the community. While it is possible that the state and structure of cell types on Wikidata will be changed in the future, we consider this a positive side, as the knowledge infrastructure needs to be flexible enough to adapt to the rapid pace of change in our knowledge about cells.

Also relevant is the fact that Wikidata is not restricted to cell types, containing over 100.000.000 other entities and capturing encyclopedic knowledge. The breadth of Wikidata's content and the size of the community makes it the largest encyclopedic knowledge graph. Due to its centrality in the web of data, Wikidata has a perspective of stable funding coming both from the Wikimedia Foundation Fund and the donations received. The way the platform is run guarantees the stability of the data, preventing the common threat of lack of support in the long run feared by other biocurated resources.

Even if Wikidata presents on itself a nice framework for community-encoding of knowledge into structured format, it would be naive to assume the Human Cell Atlas community would start using the platform in the short term. Even though libraries and museums are increasingly using Wikidata as a source of identifiers ([Tharani 2021](#)), the life sciences community is still in the infancy of dealing with structure knowledge. Wikidata lacks the authoritativeness of a domain-specific governing body, such as the OBO Foundry, the Human Genome Nomenclature Consortium (HGNC), the International Catalog of Diseases (ICD), MeSH, and other label-and-identifier-providers for the life sciences. Thus, while Wikidata plays a role in the knowledge representation ecosystem (with applications outside its own platform, e.g. as a mint for identifiers to use in nanopublications ([Mietchen et al. 2022](#), [Bucur et al. 2023](#))), we believe the more immediate contribution of Wikidata to

the Human Cell Atlas will come indirectly, by improving the curation workflow in ontologies .

In our experience, bioscientists are wary of using resources like Wikipedia and Wikidata in professional settings, but the Cell Ontology and other OBO Foundry ontologies have a much better reach, and are used widely for knowledge management in the context of the Human Cell Atlas project. ([Osumi-Sutherland et al. 2021](#)) This realization led to a decision on not promoting Wikidata use directly by the Human Cell Atlas community, but instead investing time in connecting Wikidata to OBO Foundry ontologies. During the course of the work, we identified five core benefits of integrating Wikidata to the ontology ecosystem, outlined below.

First, Wikidata is multilingual and can provide identifiers in hundreds of languages. This is in stark contrast with the anglocentric world of ontologies and controlled vocabularies. Second, Wikidata has tight links to Wikipedia. Ontology consumers (such as CELLXGENE ([Megill et al. 2021](#))) often find themselves in need of comprehensive textual descriptions of the concepts. Thus, Wikidata mappings can provide Wikipedia connections, increasing the possibilities for developers using the ontology.

Third, Wikidata has links to many resources and controlled vocabularies beyond Wikipedia. Even though most biocurated resources provide some degree of mapping (cross-references) to other resources, Wikidata plays the role of an identifier hub to connect ontologies with MeSH terms, the UMLS vocabulary, entries on libraries and encyclopedias and more. These extended links can help ontologies to grow and refine themselves by cross-validating information with other curating teams.

Fourth, Wikidata's community presents a platform to validate and gather decentralized feedback on the platform with respect to new axioms and new classes, as well as on the consistency of existing classes as discussed in Figure [{{wikidata_cl_mismatch}}](#).

Finally, Wikidata provides an easy-to-enter platform for newcomers without extensive ontology training. It provides tutorials, manuals and tooling targeting lay users and if properly integrated to the ontology workflow, Wikidata can serve as a first-pass platform for new terms and new axiom suggestions. While contributing to ontologies requires the download and configuration of the Protege platform (protege.stanford.edu/), as well as familiarity with GitHub workflows, contributing to Wikidata has a much lower barrier. Wikidata, thus, serves as a gateway for ontology development and can play a key role in the knowledge management ecosystem.

In that way, we hope to have demonstrated the value of Wikidata for organizing the knowledge of cell types. We invite readers to browse the information on the platform, searching for cells of interest and looking at the modeling details, starting for example with *neuron*, at wikidata.org/wiki/Q43054.

7.6 Additional information

To end the chapter, we considered it relevant to provide an example of the curation process of new cell classes on Wikidata and the Cell Ontology. It is a relatively long and detailed section in comparison with the rest of the work. We thought that, nevertheless, it was important to show the insider perspective on the catalog of cells, so as to give the reader a better grasp on the challenges associated with the curation of cell types from the literature and the intricacies of biomedical texts that make the process less than trivial.

In June 2024 we encountered a work about lamellar cells named "*Lamellar cells in Pacinian and Meissner corpuscles are touch sensors*." (NIKOLAEV et al., 2020) This work was found when trying to sort conceptual mess on Wikidata, as the Pacinian corpuscle and similar mechanoreceptors were classified as cell types *and* nerve endings at the same time, but neither seemed really fit to the complex structure of these corpuscles. An example of this mess is found in the Medical Subject Headings controlled vocabulary (which does not have the strictness of a formal ontology),

where the term *mechanoreceptor*³⁴ is cataloged both as a cell and as a parent term of *Pacinian Corpuscles*,³⁵ a multicellular structure. As MeSH has been connected to Wikidata in the past, this is possibly one of the sources of the confusion too.

The lamellar cells have been seen at least since the first half of the XIX century Fig {{pacini_kolliker}}, haven't been cataloged yet, neither on the Cell Ontology nor on Wikidata. It also was missed by the catalog of Vickaryous and Hall from 2006 (VICKARYOUS; HALL, 2006). This literature gap is acknowledged by Nikolaev and colleagues, that state "despite their widespread presence in vertebrates, no functional studies of lamellar cells from Meissner- or Pacinian-like corpuscles from any species exist, and their physiological roles remain unknown."

Fig {{pacini_kolliker}} Drawing of *Pacinischen Körperchen* in Jacob Henle & Albert Kölliker *Ueber die Pacinischen Körperchen an den Nerven des Menschen und der Säugethiere*³⁶ showing what we now call lamellar cells, even though they were not recognized as cells at the moment. (<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/rm5wwg2e/items?canvas=43>)

³⁴ <http://id.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/D008465>

³⁵ <https://id.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/D010141>

³⁶ Text and image in Public Domain.

The combination of clear identification for the class and the apparent lack of previous systematization makes this example prone to a qualitative test of three tenets of the PhD thesis: the applicability of the philosophical categories presented (arche-class, *sensu stricto* cell class, infra-class and technoclass), the applicability of the system for curation of cell types and, finally, of the infrastructure of porting such cell types to Cell Ontology. This section, then, will demonstrate the process of curating cell types on Wikidata in connection with the Cell Ontology by using the lamellar cells as an example.

7.4.4.1 Anatomical entities in Nikolaev et al. 2020

To start the catalog, I will manually extract the mentions of anatomical structures by Nikolaev et al. , starting from the Introduction:

"The human palm contains a dense population of mechanosensory end-organs, including Pacinian, Meissner, and Ruffini corpuscles, along with Merkel cell-neurite complexes. The same or analogous structures are present in the skin of most vertebrates."

Here we have a mention of some anatomical structures presented in a species-neutral fashion, but localized to the human palm. The terms are commonly used for several species and have been cataloged on UBERON (Fig `{{uberon_mechanoreceptor}}`). They mention the *same or analogous structures* in different organisms, further reinforcing the multispecies nature of the idea. It continues on the analogy to mention "the star organ of the star-nosed mole and the bill of tactile-foraging waterfowl"

Fig {{uberon_mechanoreceptor}}. The UBERON entry for mechanoreceptors (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0012449), with several of the mentioned classes.

UBERON has the species-neutral term *beak*,³⁷ but misses the more specific ***tactile-foraging waterfowl beak***³⁸, as not all beaks are **mechanosensory organs**. The group of *tactile-foraging waterfowl* does not correspond to a systematized biological taxon, adding an extra challenge to a precise classification. UBERON does catalog the *star organ of the star-nosed mole* under the name *nasal tentacle*.³⁹ The authors continue to describe the corpuscles in the continuation of the article:

"In Pacinian corpuscles, the mechanoreceptor is surrounded by onion-like sheaths formed by **lamellar cells**, whereas it is sandwiched between two or more lamellar cells in Meissner corpuscles."

³⁷ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0005094

³⁸ In bold, the terms that will be added to Wikidata as part of this work.

³⁹ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0013206

In this passage, Nikolaev et al. confirm that their idea of a *lamellar cell* is valid for both Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles, thus supporting the curation of a general term for *lamellar cell* that may be used for both structures. The continuation of the text is surprising, as the authors make clear that their experiments are done in an unlikely organism, using "a glabrous skin preparation from the bill of Pekin duck, a tactile-specialist bird."

The concept of a **glabrous skin** in that context refers, likely, to the avian skin without feathers. It has no conceptual match in UBERON and the match in FMA⁴⁰ is restricted to humans. We also have the concept of the **Pekin duck bill** (and *Pekin duck bill skin*), an infraclass (i.e. a class valid at sub-specific level, as described in chapter {{technoclasses}}), as the Pekin duck is a particular breed of the domestic duck, *Anas platyrhynchos domesticus*.⁴¹ This is relevant, as all observations done in this particular collection of experiments refer not to a species, but to a breed, a fact that will extend to the cell types.

The text continues to reveal details that are necessary for appropriate categorization of the cell concepts, stating that "duck bill skin contains a dense population of Pacinian- and Meissner-like corpuscles, referred to as Herbst and Grandry corpuscles, respectively". This sentence now presents the term *duck bill skin*, a good example of how a term might be used polysemically as an archeclass, ducks, a species-specific class, to *Anas platyrhynchos*, or even an infraclass, to Pekin duck. It also mentions the *Herbst corpuscles*,⁴² present in UBERON, and the *Grandry corpuscles*, mentioned in UBERON, but present on Wikidata.⁴³ It also brings up two anatomical classes: the **Pacinian-like corpuscle** and the **Meissner-like corpuscle**, somehow extending the concept. The authors continue with detailing information about their experiments.

⁴⁰ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FMA_67815

⁴¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=American_Pekin&oldid=1226219782

⁴² http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0012448

⁴³ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q7674135>

"Pacinian and Meissner corpuscles, which could be distinguished by their unique morphology and size (Fig. 1, B, and C). Duck Pacinian corpuscles had an oval structure, ~35 to 120 μ m in size (n = 140 corpuscles), [...] Duck Meissner corpuscles were more spherical and smaller in size (~15 to 35 μ m in diameter, n = 50 corpuscles) than Pacinian corpuscles (Fig. 1, G to I) (14, 18)."

From this point on, the authors seem to have decided to simply use the names Pacinian corpuscle and Meissner corpuscle instead of the names "Herbst" and "Grandry". They also refer to *duck Pacinian corpuscle* and *duck Meissner corpuscle*, where they can only refer to the Pekin duck they are studying. This is an example discussed in thesis `{{technoclass}}`: while observations are at a subspecific level, scientific texts also jump to report results at a species or even at a multispecies level, using what is called epistemically as a process of induction. The choice of using *Pacinian* and *Meissner* instead of the names usually used for the structures in *Aves* may be related with trying to imply similarity with humans, arguing that "the presence of Pacinian and Meissner corpuscles in duck bill skin suggests that it as a good model system for the human palm." Readers are led to believe findings are valid for a much larger population than the data supports directly, a process not considered scientific by Popperian standards. (RAERINNE, 2024)

Of note, this is not only a matter of lexical precision or pedantry but is necessary when making decisions on how to catalog information. For example, Wikidata has properties for asserting the *diameter*⁴⁴ and the *length*⁴⁵ of structures⁴⁶. Are the measurements presented by the authors valid for *Meissner corpuscles*, *Meissner-like*

⁴⁴ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/P2386>

⁴⁵ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/P2043>

⁴⁶ The authors also measure the whole-cell membrane capacitance (9.6 ± 1.4 and 24.6 ± 4.6 pF, respectively), the resting membrane potential (-51.9 ± 2.0 mV and -73.5 ± 2.4 mV) and the apparent input resistance (5.8 ± 1.8 G Ω , and 1.5 ± 0.4 G Ω). All these features could also, in theory, be added to Wikidata, but that would require approval of new properties by the community (see the chapter about PanglaoDB for details on the process).

corpuses, for *duck Meissner corpuses* or for the ***Pekin duck Meissner-like corpuscle***?

By now, we have a general infraclass for lamellar cells, the ***lamellar cells of the Pekin duck bill*** and their structure-specific counterparts, the *lamellar cell of the Pekin duck bill Meissner-like corpuscle*, and the *lamellar cell of the Pekin duck bill Pacinian-like corpuscle*. These classes start to be very specific, approaching the concept of a technoclass (the most specific class probed on an experiment). But if we want to record accurately the data for cell length, we need to be precise on what we are referring to.

It is disappointing that a study with a species-neutral flashy title ("*Lamellar cells in Pacinian and Meissner corpuses are touch sensors*") that starts with a mention of the human palm ("*The skin covering the human palm[...]*") only studies Pekin ducks. It is important to see that earlier in 2020, a different group of researchers presented similar work in the *Science* journal, more prestigious in academic rankings than *Science Advances*. (NEUBARTH et al., 2020) Neubarth et al. used also a species-neutral flashy title, "*Meissner corpuses and their spatially intermingled afferents underlie gentle touch perception*", but also studied only one species, namely mice. This type of logical jump is a common practice in life sciences reporting, and a challenge for a critical evaluation of works in the context of biocuration.

7.4.4.2 Complementing our understanding with Neubarth et al 2020 and Suazo et al 2022.

To complement our understanding of lamellar cells before proceeding with curation in Wikidata and the Cell Ontology, we decided to consult two more articles: the work on mice by Neubarth et al., 2020, and a review on lamellar cells done by Suazo and colleagues in 2022.

Neubarth et al. help us to classify the lamellar cells by stating that "Meissner corpuscle lamellar cells [...] are specialized terminal Schwann cells." This statement

would apparently put the ***Meissner corpuscle lamellar cell*** directly under *terminal Schwann cell*⁴⁷ in the Cell Ontology, Wikidata, and other taxonomies. A terminal Schwann cell is defined on CL as "a neuroglial cell of the peripheral nervous system inside the basal lamina of the neuromuscular junction" and Meissner corpuscles are *not* in the neuromuscular junction, denoting the ambiguity in the literature and the need to sort out the confusion.

The review by Suazo et al. starts with a similar classification of lamellar cells as *terminal glia cell* and using the -like suffix, calling them *non-myelinating Schwann-like cells*. The Cell Ontology has a term for *non-myelinating Schwann cell*⁴⁸ which might be a fitting superclass in the ontology. It is unclear, however, if the authors consider the lamellar cells as *true* Schwann cells or merely *Schwann-like*, whatever that means.

Suazo et al. continue to describe the context of the lamellar cells, introducing a name for the different mechanosensory corpuscles present in the skin:

"Sensory corpuscles, or cutaneous end-organ complexes, are complex structures [...] they consist, in addition to the axons, of non-myelinating Schwann-like cells (terminal glial cells) and endoneurial and perineurial-related cells. The terminal glial cells are the so-called lamellar cells in Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles. "

In this snippet, Suazo and colleagues introduced the terms ***cutaneous end-organ complexes*** (CEOCs) and ***sensory corpuscles***, neither part of UBERON ontology. As can be seen in Fig {{uberon_mechanoreceptor}}, UBERON puts the Pacinian corpuscles as subclasses of *sensory receptor*, itself a subclass of *nerve ending*⁴⁹. On UBERON, mechanoreceptors are *nerve endings*, but in the Cell Ontology the

⁴⁷ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000692

⁴⁸ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0002376

⁴⁹ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0012453

term *mechanoreceptor*⁵⁰ is also a subclass of *sensory neuron*.⁵¹ In the Foundational Model of Anatomy, there is a term for the *nerve ending within the Pacinian corpuscle*, so some ontologists conceptualize the nerve ending as a part of the Pacinian corpuscle.⁵² The polysemy and ambiguity of words in the academic literature make the process not merely a collection, but also a re-conceptualization and decision-making process.

Suazo et al. add more information for our task, providing support for putting Meissner, Ruffini and Pacinian corpuscles as types of CEOCs, a conceptualization described in {{suazo_figure_1}}:

"the sets of axon and glial Schwann-like cells (terminal glial cells) form the core of CEOCs, i.e., Meissner corpuscles, Ruffini's corpuscles, and Pacinian corpuscles [...]"

In the figure, the authors also mention the *human digital Meissner corpuscle*, which might have its particular characteristics.

⁵⁰ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000199

⁵¹ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000101

⁵² <http://purl.org/sig/ont/fma/fma83996>

Figure {{suazo_figure_1}} The first figure by Suazo and colleagues, shows a schematic representation of sensory corpuscles.⁵³

The text proceeds to describe the *terminal glial cells* in Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles. The excerpt regarding Meissner corpuscles is of especial ontological relevance:

"Meissner corpuscles (Figure 1A) are exclusive in humans and primates, although similar structures, i.e., Meissner-like corpuscles, are also present in other mammals [...]. They are typical of the glabrous skin but concentrate in areas of fine touch discriminative capacities (fingertips, palm, sole of the feet, lips, and male and female genital skin) and occasionally on the tongue and palate [...]."

This excerpt provides a better reference for the broader term *Meissner-like corpuscle* and directly contradicts the use of "Meissner corpuscle" by Nikolaev et al. for the structures found in Pekin ducks.

In the continuation of the review, Suazo and colleagues provide us with further morphological descriptions and hints as to how to classify such cells mentioning that, for the Meissner corpuscle, "the axon is coated by Schwann-related cell-denominated laminar cells" and that for the Pacinian corpuscle "the inner core consists of hemilamellae of non-myelinating terminal glial cells." Throughout the text, it is common to see hesitancy to ontological commitments, using the *-like* and *-related* suffixes.

⁵³ Figure available under the CC-BY license.

In the continuation, is made clear how lamellar cells may be considered a specialized type of Schwann cell in the current understanding of cellular classification:

"The progenitors of the peripheral glial cells originate mainly from *neural crest cells*⁵⁴ (NCCs) or from *cap boundary cells* (BCs). These cells contact and attach to the surface of developing axons and differentiate into *Schwann cell precursors*⁵⁵ (S) and then into *immature Schwann cells*⁵⁶ (ISCs) [...] The ISCs give rise to a pleiad of *peripheral glia*⁵⁷ including *myelinating*⁵⁸ and *non-myelinating Schwann cells*⁵⁹, the *satellite glial cells*⁶⁰ of the peripheral sensory and vegetative ganglia, the *enteric glia*⁶¹, the *terminal glial cells of the neuromuscular junctions and CEOCs* (also denominated end-organ glia)."

A detailed ontological review of the development of glia is out of the scope of this text, but it is interesting to note that the author collects the ***terminal glial cells of the neuromuscular junctions and CEOCs*** as derivatives of *immature Schwann cells*. It seems reasonable thus, to classify lamellar cells under *Schwann cell*. In Figure {{suazo_figure_2}}, we can see that the authors actually have two different types of

⁵⁴ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0011012

⁵⁵ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0002375

⁵⁶ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0002377

⁵⁷ Not present in CL, only cataloged for *Drosophila* in FBBT http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FBbt_00001320

⁵⁸ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000218

⁵⁹ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0002376

⁶⁰ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000516, *satellite glial cell* currently not present as a synonym and not classified under "glial cell".

⁶¹ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_4040002

terminal glial cell (TGC), the TGCs in sensory corpuscles and the TGCs in the neuromuscular junctions.

FIGURE 2 | Schematic representation of development and differentiation of peripheral glial cells subtypes. BC, boundary cells; BDNF, brain-derived neurotrophic factor; DRG, dorsal root ganglia (dr, dorsal root; vr, ventral root); erbBs, neuregulin receptors; NCCs, neural crest cells; NRGs, neuregulins; NT, neural tube; SCs, Schwann cells; SGCs, satellite glial cells; TGCs, terminal glial cells; TGCs, terminal glial cells. Imitated from Kastriiti and Adameyko (2017).

Figure {{suazo_figure_2}}. The Figure 2 of the review by Suazo et al. shows graphically their conceptualization of the types of peripheral glia.

The review continues to the end with details of the molecular characteristics of lamellar cells, as well as models of which kinds of roles they play in mechanosensation in the corpuscles. For the classification task, one last excerpt is of value, commenting on the work on Pekin ducks by Nikolaev et al. :

"The most overwhelming putative role of lamellar cells in mechanosensation was provided recently by Nikolaev et al. (2020). They observed that the lamellar cells of Grandry's corpuscles (assimilated to the lamellar cells within Meissner

corpuscles) from duck bill skin detect tactile stimuli, thus, suggesting that also lamellar cells are touch sensor. [...] Furthermore, they also showed that outer-core lamellar cells from Herbst corpuscles (equivalent to the mammalian Pacinian corpuscles) are mechanosensitive. [...] It may be worth to note that even the structures are not identical; there is striking similarity between microanatomy, function, and electrophysiology of the avian Grandry's and Herbst corpuscles vs. Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles, respectively."

7.4.4.1 Adding concepts to Wikidata

After analysing the publications, it is possible to start formalizing the concepts into the knowledge graph of Wikidata and of the ontologies Cell Ontology and UBERON. Tables `{{anatomy_concepts}}` and `{{cell_concepts}}` capture the concepts, their main source and whether we considered them to be fit for UBERON/CL or not.

Table `{{anatomy_concepts}}`. Subclasses of *anatomical entity* related to mechanosensory corpuscles that will be added to Wikidata

Term	Parent term(s)	4-way class	Synonyms	Source	Fit for CL or UBERON
<i>tactile-foraging waterfowl beak</i>	beak	archeclass	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	Likely not
mechanosensory organ	sense organ	archeclass	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	Yes
glabrous skin	skin	archeclass	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	Yes
Pekin duck bill	<i>tactile-foraging waterfowl beak</i>	infraclass	Pekin duck beak	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
<i>duck bill skin</i>	glabrous skin	<i>sensu stricto class</i>	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> bill	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No

			skin		
Pekin duck bill skin	duck bill skin	infraclass	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
sensory corpuscle	mechanoreceptor	archeclass	cutaneous end-organ complex, COEC, COECs	Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Pacinian-like corpuscle⁶²	sensory corpuscle	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Maybe
Meissner-like corpuscle⁶³	sensory corpuscle	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Maybe
digital Meissner's corpuscle	Meissner's corpuscle	archeclass	-		Maybe

Table {{cell_concepts}}. Subclasses of *cell* related to lamellar cells of mechanosensory corpuscles that will be added to Wikidata

Term	Parent term(s)	4-way class	Synonyms	Source	Fit for UBERON/CL
terminal glia cell⁶⁴	Schwann cell	archeclass	TGC, end-organ-glia	Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
lamellar cell	terminal glia cell	archeclass	sensory corpuscle lamellar cell, sensory corpuscle TGC, terminal glia cell of sensory corpuscle	Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Meissner-like corpuscle lamellar cell	lamellar cell	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Maybe

⁶² Pacinian corpuscle and Herbst corpuscles should be sorted under this term.

⁶³ Meissner's corpuscles and Grandry's corpuscles should be sorted under this term.

⁶⁴ A distinct, umbrella term will need to be created splitting the TGC from the neuromuscular junction to the TGCs from sensory corpuscles.

Pacinian-like corpuscle lamellar cell	lamellar cell	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Maybe
Meissner's corpuscle lamellar cell	Meissner-like corpuscle lamellar cell	archeclass	-	Neubarth et al. 2020, Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Pacinian corpuscle lamellar cell	Pacinian-like corpuscle lamellar cell	archeclass	-	Neubarth et al. 2020, Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Meissner's corpuscle sensory neuron	sensory neuron	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Pacinian corpuscle sensory neuron	sensory neuron	archeclass	-	Suazo et al. 2022	Yes
Pekin duck glabrous skin bill sensory corpuscle lamellar cell	lamellar cell	infraclass (approaching technoclass)	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
Pekin duck sensory corpuscle lamellar cell	lamellar cell	infraclass	-	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
Pekin duck Meissner-like corpuscle lamellar cell	Meissner-like corpuscle lamellar cell	infraclass	Pekin duck Grandry's corpuscle lamellar cel	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
Pekin duck Pacinian-like corpuscle lamellar cell	lamellar cell	infraclass	Pekin duck Herbst's corpuscle lamellar cell	Nikolaev et al. 2020	No
human Meissner's corpuscle lamellar cell	Meissner's corpuscle lamellar cell	sensu stricto class	-	Suazo et al. 2022	No
human Pacinian corpuscle lamellar cell	Pacinian corpuscle lamellar cell	sensu stricto class	-	Suazo et al. 2022	No

Figure `{{lamellar_sparql}}` . Top: the hierarchy of cell types extracted from Suazo et al. 2022 on Wikidata (query available at <https://w.wiki/AHYy>, 04/06/2024). Bottom: the types of sensory corpuscle, based on the works of Nikolaev et al., 2020, and Suazo et al., 2022 (query available at <https://w.wiki/AHZV>, 04/06/2024).

To operationalize the parsing into Wikidata of those classes, we created a dedicated MIRACL-like spreadsheet and uploaded the content to Wikidata using our curation pipeline.⁶⁵ Additionally, we connected manually the anatomical concepts on Wikidata to the classes created. After the biocuration process, it became possible to parse the content on Wikidata using SPARQL queries. For example, in Figure `{{lamellar_sparql}}` we show the hierarchy of lamellar cells and other concepts derived from Suazo et al. (top) and the hierarchy of sensory corpuscles currently on Wikidata (bottom).

7.4.4.2 Moving from Wikidata to the Cell Ontology and UBERON

The process of adding and updating the content on Wikidata was very fast, taking 2 days from inception to adding the classes to the platform. The actual reconciliation time, after the spreadsheets were prepared, took less than one hour. This is due to the lack of back-and-forth and double checks by community members and the simple infrastructure for committing the new classes, without pull requests and reviews.

Entities on Wikidata also lack a strong logical commitment and don't rely on importing axioms from other providers. For example, the work done in the previous session would require modifications to two different ontologies, UBERON and Cell Ontology, and knowledge of two different technical and social infrastructures.

The same processes that make Wikidata fast, however, make the academic community wary of using it directly, and researchers often rely on controlled vocabularies with a higher degree of gatekeeping. That is why, in the context of this PhD project, we consider that the more immediate value of Wikidata curation comes from the possibility of integrating it into the OBO Foundry ontologies in a relatively seamless way.

⁶⁵ github.com/lubianat/wikidata_cell_curation/tree/73ce378dd67bb54471f88a246f837084f7ee5459

Add a title

[NTR] New Term Request: sensory corpuscle

Add a description

Write Preview

Preferred term label:
sensory corpuscle

Synonyms
COEC, COECs, cutaneous end-organ complex

Definition (free text, please give PubMed ID)
[PMID:35356056](#)

Parent term (use ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/uberon)
mechanoreceptor structure
UBERON ID: [UBERON:0012449](#)

Anatomical structure where the term is found
UBERON ID: N/A

Your nano-attribution (ORCID)
orcid.org/0000-0003-2473-2313

Link back to Wikidata item
wikidata.org/wiki/Q126363978

+ Add tasklist Submit new issue

Remember, contributions to this repository should follow its [contributing guidelines](#) and [code of conduct](#).

Figure {{wikidata_based_ntr}} A new term request for sensory corpuscle in the UBERON ontology pulling structured information from Wikidata. The draft request for a new term was generated using <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/User:TiagoLubiana/cell-ontology.js>

After adding the terms to the issue trackers of both ontologies, it is possible to make pull requests and try to add them to the ontology source file. For the UBERON ontology, we needed to wait until someone in the community replies to the issue and gives us permission to proceed. This process took about 2 days, as the proponent (T.L.) is a trusted member of the Cell Ontology community.

In Cell Ontology, we already have the credentials to propose changes to the ontology. However, adding the new cell concepts requires some extra technical work, as one needs to import concepts (e.g. "Pacinian corpuscle") from the UBERON ontology, a process that is not trivial. The OBO foundry ontologies does not import in full the other ontologies, as the ontology engineering pipelines include resource intensive-tasks, such as running the ELK reasoner (KAZAKOV; KRÖTZSCH; SIMANČÍK, [s.d.]) which would be unsustainable for the size of the combined ontologies. Even for individual imports, the links are non is highlighted by the conditional clause in the documentation: "If you have the technical skills and/or the

required computer resources (refreshing imports can be a memory-intensive task), you may refresh the imports yourself before submitting the pull request, by following the appropriate procedure."⁶⁶

This need for dedicated time to understand the different social and technical processes of the CL and UBERON ontologies is similar to other ontologies in the OBO Foundry. As such, the ontologies rarely have direct contributions from researchers or non-tech-savvy volunteers, usually relying on professional staff. Cell Ontology and UBERON are not hosted by any particular institution, even though they are core ontologies used by large projects like HubMap, the Human Cell Atlas, and CELLxGENE, and the staff cannot always attend to all issues. Currently, there are 215 open tickets on the GitHub Cell Ontology issue tracker (github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology) and another 248 on UBERON (github.com/obophenotype/uberont).

Due to the sociotechnical complexity, the terms are still being worked on currently and will be only available after the time of writing.

7.4.4.5 Discussion

In this report, we exemplified a biocuration process of extracting information and modeling that in knowledge bases. This narrative report illustrates a few of the challenges of the biocurators and ontologists such as the imprecisions in reports in contrast with the data, contradictions between language used across articles and knowledge bases, terminological hesitancy in reports when classifying concepts (using "-like" endings) and the dimension of the task of terms that *can* be classified.

Besides the scientific tasks, biocuration work demands technical ability of parsing information for incorporation in knowledge bases. For the OBO Foundry ontologies, widely used by the members of the Human Cell Atlas consortium, the technical barrier is steep, requiring a good grasp of Semantic Web tools and concepts, the

⁶⁶ obophenotype.github.io/cell-ontology/contributing/

installation and use of the Protégé software, fluency in the GitHub workflow of software contributions and the technical decisions of the particular community (e.g. which ontologies are imported, what design patterns are used). Also, a good amount of soft social skills are needed, as one needs to communicate with the ontology maintainers and attend training and regular meetings to be able to contribute to the catalog directly – even for a small contribution, such as adding "laminar cells" to the catalog.

While it is possible to propose new terms in the Cell Ontology Issue Tracker and wait for the staff to make the changes, this does not guarantee a term will be added. The Cell Ontology is a small decentralized community handling a complex project with many stakeholders, and the staff is usually overloaded. It still has the great merit of being an open community, as the members are very helpful and generous, so anyone who is willing to go through the tech barrier *can* contribute – even graduate students in Brazil– it just requires a sizable dedication.

The Wikidata-based workflow for editing Wikidata is arguably faster and more flexible, being complementary to the OBO Foundry infrastructure. It includes the option of direct edits in the graphical web interface, which made it possible to quickly connect the "Grandry" and "Herbst" corpuscles to the "Pacinian-like" and "Meissner-like" upper classes. It also is amenable to simple scripting, enabling the quick creation of tens of classes in a couple of hours requiring only Google Spreadsheets (in a MIRACL-based format) and a Python script, tools that are familiar to most computational biologists.⁶⁷ The important information on Wikidata can be pulled with a couple of API requests knitted in a userscript, easing the reuse of information from the platform on OBO Foundry ontologies. In this example, we modeled knowledge about lamellar cells and sensory corpuscles quickly, providing the international community with knowledge in a hierarchical organization, with literature references and a seamless connection to the web of data (as shown in

⁶⁷ Of note, Python programming is taught in the first semester of the Biomedical Sciences undergraduate major at the University of São Paulo at least since 2014. We consider it reasonable to assume that it is also not unfamiliar to early career biomedical researchers.

Figure {{lamellar_sparql}}, a process that led to new terms being incorporated into UBERON and CL.

Besides the technical aspects, we illustrate how the 4-way classification system of cells provides a useful way of organizing concepts when parsing a scientific text. It allows us to clearly tease apart what is valid only for an experimental technoclass or a subspecies infraclass (e.g. the size of the Pekin duck Pacinian-like corpuscle) and what is important to record at the species level or at the archeclass (such as the lamellar cells, eventually incorporated in the Cell Ontology). Moreover, the dive into the philosophical discussions pertaining to classification of cells is essential for making the decisions during the curation process, namely deciding (1) what should be considered a cell type/class and (2) what should be actively curated into our models of the biological world.

To sum up, we hope that this narrative example contributed to clarifying how this last chapter of the thesis ties together with the previous four and illustrates the thought processes involved in the large-scale biocuration of cell classes. Particularly, we hope it shows that classification of cells is not a trivial process, and the development of technical protocols, tools and infrastructure (such as developed for Wikidata here) have a core role at the root of how we organize cell types. The connection with the Human Cell Atlas more generally and the bioinformatics task of analyzing single-cell RNA-seq in particular stands at a basal level. The kind of work here is necessary for the development of precise annotation and metadata systems, which in turn enable large-scale reuse, integration and interpretation of biological data. Every new class that is formalized using a proper identifiers system (such as the Cell Ontology or Wikidata) enables the community to improve their metadata. It is composed of small advances, such as the one pursued here: be it on CELLxGENE, on the EBI Expression Atlas, or anywhere else, now we have a way to annotate lamellar cells properly.

8. Conclusion

In this thesis we described the process of integrating a Wikidata-based workflow into the state-of-the-art of curation of information about cell types. Taking the Human Cell Atlas as a starting point, we delved into how knowledge about cells is classified and came up with technical, theoretical and social contributions to improve the status quo. We started from a naive initial approach on using Wikidata directly to model information about the cell types we know. We grew to see that the catalog of cell types is still far from resolved and potentially much larger than a few hundred classes, and the very definition of cell type still needs philosophical work. We also grew to see that Wikidata, while fast and flexible, is yet to be used directly by the research and knowledge management community.

Besides the written works that were published (and the others we expect to publish after the thesis defense) the project has some legacies worth mentioning. First is the catalog of cell classes itself, the biggest organized collection of cell classes so far. The collection is alive and growing on Wikidata, directly connect and organizing content on Wikipedia, one of the world's top 10 visited websites⁶⁸. More important than the collection of cell types, perhaps, is the digital infrastructure and curation methodology built in Wikidata, with its multilingual infrastructure and openness. Also relevant are the methods to connect it and support OBO Foundry ontologies, impacting, in that way, biocuration efforts in the Human Cell Atlas and beyond. We hope that these tools will be of use in the upcoming years, as we deal more and more with the collective knowledge produced by large-scale, globally connected life sciences – and the powerful Large Language Models coming into play.

It took 2 centuries from Robert Hooke's observation of cork alveoli in 1665 to Theodor Schwann's description of a cell theory in 1839, claiming that the cell was the elementary unit of not only plants – as mentioned by Schleiden in 1838 – but also

⁶⁸ See en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=List_of_most-visited_websites&oldid=1226555137 for the current rank as of April 2024, when Wikipedia ranks as the 7th most visited website.

animals. Then, it took 2 more centuries to the rise of the Human Cell Atlas and the powerful single-cell omics techniques. Gradually, we, as humanity, build our collective knowledge of the elementary parts of the human body and the way they are molded and directed by the genome to perform their physiological functions. This thesis is a humble contribution to this endeavor, making a small contribution to the progress of the way we organize our knowledge about the diversity of cells in the 21st century.

9. References

- AEVERMANN, B. D. et al. Cell type discovery using single-cell transcriptomics: implications for ontological representation. **Human Molecular Genetics**, v. 27, n. R1, p. R40–R47, mar. 2018.
- ANDO, Y.; KWON, A. T.-J.; SHIN, J. W. An era of single-cell genomics consortia. **Experimental & Molecular Medicine**, v. 52, n. 9, p. 1409–1418, set. 2020.
- ARAKAKI, A. C. S.; CASTRO, F. F. DE; ARAKAKI, F. A. Painel de informação sobre a COVID-19: consultas SPARQL na Wikidata. **AtoZ**, v. 9, n. 2, p. 160, dez. 2020.
- ARP, R.; SMITH, B.; SPEAR, A. D. **Building ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology**. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2015.
- ASHBURNER, M. et al. Gene Ontology: tool for the unification of biology. **Nature Genetics**, v. 25, n. 1, p. 25–29, maio 2000.
- BAKKEN, T. et al. Cell type discovery and representation in the era of high-content single cell phenotyping. **BMC Bioinformatics**, v. 18, n. S17, p. 559, dez. 2017.
- BARD, J.; RHEE, S. Y.; ASHBURNER, M. An ontology for cell types. **Genome Biology**, v. 6, n. 2, p. R21, 2005.
- BASTIAN, F. B. et al. The Bgee suite: integrated curated expression atlas and comparative transcriptomics in animals. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 49, n. D1, p. D831–D847, 8 jan. 2021.
- BIGAEVA, E. et al. Understanding human gut diseases at single-cell resolution. **Human Molecular Genetics**, v. 29, n. R1, p. R51–R58, 30 set. 2020.
- BLANCO-MELO, D. et al. Imbalanced Host Response to SARS-CoV-2 Drives Development of COVID-19. **Cell**, v. 181, n. 5, p. 1036–1045.e9, 28 maio 2020a.
- BLANCO-MELO, D. et al. Imbalanced Host Response to SARS-CoV-2 Drives Development of COVID-19. **Cell**, v. 181, n. 5, p. 1036–1045.e9, 28 maio 2020b.
- BÖRNER, K. et al. Anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas. **Nature Cell Biology**, v. 23, n. 11, p. 1117–1128, nov. 2021.
- BRASILEIRO, F. et al. **Applying a Multi-Level Modeling Theory to Assess Taxonomic Hierarchies in Wikidata**. Proceedings of the 25th International Conference Companion on World Wide Web - WWW '16 Companion. **Anais...ACM Press**, 2016. Disponível em: <<https://doi.org/10.1145%2F2872518.2891117>>
- BUCUR, C.-I. et al. Nanopublication-based semantic publishing and reviewing: a field study with formalization papers. **PeerJ Computer Science**, v. 9, p. e1159, 21 fev. 2023.
- BURGSTALLER-MUEHLBACHER, S. et al. Wikidata as a semantic framework for the Gene Wiki initiative. **Database**, v. 2016, p. baw015, 1 jan. 2016.
- CHOW, V. et al. Global hypercoagulability in patients with schizophrenia receiving long-term antipsychotic therapy. **Schizophrenia Research**, v. 162, n. 1–3, p. 175–182, mar. 2015.
- CLEVERS, H. et al. What Is Your Conceptual Definition of "Cell Type" in the Context of a Mature Organism? **Cell Systems**, v. 4, n. 3, p. 255–259, 2017.
- COLE, B. et al. Plant single-cell solutions for energy and the environment. **Communications Biology**, v. 4, n. 1, p. 962, 12 ago. 2021.
- CZI SINGLE-CELL BIOLOGY PROGRAM et al. **CZ CELL×GENE Discover: A single-cell data platform for scalable exploration, analysis and modeling of**

aggregated data. bioRxiv, , 2 nov. 2023. Disponível em:
<<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.10.30.563174v1>>. Acesso em: 7 nov. 2023

DECET, M.; SOUKUP, S.-F. Endophilin-A/SH3GL2 calcium switch for synaptic autophagy induction is impaired by a Parkinson's risk variant. **Autophagy**, p. 1–3, 17 abr. 2023.

DIEHL, A. D. et al. The Cell Ontology 2016: enhanced content, modularization, and ontology interoperability. **Journal of Biomedical Semantics**, v. 7, n. 1, p. 44, dez. 2016.

ELMENTAITE, R. et al. Single-Cell Sequencing of Developing Human Gut Reveals Transcriptional Links to Childhood Crohn's Disease. **Developmental Cell**, v. 55, n. 6, p. 771–783.e5, dez. 2020.

FALLIS, D. Toward an epistemology of *Wikipedia*. **Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology**, v. 59, n. 10, p. 1662–1674, ago. 2008a.

FALLIS, D. Toward an epistemology of *Wikipedia*. **Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology**, v. 59, n. 10, p. 1662–1674, ago. 2008b.

FINN, R. D.; GARDNER, P. P.; BATEMAN, A. Making your database available through Wikipedia: the pros and cons. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 40, n. D1, p. D9–D12, 1 jan. 2012.

FRANZÉN, O.; GAN, L.-M.; BJÖRKEGREN, J. L. M. PanglaoDB: a web server for exploration of mouse and human single-cell RNA sequencing data. **Database**, v. 2019, jan. 2019.

FÜLLGRABE, A. et al. Guidelines for reporting single-cell RNA-seq experiments. **Nature Biotechnology**, v. 38, n. 12, p. 1384–1386, dez. 2020.

GANDAL, M. J. et al. Transcriptome-wide isoform-level dysregulation in ASD, schizophrenia, and bipolar disorder. **Science**, v. 362, n. 6420, p. eaat8127, 14 dez. 2018.

GROTH, P.; GIBSON, A.; VELTEROP, J. The anatomy of a nanopublication. **ISU**, v. 30, n. 1–2, p. 51–56, set. 2010.

GUPTA, A.; MACKERETH, S. Definitions. Em: ZALTA, E. N.; NODELMAN, U. (Eds.). **The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy**. Fall 2023 ed. [s.l.] Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2023.

HATTON, I. A. et al. The human cell count and size distribution. **Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences**, v. 120, n. 39, p. e2303077120, 26 set. 2023.

HELMY, M.; CRITS-CHRISTOPH, A.; BADER, G. D. Ten Simple Rules for Developing Public Biological Databases. **PLoS Comput Biol**, v. 12, n. 11, p. e1005128, nov. 2016.

HOSSEINI BEGHAEIRAVERI, S. A. et al. Wikidata subsetting: Approaches, tools, and evaluation. **Semantic Web**, p. 1–27, 27 dez. 2023.

HUBMAP CONSORTIUM et al. The human body at cellular resolution: the NIH Human Biomolecular Atlas Program. **Nature**, v. 574, n. 7777, p. 187–192, 10 out. 2019.

HUNTLEY, R. P. et al. The GOA database: gene Ontology annotation updates for 2015. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 43, n. Database issue, p. D1057-1063, jan. 2015.

III, J. W. H. et al. A Gene Wiki for Community Annotation of Gene Function. **PLOS Biology**, v. 6, n. 7, p. e175, 8 jul. 2008.

JACKSON, R. et al. OBO Foundry in 2021: operationalizing open data principles to

evaluate ontologies. v. 2021, 2021.

JUPP, S. et al. A New Ontology Lookup Service at EMBL-EBI. 2015.

KARLSSON, M. et al. A single-cell type transcriptomics map of human tissues. **Science Advances**, v. 7, n. 31, p. eabh2169, 30 jul. 2021.

KAZAKOV, Y.; KRÖTZSCH, M.; SIMANČÍK, F. ELK Reasoner: Architecture and Evaluation. [s.d.].

KLEMENT, K. Russell's Logical Atomism. Em: ZALTA, E. N. (Ed.). **The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy**. Spring 2020 ed. [s.l.] Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2020.

KOROTKEVICH, G. et al. **Fast gene set enrichment analysis**. bioRxiv, , 1 fev. 2021. Disponível em: <<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/060012v3>>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2024

LABRA-GAYO, J. E. WShEx: A language to describe and validate Wikibase entities. [s.d.].

LAYEGH, A. et al. **Wiki-based Prompts for Enhancing Relation Extraction using Language Models**. Proceedings of the 39th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing. **Anais...: SAC '24**. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Maio 2024. Disponível em: <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3605098.3635949>>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2024

LUBIANA, T. et al. **Guidelines for reporting cell types: the MIRACL standard**. arXiv, , 25 maio 2022a. Disponível em: <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2204.09673>>. Acesso em: 6 jun. 2024

LUBIANA, T. et al. **WikiGOA: Gene set enrichment analysis based on Wikipedia and the Gene Ontology**. , 17 set. 2022b. Disponível em: <<http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2022.09.15.508149>>. Acesso em: 2 abr. 2024

LUBIANA, T. et al. Ten quick tips for harnessing the power of ChatGPT in computational biology. **PLOS Computational Biology**, v. 19, n. 8, p. e1011319, 10 ago. 2023.

LUBIANA, T.; NAKAYA, H. I. **Towards a pragmatic definition of cell type**. , 4 jan. 2021. Disponível em: <<https://www.authorea.com/users/384178/articles/501068-towards-a-pragmatic-definition-of-cell-type?commit=8b84e0b133b310eb35e733805cdba0e00cc8227a>>. Acesso em: 20 abr. 2024

MARTENS, M. et al. WikiPathways: connecting communities. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 49, n. D1, p. D613–D621, nov. 2020.

MARTENS, M. et al. WikiPathways: connecting communities. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 49, n. D1, p. D613–D621, 8 jan. 2021.

MATENTZOGLU, N. et al. Ontology Development Kit: a toolkit for building, maintaining and standardizing biomedical ontologies. **Database**, v. 2022, jan. 2022a.

MATENTZOGLU, N. et al. A Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM). **Database**, v. 2022, jan. 2022b.

MCMURRY, J. A. et al. Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. **PLoS Biol**, v. 15, n. 6, p. e2001414, jun. 2017.

MEEHAN, T. F. et al. Logical Development of the Cell Ontology. **BMC Bioinformatics**, v. 12, n. 1, p. 6, dez. 2011.

MELDAL, B. H. M. et al. Complex Portal 2022: new curation frontiers. **Nucleic Acids**

Research, v. 50, n. D1, p. D578–D586, out. 2021.

MILACIC, M. et al. The Reactome Pathway Knowledgebase 2024. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 52, n. D1, p. D672–D678, 5 jan. 2024.

MILLER, J. A. et al. Common cell type nomenclature for the mammalian brain. **eLife**, v. 9, dez. 2020.

MONS, B. et al. Calling on a million minds for community annotation in WikiProteins. **Genome Biology**, v. 9, n. 5, p. R89, 28 maio 2008.

MUKHERJEE, S. **A canção da célula: As descobertas da medicina e o novo humano**. Tradução: Berilo Vargas. São Paulo, SP: Companhia das Letras, 2023.

MUNGALL, C. et al. Uberon: towards a comprehensive multi-species anatomy ontology. **Nature Precedings**, ago. 2009.

MUNN, K.; SMITH, B. **Applied ontology: an introduction**. Frankfurt am Main: Ontos Verl, 2008.

MUSEN, M. A. The Protégé Project: A Look Back and a Look Forward. **AI matters**, v. 1, n. 4, p. 4–12, jun. 2015.

NAVEED, H. et al. **A Comprehensive Overview of Large Language Models**. arXiv, , 9 abr. 2024. Disponível em: <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2307.06435>>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2024

NEUBARTH, N. L. et al. Meissner corpuscles and their spatially intermingled afferents underlie gentle touch perception. **Science**, v. 368, n. 6497, p. eabb2751, 19 jun. 2020.

NIELSEN, F. Å.; MIETCHEN, D.; WILLIGHAGEN, E. Scholia, Scientometrics and Wikidata. Em: **Lecture Notes in Computer Science**. [s.l.] Springer International Publishing, 2017. p. 237–259.

NIKOLAEV, Y. A. et al. Lamellar cells in Pacinian and Meissner corpuscles are touch sensors. **Science Advances**, v. 6, n. 51, p. eabe6393, 18 dez. 2020.

OSUMI-SUTHERLAND, D. et al. Cell type ontologies of the Human Cell Atlas. **Nature Cell Biology**, v. 23, n. 11, p. 1129–1135, nov. 2021.

OVERTON, J. A. et al. Reporting and connecting cell type names and gating definitions through ontologies. **BMC Bioinformatics**, v. 20, n. S5, abr. 2019.

PAN, S. et al. Unifying Large Language Models and Knowledge Graphs: A Roadmap. **IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering**, p. 1–20, 2024.

PANINA, Y. et al. Human Cell Atlas and cell-type authentication for regenerative medicine. **Exp Mol Med**, v. 52, n. 9, p. 1443–1451, set. 2020.

PANIZZUTTI, B. et al. Transcriptional Modulation of the Hippo Signaling Pathway by Drugs Used to Treat Bipolar Disorder and Schizophrenia. **International Journal of Molecular Sciences**, v. 22, n. 13, p. 7164, jan. 2021.

PAPATHEODOROU, I. et al. Expression Atlas update: from tissues to single cells. **Nucleic Acids Research**, v. 48, n. D1, p. D77–D83, 8 jan. 2020.

PELLISSIER TANON, T. et al. **From Freebase to Wikidata: The Great Migration**. Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on World Wide Web. **Anais...** Em: WWW '16: 25TH INTERNATIONAL WORLD WIDE WEB CONFERENCE. Montréal Québec Canada: International World Wide Web Conferences Steering Committee, 11 abr. 2016. Disponível em: <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2872427.2874809>>. Acesso em: 9 nov. 2023

Petilla terminology: nomenclature of features of GABAergic interneurons of the

cerebral cortex. **Nat Rev Neurosci**, v. 9, n. 7, p. 557–568, jul. 2008.

PFUNDNER, A. et al. Utilizing the Wikidata System to Improve the Quality of Medical Content in Wikipedia in Diverse Languages: A Pilot Study. **Journal of Medical Internet Research**, v. 17, n. 5, p. e4163, 5 maio 2015.

POPESCU, L. M.; FAUSSONE-PELLEGRINI, M.-S. TELOCYTES – a case of serendipity: the winding way from Interstitial Cells of Cajal (ICC), lessigreater via less/igreater Interstitial Cajal-Like Cells (ICLC) to TELOCYTES. **J Cellular Molecular Medi**, v. 14, n. 4, p. 729–740, abr. 2010.

POPPER, K. **Logik der Forschung**. Wien: Springer-Verlag, 1934.

PUTMAN, T. et al. ChlamBase: a curated model organism database for the Chlamydia research community. **Database**, v. 2019, p. baz041, 1 jan. 2019.

PUTMAN, T. E. et al. WikiGenomes: an open web application for community consumption and curation of gene annotation data in Wikidata. **Database**, v. 2017, p. bax025, 1 jan. 2017.

QUAKE, S. R. The cell as a bag of RNA. **Trends in Genetics**, v. 37, n. 12, p. 1064–1068, dez. 2021.

RAERINNE, J. Popperian ecology is a delusion. **Ecology and Evolution**, v. 14, n. 3, p. e11106, mar. 2024.

RASBERRY, L. et al. Robustifying Scholia: paving the way for knowledge discovery and research assessment through Wikidata. **RIO**, v. 5, maio 2019.

REGEV, A. et al. The Human Cell Atlas. **eLife**, v. 6, p. e27041, 5 dez. 2017.

ROZENBLATT-ROSEN, O. et al. The Human Cell Atlas: from vision to reality. **Nature**, v. 550, n. 7677, p. 451–453, out. 2017.

RUTZ, A. et al. The LOTUS initiative for open knowledge management in natural products research. **eLife**, v. 11, maio 2022.

SAORÍN, T.; PASTOR-SÁNCHEZ, J.-A.; BAÑOS-MORENO, M.-J. Uso de Wikidata y Wikipedia para la generación asistida de un vocabulario estructurado multilingüe sobre la pandemia de Covid-19. **EPI**, set. 2020.

SCHULZE-KREMER, S.; SMITH, B. Ontologies for the life sciences. Em: JORDE, L. B. et al. (Eds.). **Encyclopedia of Genetics, Genomics, Proteomics and Bioinformatics**. 1. ed. [s.l.] Wiley, 2005.

SELTMANN, S. et al. CELDA - an ontology for the comprehensive representation of cells in complex systems. **BMC Bioinformatics**, v. 14, n. 1, p. 228, 17 jul. 2013.

SHAFEE, T. et al. Ten quick tips for editing Wikidata. **PLOS Computational Biology**, v. 19, n. 7, p. e1011235, 20 jul. 2023.

SIB SWISS INSTITUTE OF BIOINFORMATICS RDF GROUP MEMBERS et al. The SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics Semantic Web of data. **Nucleic Acids Research**, p. gkad902, 25 out. 2023.

STECCO, C. et al. The fasciocytes: A new cell devoted to fascial gliding regulation. **Clinical Anatomy**, v. 31, n. 5, p. 667–676, abr. 2018.

Submit a Topic Page to PLOS Computational Biology and Wikipedia | PLOS Computational Biology. Disponível em:
<<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1006137>>.
Acesso em: 10 jun. 2024.

SUBRAMANIAN, A. et al. Gene set enrichment analysis: a knowledge-based approach for interpreting genome-wide expression profiles. **Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America**, v. 102, n. 43, p.

15545–15550, 25 out. 2005.

SVENSSON, V.; BELTRAME, E. DA V.; PACHTER, L. A curated database reveals trends in single-cell transcriptomics. **Database**, v. 2020, 2020.

TAN, S. Z. K. et al. **Digital Evolution: Novo Nordisk's Shift to Ontology-Based Data Management**. arXiv, , 10 maio 2024. Disponível em: <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2405.05413>>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2024

TARSKI, A. The Semantic Conception of Truth: and the Foundations of Semantics. **Philosophy and Phenomenological Research**, v. 4, n. 3, p. 341, mar. 1944.

THE FAIRSHARING COMMUNITY et al. FAIRsharing as a community approach to standards, repositories and policies. **Nature Biotechnology**, v. 37, n. 4, p. 358–367, abr. 2019.

THE GENE ONTOLOGY CONSORTIUM et al. The Gene Ontology knowledgebase in 2023. **GENETICS**, v. 224, n. 1, p. iyad031, 4 maio 2023.

THE OBI CONSORTIUM et al. The OBO Foundry: coordinated evolution of ontologies to support biomedical data integration. **Nature Biotechnology**, v. 25, n. 11, p. 1251–1255, nov. 2007.

THOREAU, H. D. **Walden, or, Life in the Woods**. Boston: Ticknor and Fields, 1854.

TORO, S. et al. **Dynamic Retrieval Augmented Generation of Ontologies using Artificial Intelligence (DRAGON-AI)**. arXiv, , 17 dez. 2023. Disponível em: <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2312.10904>>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2024

TURKI, H. et al. Representing COVID-19 information in collaborative knowledge graphs: The case of Wikidata. **SW**, v. 13, n. 2, p. 233–264, fev. 2022a.

TURKI, H. et al. Using logical constraints to validate statistical information about disease outbreaks in collaborative knowledge graphs: the case of COVID-19 epidemiology in Wikidata. **PeerJ Computer Science**, v. 8, p. e1085, set. 2022b.

VICKARYOUS, M. K.; HALL, B. K. Human cell type diversity, evolution, development, and classification with special reference to cells derived from the neural crest. **Biol. Rev.**, v. 81, n. 03, p. 425, jun. 2006.

VILLANI, A.-C. et al. Single-cell RNA-seq reveals new types of human blood dendritic cells, monocytes, and progenitors. **Science**, v. 356, n. 6335, abr. 2017.

VRANDEČIĆ, D.; PINTSCHER, L.; KRÖTZSCH, M. **Wikidata: The Making Of**. Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023. **Anais...** Em: WWW '23: THE ACM WEB CONFERENCE 2023. Austin TX USA: ACM, 30 abr. 2023. Disponível em: <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3543873.3585579>>. Acesso em: 8 nov. 2023

WAAGMEESTER, A. et al. Wikidata as a FAIR knowledge graph for the life sciences. out. 2019.

WAAGMEESTER, A. et al. Wikidata as a knowledge graph for the life sciences. **eLife**, v. 9, p. e52614, 17 mar. 2020.

WAAGMEESTER, A. et al. A protocol for adding knowledge to Wikidata: aligning resources on human coronaviruses. **BMC Biol**, v. 19, n. 1, jan. 2021a.

WAAGMEESTER, A. et al. A protocol for adding knowledge to Wikidata: aligning resources on human coronaviruses. **BMC Biology**, v. 19, n. 1, p. 12, 22 jan. 2021b.

WALDROP, M. Big data: Wikiomics. **Nature**, v. 455, n. 7209, p. 22–25, set. 2008.

WANG, S. et al. Leveraging the Cell Ontology to classify unseen cell types. **Nat Commun**, v. 12, n. 1, set. 2021.

WIJESOORIYA, K. et al. Urgent need for consistent standards in functional

enrichment analysis. **PLOS Computational Biology**, v. 18, n. 3, p. e1009935, 9 mar. 2022.

WILKINSON, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. **Scientific Data**, v. 3, n. 1, p. 160018, 15 mar. 2016.

WINSTON, J. E. **Describing species: practical taxonomic procedure for biologists**. New York, NY: Columbia Univ. Press, 1999.

WOO, J. J. et al. The complement system in schizophrenia: where are we now and what's next? **Molecular Psychiatry**, v. 25, n. 1, p. 114–130, jan. 2020.

YOKOYAMA, S. Genetic polymorphisms of bone marrow stromal cell antigen-1 (BST-1/CD157): implications for immune/inflammatory dysfunction in neuropsychiatric disorders. **Frontiers in Immunology**, v. 14, p. 1197265, 29 maio 2023.

YON RHEE, S. et al. Use and misuse of the gene ontology annotations. **Nature Reviews Genetics**, v. 9, n. 7, p. 509–515, jul. 2008.